

HOLPA implementation guide

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1. Guidelines for implementing HOLPA at the farm-household level

This section provides details on practical aspects of implementing HOLPA for farm-households inside an agroecology living landscape (ALL). ALL's are areas with a clearly defined boundary, including multiple communities, within which research on agroecology will be conducted.

1.1. Tool overview

The farm-household level HOLPA comprises a household survey (see Appendix 2) and a fieldwork survey (Appendix 3), implemented using an ODK-based digital survey to facilitate data collation and timely quality checking. These surveys together provide data that can be used to compare socio-ecological contexts, adherence to 13 agroecological principles, and key performance indicator (KPI) scores for 18 performance themes. Additional information for the three modules can be collected through desk-work (e.g. analysing existing survey data or remotely sensed sources), focus groups (e.g. for assessment of farmer agency at the community level), and key informant interviews (e.g. to gather information on national or regional policy priorities and food system challenges).

The global HOLPA surveys have been coded for use in Kobo Toolbox in English (Appendix 4). The HOLPA survey can be answered using a tablet or smartphone with the KoboCollect app installed. Users may need to translate the survey into the appropriate language prior to data collection. The survey form can be configured to add as many additional questions and additional response options as needed, but users are advised to keep the core set of questions and response options intact to ensure indicators can be correctly computed and data is comparable across sites.

1.2. Sampling methodology

For the household survey, to ensure gender, youth and social inclusion, we recommended that a male and a female are chosen alternatively as respondents so that 50% of the HOLPA survey respondents are male and the other 50% are female. To capture youth aspects, we recommended that 30% of the farms selected for sampling are managed by young farmers, e.g. below the age of 30 years old.

1.3. Resources required

Many of the HOLPA survey questions have multiple-choice responses facilitating fast data collection. Some of the questions (e.g. under *Productivity*, which investigate the types and amounts of crops, livestock, and fish produced and harvested) require quantitative (numeric) answers that need to be input for each of the three main crop/livestock/fish species. Other questions, particularly related to social performance indicators, require oral responses and these should be recorded by the enumerator using a voice recorder or the audio recording option on the tablet used for data collection, to allow full post-collection analysis. For all questions, and particularly those that are

open-ended, it is greatly beneficial to have a well-established rapport with the participants prior to undertaking the survey.

The resources required to collect data from 200 farms, surveyed at the whole farm level, are likely to include as a minimum:

- 1 enumerator x 100 days (or 2 enumerators x 50 days, based on the number of farms)
- 1 handheld tablet per enumerator with KoboCollect (or another ODK-compatible app) installed
- 1 device with camera for taking photographs per enumerator
- 1 GPS per enumerator
- 1 rucksack
- Motorbike or car to move between sites
- 1 trowel (handheld shovel to take soil samples)
- 30 cm ruler or soil probe
- 2 * 1 L airtight bags per farm
- Metal wire flag (length ~50 cm, thickness ~0.08 mm) per enumerator
- Hydrogen peroxide (volume ~50 ml) per farm
- Marker pens for labeling
- Notepad + pen

This assumes an average survey rate of two farms per day. For farms that are in close proximity the survey rate can be higher. All enumerators will need to be trained prior to data collection.

1.4. Enumerator training

Enumerators need training prior to data collection to ensure i) a good understanding of the survey purpose and of all concepts used in question and response options, ii) social sensitivities to be aware of, e.g. potential for cultural anxiety related to providing information on land tenure, and agreed approaches for handling these, iii) potential errors to avoid, e.g. mismatch between the total income received and the breakdown by source. Enumerators can be trained together in a half or full day workshop. In addition, we recommend new enumerators are accompanied for the first few days of data collection by a project researcher or experienced enumerator familiar with administering the HOLPA survey, to demonstrate how to build a good rapport with each respondent, how to help respondents provide relevant answers to more complex questions, and how to conduct the field survey for farms of different sizes and layouts. It is important to train the enumerators to save and submit completed surveys at the end of each day.

2. HOLPA Key Performance Indicator Protocols

2.1. Indicator protocol format

Each indicator has a protocol for use, which describes the indicator purpose, how to collect data for it, and references for further information. The protocol format is as follows:

Indicator	Name of indicator
Theme	Performance framework theme
Purpose of indicator	Rationale for monitoring this indicator
Data source	Proposed data source, e.g. farmer recall, farm records, household survey or interview, focus group, transect, plot measurements, local expert, satellite data.
Measurement	Recommended measurement
Measurement units	Recommended measurement units
Guidance on measurement	Guidance on how to correctly collect data for and calculate the recommended measurement, including tips on where common measurement errors occur and how to avoid them.
Guidance on data entry and reporting	Guidance on how to report data in a transparent and consistent way to facilitate understanding and comparability. This includes any data conversion steps (e.g. to code qualitative data, or convert tree height and diameter measurements to estimated carbon stocks).
Indicator interpretation and threshold setting	How to interpret the measurements used for this indicator and thresholds or reference points to use for defining sustainable and unsustainable values ideally justified with scientific literature. Thresholds can be set in two ways: 1. Using absolute values, e.g. setting minimum and maximum limits based on scientific literature or expert opinion, 2. Using relative values, e.g. compared to the best and worst values in the dataset.
Limitations	Limitations of the measurement method and ideas for alternative measurements to consider in future research and projects.
References	Key references on the indicator

2.2.Environmental KPIs

2.2.1. Crop, livestock and fish diversity

Indicator	Crop, livestock and fish diversity
Theme	Agrobiodiversity
Purpose of indicator	Relevant for the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework Target 10 on ‘Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture’, where the Agrobiodiversity Index is a complementary indicator (CBD/COP/15/L.26). The Agrobiodiversity Index includes various measures of agrobiodiversity, including crop and livestock diversity.
Data source	Household survey
Measurement	Gap in diversity of crop varieties (or species) and fish and livestock breeds (or species) on the farm, measured using data on richness relative to the local maximum.
Measurement units	Count with associated production area recorded in hectares, disaggregated by crop and animal species and ideally also variety/breed
Guidance on measurement	<p>This indicator can be calculated by collecting data on the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Count of crop varieties and species, and the relative area occupied. • Count of livestock breeds and species. • Count of fish breeds and species. <p>These data can be collected as part of a household survey. To verify the data, and if time allows, the researcher and farmer could conduct a transect of the farm and discuss and record where different crops are planted.</p>
Guidance on data entry and reporting	Be sure to use the same area units for all species/varieties/breeds, so that diversity indices can be calculated. Crop and livestock varieties/breeds and species names should be stored in the local language and also using their scientific and English names to enable comparisons across sites. A local agronomist may need to help identify the scientific and English names.
Indicator interpretation and threshold setting	
Limitations	
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (FAO, 2019; Jones et al., 2021)

2.2.2. Insect, mammal and tree diversity

Indicator	Insect, mammal and tree diversity
Theme	Biodiversity
Purpose of indicator	Relevant for global climate mitigation targets (the Paris Agreement) and the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework Target 10 on ‘Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture’. Biodiversity indicators selected to be easy to use and scalable, in line with Essential Biodiversity Variables 2020 initiative recommendations.
Data source	Household survey, field survey
Measurement	Diversity of insect, mammal and tree species per hectare of farmland, measured using data on richness, abundance, and density, and standardised to a scale of 0 to 100 to enable data aggregation.
Measurement units	Count with associated production area recorded in hectares, disaggregated by insect/mammal/tree species, tree maturity, and local/exotic origin.
Guidance on measurement	<p>This indicator can be calculated by collecting data on the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Richness and abundance of mammals, insects and trees <p>These data can be collected as part of household and field surveys.</p> <p>To enable more indepth tree data analysis, e.g. to support efforts to monitor native species, ancient specimens, and carbon sequestration on-farm, additional data can be collected on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proportion of native tree species Proportion of mature trees (>50cm diameter at breast height, or height >10m)
Guidance on data entry and reporting	Species names (if available) should be stored in the local language and also using their scientific and English names to enable comparisons across sites.
Indicator interpretation and threshold setting	
Limitations	
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (Landmann et al., 2023) (Navarro et al., 2017)

2.2.3. Landscape complexity

Indicator	Landscape complexity
Theme	Biodiversity
Purpose of indicator	Relevant for the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework Goal B on conserving services provided by ecosystems and Target 10 on ‘Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture’ (CBD/COP/15/L.26). Aligns with SDG indicators 2.4.1 and 15.3.1 on proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture. Maintaining at least 20% natural and semi-natural habitat in agricultural landscapes is important for safeguarding food security, biodiversity, and ecosystem services (Garibaldi et al. 2020).
Data source	Satellite data, or direct measurement by walking around natural or semi-natural features on-farm with a GPS. In both cases, the field or farm boundary needs delineating.
Measurement	Percentage of farmland area that is covered with natural or semi-natural vegetation.
Measurement units	Percentage cover, disaggregated by type of feature
Guidance on measurement	<p>We discuss three options for measurement, i) farmer estimates validated through field surveys (default option in HOLPA), ii) using satellite imagery, iii) direct measurement.</p> <p>Farmer estimates</p> <p>A simplistic and rapid way to assess this indicator is to ask respondents to estimate the proportion of their farmland covered by natural or semi-natural vegetation (e.g. bushland, fallow land, hedgerows, natural grassland, ponds, lakes, forest patches). This can be validated by assessing the proportion of natural vegetation contained within three 10x10m plots sampled on the farm, taking a GPS point to allow for satellite-based analysis of the proportion of natural vegetation at larger spatial scales.</p> <p>Satellite imagery</p> <p>Natural or semi-natural features on farmland (see Definitions) are often visible on high resolution (<50m and ideally <10m) satellite imagery, such as Google Earth imagery. In a GIS, import the boundary of the field or farm of interest (see Definitions). If no boundary is available, generate a 1km diameter circular plot around each fieldwork plot, using a GPS point collected at the centre of the plot on the ground. In Google Earth Engine, digitise all visible natural or semi-natural features within the area of interest. Calculate the area of land with natural or semi-natural features to obtain an estimate of the share of land covered with natural or semi-natural features. Where possible this should be verified on the ground.</p>

Examples:

Known problems:

- Distinguishing between tree canopies and shade can be difficult.
- Determining what is farmland and what is natural land can be difficult.
- Distinguishing between grass and shrubs is not always easy.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The condition of the vegetation is an unknown but important variable. <p>Direct measurement</p> <p>Natural or semi-natural features coverage can be determined by walking around the field or farm of interest including all natural or semi-natural features, recording the boundaries with a handheld GPS. These areas can be imported into a GIS and used to obtain an estimate of the percentage of farmland covered with natural or semi-natural features.</p> <p>Definitions:</p> <p>Farmland includes areas delineated with generally linear boundaries and inside which there are one of the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Regular rows of woody or herbaceous crops Visible tractor tracks Visible rows of tilled soil Evidence of irrigation, e.g. area is much greener than surrounding land, or visible sprinkler system Hay bales in field <p>Natural or semi-natural features on farmland includes linear or areal features on farmland comprising:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Single or small groups of trees or shrubs not regularly arranged within the field. These include woodlots, forest remnants. Narrow strips of trees, shrubs or other vegetation along field edge that have no visible management, e.g., are not arranged in rows, no signs of tractor or tillage activity, irregular shape. These include hedgerows, flower strips, grass borders. Other natural or semi-natural features, including long-term (>6 month) fallow land, rivers, ponds. <p>This list of natural or semi-natural features should be discussed and adjusted with local communities and/or based on expert knowledge of the context</p>
Guidance on data entry and reporting	Record which natural or semi-natural features were detected, e.g. hedgerows, flower strip. For fallow land, record how long the land has been in fallow.
Indicator interpretation and threshold setting	
Limitations	
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (Garibaldi et al., 2020; Mohamed et al., 2024)

2.2.4. Water stress

Indicator	Water stress
Theme	Water
Purpose of indicator	Aligns to SDG 6.4.2 on level of water stress, and SDG 6.6.1 on extent of water-related ecosystems.
Data source	Household survey
Measurement	Proportion of months with agricultural water shortages per year, for all agriculturally active months
Measurement units	%
Guidance on measurement	<p>This indicator can be calculated by collecting data on the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of months for which a household experienced water shortages in the last 12 months, in relation to crop, livestock, fish or other agricultural activities (ideally disaggregated). <p>The indicator is calculated by summing the number of months of water stress and dividing this by 12, and then taking the inverse (1/x) so that higher values indicate less water stress.</p> <p>Additional data can be collected on water sources (disaggregated by rainwater, water storage on-farm, water storage off-farm, flood water, piped water, other) to distinguish rainfed water stress versus irrigated water stress, and whether water harvesting measures are used.</p> <p>These data can be collected as part of a household survey.</p>
Guidance on data entry and reporting	Collect data by asking which months (Jan, Feb, Mar, etc) water is needed per activity, and then which months there are water shortages per activity, to ensure alignment between the two responses.
Indicator interpretation and threshold setting	This indicator presents the percentage of months in a year with water stress. Lower values indicate less stress, while high values indicate more stress. Therefore the indicator values should be inverted
Limitations	<p>Key limitations of the measurement approach for this indicator include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water quality is not accounted for. - Water storage and delivery infrastructure are not considered. <p>Alternatives to consider for future surveys include the "Agricultural Water Scarcity Index" which is a dimensionless index; or "Water Productivity" (kg produced/m³ water consumed); or Quantify freshwater (rainfall, groundwater and surface water) supplied to different agricultural enterprises on the farm during the month or year. For the latter, users should:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Estimate amount of water (m³/year) required by crop, livestock, fish or other agricultural enterprises (disaggregated) on the farm. - Estimate the amount of water (m³/year) supplied to each agricultural enterprise on the farm. - Calculate: $\text{Water Stress (\%)} = (\text{Total freshwater supplied} / \text{Available freshwater resources}) \times 100$. - Classify water stress (%) into the following categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ No stress = <10. Low water demand relative to water supply. ○ Low stress = 10-20. Moderate demand – sustainable status. ○ Medium stress = 20-40. Significant pressure on water resources. ○ High stress = 40-80. Strong competition for water – management is critical. ○ Critical stress = >80. Unsustainable water extraction for agriculture.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Biancalani and Marinelli, 2021) • (van Vliet et al., 2021)

2.2.1. Energy use

Indicator	Sustainable energy use
Theme	Energy use
Purpose of indicator	Fossil fuels and other non-renewable energy sources contribute to global greenhouse gas emissions, exacerbating global warming. Increasing the share of renewable energy sources while reducing overall energy consumption contributes to net zero emissions targets (Paris Agreement, SDG 13), while self- and locally produced energy helps ensure an affordable and reliable energy supply (SDG 7).
Data source	Household survey
Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportion of energy sources that are from renewable sources (energy produced from solar panels, wind turbines, hydropower or other renewable sources). • Proportion of consumed energy that is produced on-farm or by local suppliers.
Measurement units	Likert scale (1-3), where 1 represents only renewable energy use, 2 a mixture of renewable and non- renewable energy use, 3 only non-renewable energy use.
Guidance on measurement	<p>This indicator can be calculated by collecting data on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sources of energy , disaggregated by renewable and non-renewable, per activity (cooking, irrigation, tillage, and other food-related/agricultural activities). Used to provide a Likert scale measure of clean energy use: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 1: Totally renewable ○ 2: Partially renewable ○ 3: Not renewable. • Proportion of energy used that is produced on-farm, by the community, or purchased from other sources <p>Data on the proportion of renewable and locally produced energy sources can be combined to provide a Likert-scale measure of the sustainability of energy use.</p>
Guidance on data entry and reporting	Record the energy sources in the system assessed.
Indicator interpretation and threshold setting	
Limitations	Some renewable energy have negative environmental impacts, e.g. biogas digestors contribute to GHG emissions when they leak
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Sustainability Directory, 2025)

2.2.2. Climate mitigation

Indicator	Net greenhouse gas emissions
Theme	Climate mitigation
Purpose of indicator	<p>Globally, the agriculture and land use sector contributes approximately 18% of total greenhouse gas emissions, rising to nearly 60% of GHG emissions in parts of the developing world where agriculture dominates the economy. With the world set to exceed the emissions threshold for keeping warming below 1.5°C in less than 10 years (Liu et al., 2023), mitigation from all sectors is a top global priority.</p> <p>This indicator is relevant for global climate mitigation goals (Paris Agreement) and nationally determined contributions (NDCs). It is also relevant for the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework Target 10 on ‘Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture’, where changes in soil organic carbon stocks is a complementary indicator (CBD/COP/15/L.26).</p>
Data source	Farmer survey, literature review, and/or field measurements
Measurement	Qualitative score of net greenhouse gas emissions (alternative: carbon storage in soil and above-ground biomass)
Measurement units	5-point Likert scale (alternative: t C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)
Guidance on measurement	<p>We discuss two options for measurement of net greenhouse gas emissions: i) qualitative assessment of climate mitigation potential of on-farm practices, ii) quantitative assessment of carbon storage and sequestration only, based on soil organic carbon (SOC) and estimates of carbon stored in live woody biomass.</p> <p>Qualitative assessment</p> <p>Given the importance of climate change mitigation and the relative difficulty of accurately quantifying net GHG emissions from smallholder agriculture across diverse country contexts, we propose a qualitative approach for integration of mitigation into all performance assessments.</p> <p>Measurement involves:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classifying farming practices according to their net emissions: 1,2,3,4,5, where 1 represents high emitting and low sequestering practices, and 5 represents low emitting and high sequestering practices. • Collecting household survey data on the share of cropland under each practice. • Calculating a weighted average score for all practices found on the farm, using the share of cropland as weights. <p>Note that the final score could instead be weighted by productivity for an emissions intensity estimate, if practice data are collected for each main crop/livestock/fish.</p>

Locally relevant farming practices need to be identified and classified into a net emissions category. The classification can be done through literature review and local experts.

Some qualitative assessments/reviews of mitigation potential of agricultural practices already exist. We use one such review by Bell et al. (2018) to provide an example scoring of practices by emission category. The overall score is an average of the component score. In the overall score, 1 represents high emitting and low sequestering practices, and 5 represents low emitting and high sequestering practices.

Practices	Carbon sequestration in soils	Carbon sequestration in biomass	Avoided GHG emissions	Overall score	References
<i>Cropping systems</i>					
Agroforestry	5	5	4	4.66	Bell et al. (2018)
Biochar	3	3	2	2.66	Bell et al. (2018)
Crop rotation	3	3	3	3	Bell et al. (2018)
Drip irrigation	3	3	2	2.66	Bell et al. (2018)
Embedded natural (hedgerows)	4	5	4	4.33	Bell et al. (2018)
Green manure	4	3	2	3	Bell et al. (2018)
Intercropping	5	3	5	4.33	Bell et al. (2018)
Microdosing	3	3	2	2.66	Bell et al. (2018)
Mulching	4	3	3	3.33	Bell et al. (2018)
Reduced tillage	4	3	4	3.66	Bell et al. (2018)
<i>Lowland rice systems</i>					
Biochar	4	4	2	3.33	Bell et al. (2018)
Green manure	4	4	4	4	Bell et al. (2018)

Microdosing	4	4	2	3.33	Bell et al. (2018)
Rice-fish integration	3	3	4	3.33	Bell et al. (2018)
Alternate wetting and drying	3	3	4	3.33	Bell et al. (2018)
Livestock systems					
Improved feed quality	4	4	4	4	Bell et al. (2018)
Planting N-fixing legumes	4	3	3	3.33	Bell et al. (2018)
Rotational grazing	4	3	3	3.33	Bell et al. (2018)
Fish systems					
Improved feed quality	3	3	3	3	Bell et al. (2018)

Quantitative assessment

Measurement involves collecting data on tree diameter at breast height (dbh), tree height, number of trees, and collecting data on soil organic carbon through laboratory analysis of soil samples.

Carbon storage and sequestration in woody biomass:

- Get on-farm tree count for trees with dbh > 50cm or >10m in height
- Convert above and below-ground biomass to t/ha using IPCC conversion factors.

Soil carbon storage:

- Use the median SOC in the 0-20cm zone from across the three plots per farm (see Soil Health indicator).

Additional GHG measurement options (beyond the scope of the standard HOLPA tool, see Complementary Indicators)

The most precise, quantitative measurements of GHG emissions are obtained through field measurements of GHG fluxes, either through collection of gas samples and later analysis in a gas chromatography lab (e.g. for ruminant methane emission), or through real-time measurement of gas fluxes using an infrared gas analyzer (e.g. leaf photosynthesis and respiration, soil respiration, or landscape eddy covariance). These methods require costly equipment and/or laboratory analysis, as well as expert technicians to collect and analyze the samples. Further details on the procedures are provided in the section on Complementary Indicators.

	<p>In lieu of direct measurement, all other approaches to quantifying GHG emissions from agriculture rely on collecting activity data and using emissions factors to convert activities into emissions levels (e.g. from IPCC). Activity data is a description of the farm practices and areas (or number of livestock) over which they are practiced. Activity data can be collected via household surveys, potentially supplemented with measurement of farm sizes. Higher levels of detail in the activity data (amounts of inputs used, crops and crop varieties, soil types, feed formulations, tree species in agroforestry systems, etc.) generally allow for more precise estimation of emissions. However, conversion of activity data into quantitative emissions relies on the use of emissions factors. Most widely available emissions factors (e.g. Tier 1 Approach) are based on data from temperate countries (Ogle et al. 2013; Albanito et al. 2017) and may not be appropriate for estimating GHG emissions from agricultural activities in tropical countries.</p> <p>Models of GHG emissions also rely on collection of activity data and emissions factors, but many can account for local conditions, such as soil types, livestock breeds, climate, etc to produce more appropriate emissions estimates for tropical or developing countries not well represented in the Tier 1 approach. Several models are available for calculating emissions, including the Ex-Ante Carbon Balance Tool (EXACT) and the Cool Farm Tool, however use of these models requires a degree of technical expertise.</p>
Guidance on data entry and reporting	
Indicator interpretation and threshold setting	
Limitations	
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Thornton et al., 2018) • (Bell et al., 2018) • (Anuga et al., 2020) • (MacLeod et al., 2020)

2.3. Agricultural KPIs

2.3.1. Crop health

Indicator	Crop health
Theme	Crop health
Purpose of indicator	Crop and pasture health can influence agricultural productivity and resilience of plants to stress, pests and competition. Crop health can be affected by any biological, chemical, or physical factors that may affect plant physiology and crop performance, impacting food production (SDG2) and the spread of food-borne diseases with consequences for human health (SDG3).
Data source	Household survey, field measurements
Measurement	% crop losses, and SOCLA indicators of crop health
Measurement units	Score from 1 to 10, representing the mean indicator value across 10 indicators
Guidance on measurement	<p>We propose two complementary measures of crop health: i) Qualitative based on household survey responses, ii) Qualitative based on field observations.</p> <p>Household survey based A simple measure of crop health can be provided by collecting responses on: What percentage of the total crop production was lost or damaged in the last 12 months?</p> <p>Field based More detailed data on crop health can be determined through field measurements interpreted jointly by farmers and researchers. Field measurements to collect data on each crop health indicator should be conducted every 50m along a transect of approximately 150m (this may vary depending on the farm size), to collect data on all 10 crop health indicators at three sampling sites per farm. Crop health should be assessed for only the main crop(s) grown on the farm to keep the task manageable.</p> <p>At three 10x10m square plots per farm, observe the crops and/or pasture present in the plot and jointly with the respondent record the responses to the indicators with the respondent. Refer to the example images provided in the field survey (Appendix 4.3.7.3 Crop and pasture health) to determine the most appropriate responses crop health related questions.</p> <p>The proposed indicators were developed by the Latin American Society for Agroecology (SOCLA) and described in Nicholls et al. (2004)(Nicholls et al., 2004b). The SOCLA 10 indicators of crop health are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Appearance

2. Crop growth
3. Disease incidence
4. Insect pest incidence
5. Natural enemy abundance and diversity
6. Weed competition and pressure
7. Actual or potential yield
8. Vegetational diversity
9. Natural surrounding vegetation
10. Management system

Each indicator is scored from 1 to 10 based on the following guidelines (from Nicholls et al. 2004, Table 1):

Appearance	1	Chlorotic, discolored foliage with deficiency signs
	5	Light green foliage with some discoloring
	10	Dark green foliage, no signs of deficiency
Crop growth	1	Uneven stand; short and thin branches; limited new growth
	5	Denser, but not uniform stand; thicker branches; some new growth
	10	Abundant branches and foliage; vigorous growth
Disease incidence	1	Susceptible, more than 50% of plants with damaged leaves and/or fruits
	5	Between 25–45% plants with damage
	10	Resistant, with less than 20% of plants with light damage
Insect pest incidence	1	More than 15 leafhopper nymphs per leaf, or more than 85% damaged leaves
	5	Between 5–14 leafhopper nymphs per leaf, or 30–40% damaged leaves
	10	Less than 5 leafhopper nymphs per leaf, and less than 30% damaged leaf
Natural enemy abundance and diversity	1	No presence of predators/parasitic wasps detected in 50 random leaf sampled
	5	At least one individual of one or two beneficial species
	10	At least two individuals of one or two beneficial species
Weed competition and pressure	1	Crops stressed, overwhelmed by weeds
	5	Medium presence of weeds, some level of competition
	10	Vigorous crop, overcomes weeds
Actual or potential yield	1	Low in relation to local average
	5	Medium, acceptable
	10	Good or high
Vegetational diversity	1	Monoculture
	5	A few weeds present or uneven cover crop
	10	With dense cover crop or weedy background
Natural surrounding vegetation	1	Surrounded by other crops, no natural vegetation
	5	Adjacent to natural vegetation on at least one side
	10	Surrounded by natural vegetation on at least two sides
Management system	1	Conventional
	5	In transition to organic with IPM or input substitution
	10	Organic, diversified with low external biological inputs

Guidance on data entry and reporting	Record the crop species and variety in the system assessed. Be sure to take a GPS point and keep a record of the geographic coordinates where crop health was assessed to allow follow-up surveys in the same locations.
Indicator interpretation and threshold setting	
Limitations	
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Nicholls et al., 2004a) • (FAO, 2019)

2.3.2. Animal health

Indicator	Animal health
Theme	Animal health
Purpose of indicator	Maintaining healthy and diverse stocks of animals on-farm contributes to overall agroecosystem functioning for more sustainable farming systems (SDG2, GBF Target 10). Keeping animals in poor health increases the spread of zoonoses, food-borne disease, and livestock mortalities, with associated negative consequences on human health (SDG2 and 3) and livelihoods (SDG1). Healthier animals have a smaller environmental footprint (SDG12 and 13).
Data source	Household survey with farm transect
Measurement	Qualitative measure of livestock disease and losses. Alternative: Health and welfare of farm animals, measured using the welfare outcome assessment tool as applied to each livestock species.
Measurement units	Various (e.g. number of animals in each welfare category, number of mortalities per 100 animals)
Guidance on measurement	<p>We discuss two measures of animal health: i) qualitative welfare assessment, ii) (optional) full welfare assessment.</p> <p>Qualitative assessment Likert score (1 to 4) based on the following questions:</p> <p>What was the extent of injury, illness, or death of livestock due to diseases in the last 12 months?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. None 2. Low 3. Medium 4. High <p>What was the extent of injury, illness or death of fish due to diseases in the last 12 months?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. None 2. Low 3. Medium 4. High <p>Full welfare assessment (optional) The welfare outcome assessment tool is a practical and scientifically informed way of assessing and measuring animal welfare. It aims to provide an objective, accurate and direct picture of animal welfare.</p> <p>The assessment measures the impact of farm inputs (e.g. housing, space, feed, veterinary care, management) on the health, physical condition and behaviour of the animals themselves. There are different assessment approaches for each livestock species: laying hens, dairy cows, pigs,</p>

	<p>broiler hens, beef cattle, sheep. The method was developed by Assurewel and is implemented by the UK Soil Association and RSPCA: http://www.assurewel.org/aboutassurewel/aboutwelfareoutcomeassessment.html.</p> <p>The assessment of one livestock species takes around 30 mins per farm. The researcher will need to complete, with the farmer, the AssureWel simple scoresheet for each livestock produced on the farm. For example, for dairy cattle, this includes documenting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobility (good, impaired, severely impaired) • Body condition (thin, moderate, fat) • Cleanliness (clean to very dirty) • Hair loss, lesions and swellings • Number of cows with broken tails • Number of cows needing further care • Farmer records of mobility, mastitis, calf and heifer survivability, cull and casualty cows.
Guidance on data entry and reporting	
Indicator interpretation and threshold setting	
Limitations	
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (AssureWel, 2018a) – assessment protocol for dairy cattle • (AssureWel, 2018b) – scoresheet for dairy cattle • (AssureWel, 2023) – explanation of measures for dairy cattle • See http://www.assurewel.org for protocols, scoresheets and explanations for laying hens, pigs, broiler hens, beef cattle, and sheep.

2.3.3. Soil health

Indicator	Soil organic carbon (alternative: qualitative measure of soil health)
Theme	Soil health
Purpose of indicator	Soil organic carbon or organic matter (SOC or SOM) is a key indicator of soil health, supporting vegetation growth, soil stability, soil fertility and other vital ecosystem services. SOC/SOM assessment is relevant for assessing carbon emission and sequestration, and soil health, under local and international commitments. This indicator is relevant to global climate mitigation goals (Paris Agreement) and the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework Target 10 on ‘Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture’, where changes in soil organic carbon stocks is a complementary indicator (CBD/COP/15/L.26). In resource-constrained projects, it can be challenging to collect soil samples and run laboratory analyses to calculate SOC. We propose using simple qualitative measures of soil erosion and fertility to provide an alternative, rapid assessment of soil health in cases where SOC is unattainable.
Data source	Soil samples collected on-site (alternative: household survey)
Measurement	Laboratory measurement of % soil organic carbon, or % soil organic matter (alternative: qualitative assessment of erosion and fertility through household survey)
Measurement units	% (alternative: Likert-scale score)
Guidance on measurement	<p>We discuss two options for the measurement of soil health: i) soil organic carbon calculated in a laboratory from soil samples, ii) qualitative measure of soil health.</p> <p>Soil organic carbon</p> <p>Soil samples should be taken randomly, in a W-shaped pattern, from 5 points per plot, for three 10x10m plots per farm.</p> <p>After collecting the soil samples, a standard laboratory procedure should be used to determine the carbon content of the sample. The loss-on-ignition method (Nelson and Sommers, 1996) can be used to estimate the SOC/SOM using the following steps.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Air-dry the soil samples after collection, and grind fine enough to sieve through a mesh <2 mm or smaller. b) Oven dry each sample at 105°C for 24 hours. c) Weigh 5.000g ±0.001g of each oven-dried sample and place each into a crucible. This will be the pre-ignition weight of the sample. d) Heat the sample in a muffle furnace at 375°C for 16 hours or overnight e) Weigh the sample after the ignition and this will be the post-ignition weight f) Calculate percentage SOC/SOM using the following equation:

	$SOC (SOM)(\%) = \frac{pre\ ignition\ weight\ (g) - post\ ignition\ weight\ (g)}{pre\ ignition\ weight\ (g)}$ <p>Alternatively, a Carbon Nitrogen (CN) Elemental Analyser can be used to estimate soil organic carbon content. The C-N elemental analyser provides a quantitative measurement of SOC and N content based on the amount of C and N produced after combustion of products in a sample.</p> <p>Alternatively, the Walkey Black method can be used to estimate soil organic matter content. Walkey Black provides a qualitative measurement of SOM after oxidising the soil with potassium dichromate and H₂SO₄ and measuring the color change; which is proportionate to the organic matter available in the soil. A conversion factor can be used to convert either SOC to SOM or vice versa.</p> <p>Qualitative measure of soil health</p> <p>To complement SOC data, and to allow for a basic assessment of soil health in cases where neither soil organic carbon data or SOCLA (see Complementary indicators) can be collected (e.g. to due to resource constraints), HOLPA includes two standard questions on farmer perceptions of soil health. Farmer perceptions of soil fertility and erosion are gathered using a simple Likert scale, based on the following two questions:</p> <p>How would you describe the fertility of your soil on your farmland?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highly fertile (score 5) • Moderately fertile (score 3.66) • Low fertility (score 2.33) • Infertile (score 1). <p>How would you describe the level of soil erosion problems on your farmland?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil erosion is not a problem on my farm (score 5) • Soil erosion is a minor problem on my farm (score 3) • Soil erosion is a major problem on my farm (score 1). <p>These perception questions can be used to assign a soil health score from 1 (infertile and major soil erosion) to 5 (highly fertile with no soil erosion), by taking the median across the fertility and erosion responses.</p>
Guidance on data entry and reporting	Report the SOC content as a volume-based concentration (i.e. %)

Indicator interpretation and threshold setting	
Limitations	
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• (Bahadori and Tofighi, 2016)• (Gelman et al., n.d.)• (Nelson and Sommers, 1996)• (Walkley and Black, 1934)

2.3.4. Nutrient use

Indicator	Nutrient use
Theme	Nutrient management
Purpose of indicator	Nutrient use per unit area provides information on the under or over-use of fertilizers, which has implications for crop productivity, economic viability, and environmental sustainability. By monitoring nutrient applications, farmers and agronomists can determine if the current inputs are meeting or exceeding the nutrient needs of the crop and if adjustments are needed to optimize input use and reduce nutrient losses to the environment. This indicator is related to a number of Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) e.g., SDG 2 on zero hunger and SDG 15 life on land.
Data source	Field measurements, household survey
Measurement	Fertilizer applications in the production system
Measurement units	Fertilizer input (kg) per hectare per year, disaggregated by organic and chemical inputs. Can be presented as a ratio of recommended fertilizer input intensity in the landscape obtained from extension services and literature.
Guidance on measurement	<p>Nutrient use can be determined at the three levels i.e. plot level (the level of individual crops), farm level (the level of a whole farm and its cropping system), and landscape level (a larger area e.g. region or watershed).</p> <p>At all scales, it is important to consider all possible sources of inputs into the system to avoid under or overestimation of nutrient use.</p> <p>Specific survey questions should address the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the amount of nutrient input, such as nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), or potassium (K), added to the farm system through fertilization or other means per year? • What proportion of these nutrients come from each source (chemical, organic plant, manure)?
Guidance on data entry and reporting	Uniform data entry and conversion of inputs to kg ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹ .
Indicator interpretation and threshold setting	
Limitations	
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Dobermann, 2007) • (EU Nitrogen Expert Panel, 2016)

2.4.Social KPIs

2.4.1. Diet quality

Indicator	Diet quality
Theme	Nutrition
Purpose of indicator	Eradicating food insecurity and malnutrition is a sustainable development goal (SDG2). Nutritious diets are a prerequisite to achieving this goal.
Data source	Household and individual survey using the Diet Quality Questionnaire (DQQ) , developed by the Global Diet Quality Project
Measurement	Diet quality from 24-hour food consumption recalls, calculated from the number of food groups consumed per individual and household, from 29 food groups.
Measurement units	<p>Raw measurement: Y/N for consumption of each food group together with (optional) food group source (own production, purchased, borrowed, food aid, other).</p> <p>Final measurement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Household Food Group Diversity Score (FGDS) (0-10) (this measurement is the default KPI) - Minimum Dietary Diversity for Women of Reproductive Age (MDD-W) (0/1) - All-5 recommended food groups consumed (0/1) - Non-Communicable Disease (NCD) Protect (0-9), which is an indicator of dietary factors that protect against NCDs according to the World Health Organisation (WHO) - NCD-Risk (0-9), which is an indicator of dietary factors increasing the risk of NCDs according to WHO - Global Dietary Recommendations (GDR) Score (0 to 18), which indicates level of adherence to global dietary recommendations for a healthy diet according to WHO - (Optional) Proportion of food that is produced on-farm
Guidance on measurement	<p>The Diet Quality Questionnaire (DQQ) is a standardized tool to collect indicators of dietary adequacy, including the minimum dietary diversity for women (MDD-W) indicator, and All-5, as well as indicators of protection of health against noncommunicable diseases (NCDs), including NCD-Protect, NCD-Risk, and the global dietary recommendations score (GDR). It is a low-burden tool for collecting valid, comparable food group consumption data in populations.</p> <p>The DQQ is two-pages long and includes 29 multiple choice questions corresponding to the 29 DQQ food groups. Each question asks the respondent if they consumed a specific DQQ food groups with yes/no responses. The questionnaire takes approximately 5 minutes to complete per individual.</p>

The survey should be completed for the adult household members, including men and women. Researchers can optionally add one column asking, for each food group, the source: own production, purchased, borrowed, food aid, other. This will allow calculation of the proportion of consumed food that is from each source.

Note that the timing of survey affects results. Try to collect data from all farms at a period when food supplies are adequate, rather than when some farms are more likely to suffer shortages (e.g. end of dry season, or after a drought season).

DQQ Food Groups:

1. Foods made from grains
2. Whole grains
3. White roots, tubers, and plantains
4. Pulses
5. Vitamin A-rich orange vegetables
6. Dark green leafy vegetables
7. Other vegetables
8. Vitamin A-rich fruits
9. Citrus
10. Other fruits
11. Baked / grain-based sweets
12. Other sweets
13. Eggs
14. Cheese
15. Yogurt
16. Processed meats
17. Unprocessed red meat (ruminant)
18. Unprocessed red meat (non-ruminant)
19. Poultry
20. Fish and seafood
21. Nuts and seeds
22. Packaged ultra-processed salty snacks
23. Instant noodles
24. Deep fried foods
25. Fluid milk
26. Sweet tea / coffee / cocoa
27. Fruit juice and fruit-flavored drinks
28. Sugar-sweetened beverages (soft drinks, energy drinks, sports drinks)
29. Fast food

Examples of how the final scores are calculated:

	<p>Food Group Diversity Score (FGDS) 1 point for each "YES" answer to the following food groups:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>MDD-W Food group</th> <th>DQQ Question numbers</th> <th>Possible points</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><i>Grains, white roots and tubers, and plantains</i></td> <td>1, 2, 3</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Pulses (beans, peas and lentils)</i></td> <td>4</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Nuts and seeds</i></td> <td>21</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Dairy</i></td> <td>14, 15, 25</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Meat, poultry and fish</i></td> <td>16, 17, 18, 19, 20</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Eggs</i></td> <td>13</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Dark green leafy vegetables</i></td> <td>6*</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Other vitamin A-rich fruits and vegetables</i></td> <td>5, 8</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Other vegetables</i></td> <td>7*</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Other fruits</i></td> <td>9, 10*</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		MDD-W Food group	DQQ Question numbers	Possible points	<i>Grains, white roots and tubers, and plantains</i>	1, 2, 3	1	<i>Pulses (beans, peas and lentils)</i>	4	1	<i>Nuts and seeds</i>	21	1	<i>Dairy</i>	14, 15, 25	1	<i>Meat, poultry and fish</i>	16, 17, 18, 19, 20	1	<i>Eggs</i>	13	1	<i>Dark green leafy vegetables</i>	6*	1	<i>Other vitamin A-rich fruits and vegetables</i>	5, 8	1	<i>Other vegetables</i>	7*	1	<i>Other fruits</i>	9, 10*	1
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References	<p>Global Diet Quality Project resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - https://www.globaldietquality.org/dqq - DQQ Food Group Descriptions - Diet Quality Questionnaire (DQQ) Indicator Guide <p>Diet Quality Questionnaires are adapted to each country, downloadable from the Global Diet Quality Project website and translated into many languages.</p>																																		

2.4.2. Land tenure security

Indicator	Land tenure security
Theme	Land tenure
Purpose of indicator	Land access is closely linked to use and control over productive resources. Secure land tenure is therefore a key determinant of individual agency, income and wellbeing. This indicator is aligned with SDG 1.4.2 and 5.a.1.
Data source	Parcels (most preferable) or household/farm (most possible) survey using a simplified version of the harmonized questionnaire proposed by FAO et al. (2019)(FAO et al., 2019). Additionally, GPS delineation of parcels is strongly advised wherever feasible, as evidence points to systematic bias in farmer estimates of land area(Carletto, 2021).
Measurement	$((\text{Area of agricultural land used by the household for which at least one member of the household has their name on a legally recognized document OR has the right to sell OR has the right to bequeath})/(\text{Total land area used by the household})) * 100$
Measurement units	%
Guidance on measurement	<p>The indicator can be calculated with data collected using FAO's harmonized questionnaire, which is a standardized and succinct survey instrument designed to collect the essential data for computation of both 1.4.2^a and 5.A.1^b Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) indicators simultaneously.</p> <p>The methodology proposed 5 versions of the questionnaire (see next figure) depending on: (i) the respondent selection approach, (ii) whether or not the survey collects data at the parcel-level and (iii) whether or not the existing survey includes a parcel roster. Each version of the questionnaire has approximated 10 questions and assumes that a separate household member roster exists and that the sex of each household member is captured in that roster.</p>

Where possible, it is advised to have parcel level data and implement a self-respondent approach (i.e., where individuals respond for themselves only, not on behalf of others) (version 2 with 7 questions). Where it is not, land tenure data should be collected at the household/farm level, using the version 3 (13 questions) of the questionnaire.

A sub-indicator can be calculated as: $((\text{Number of adult women in agricultural households whose name is on a legally recognized document OR who have the right to sell OR bequeath agricultural land}) / (\text{Total adult individuals in agricultural households whose name is on a legally recognized document OR who have the right to sell OR bequeath agricultural land})) * 100$.

Note, for pastoralists, land tenure security may be better measured in terms of mobility, i.e. proportion of grazing lands over which the farmer has unrestricted rights to graze livestock.

Guidance of how to apply the questionnaire:

- The survey should be completed for the adult household member (18 years old or older).
- Because a self-respondent approach is going to be used and only some (or one) randomly selected household members are interviewed about their tenure rights, only the selected members are part of the reference population (i.e., denominator in the indicator and sub-indicator formulas).
- The country-specific questionnaire should include: i) a comprehensive list of all tenure types applicable to the country; ii) a comprehensive list of land tenure-related documents, specifying which ones the government

considers as legally recognized; iii) images of the documents considered legally recognized; iv) a context-specific definition of alienation rights.

VERSION 2 – PARCEL-LEVEL DATA; SELF-RESPONDENT APPROACH; ASSUMES PARCEL ROSTER ELSEWHERE WHICH CAN BE FED FORWARD TO EITHER (A) THE INTERVIEW OF ONE OR MORE RANDOMLY SELECTED INDIVIDUALS OR (B) THE INTERVIEWS OF ALL ADULT HOUSEHOLD MEMBERS; ASSUMES SEPARATE HOUSEHOLD MEMBER ROSTER WITH SEX.

Implementation:	Use "currently" or set a specific date -- country level decision	Named agencies and examples to be customized for context	Codes to be customized at country level - to include all legally recognized documents. Rental contracts of some form should be included, as long as rights are legally protected Photo aid to be shown to respondents.	skip for short term rental, sharecropped in, and borrowed for free	skip for short term rental, sharecropped in, and borrowed for free
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Respondent Roster ID: _____
Q0. Do you use, own, or hold use rights for any parcel of land, either alone or jointly with someone else, irrespective of whether the parcel is used by your or another household, and irrespective of the use of the parcel (including dwelling plot, agricultural, pastoral, forest and business/commercial plots)?
 YES...1
 NO...2 >> END OF QUESTIONS

ENUMERATOR: AFTER CREATING THE ROSTER OF PARCELS, GO THROUGH THE ENTIRE MODULE ONE PARCEL AT A TIME.

PARCEL ID [FED FORWARD]	1. PARCEL NAME [FED FORWARD]	2. Do you use, own, or hold use rights for this [PARCEL], either alone or jointly with someone else?	3. Is there a document for this [PARCEL] issued by or registered at the Land Registry/ Cadastral Agency, such as a title deed, certificate of ownership, certificate of hereditary acquisition, lease or rental contract?	4. What type of documents are there for this [PARCEL], and is your name listed on any of the documents as owner or right use holder? LIST UP TO 3, SHOW PHOTO AID	5. Do you have the right to sell this [PARCEL], either alone or jointly with someone else?	6. Do you have the right to bequeath this [PARCEL], either alone or jointly with someone else?	7. On a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is not at all likely and 5 is extremely likely, how likely are you to involuntarily lose ownership or use rights to this [PARCEL] in the next 5 years?
		YES..... 1 NO.....2 >> NEXT PARCEL	YES..... 1 NO..... 2 >> 5	<u>CHOOSE ONE DOCUMENT</u> TYPE: TITLE DEED.....1 CERTIFICATE OF CUSTOMARY OWNERSHIP.....2 CERTIFICATE OF OCCUPANCY.....3 CERTIFICATE OF HEREDITARY ACQUISITION LISTED IN REGISTRY.....4 SURVEY PLAN.....5 RENTAL CONTRACT.....6 LEASE, REGISTERED.....7 OTHER (SPECIFY).....8 <u>CHOOSE ONE NAME LISTED</u> YES.....1 NO.....2 DON'T KNOW.....98 REFUSAL.....99 OTHER (SPECIFY).....8	YES.....1 NO.....2 DON'T KNOW.....98 REFUSAL.....99	YES.....1 NO.....2 DON'T KNOW.....98 REFUSAL.....99	NOT AT ALL LIKELY.....1 SLIGHTLY LIKELY.....2 MODERATELY LIKELY.....3 VERY LIKELY.....4 EXTREMELY LIKELY.....5
				DOCUMENT 1 DOCUMENT 2 DOCUMENT 3 DOC. NAME DOC. NAME DOC. NAME TYPE LISTED? TYPE LISTED? TYPE LISTED?			
1							
2							
3							
4							
5							

Color Codes: ■ SDG 1.4.2 ■ SDG 5.1.1 ■ Both 1.4.2 & 5.a.1 ■ Analytical purposes only

VERSION 3 - INDIVIDUAL LEVEL DATA; SELF-RESPONDENT APPROACH; NOT REPORTED AT PARCEL LEVEL; ADMINISTERED TO (A) ONE OR MORE RANDOMLY SELECTED INDIVIDUALS OR (B) ALL ADULT HOUSEHOLD MEMBERS.

Implementation/ CAPI Notes	Use "currently" or set a specific date - country level decision	Named agencies and examples to be customized for context	Codes to be customized at country level - to include all legally recognized documents. Rental contracts of some form should be included, as long as rights are legally protected	skip for short term rental, sharecropped in, and borrowed for free	skip for short term rental, sharecropped in, and borrowed for free
			Photo aid to be shown to respondents.		

Q0. Do you or does any member of your household use, own, or hold use rights for any parcel of land, either alone or jointly with someone else, irrespective of whether the parcel is used by you or another household, and irrespective of the use of the parcel (including dwelling plot, agricultural, pastoral, forest and business/commercial plots)?

YES...1

NO...2 >> END OF QUESTIONS

Agricultural Land						
RESPONDENT ID	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.
	Do you currently use, own, or hold use rights for any agricultural land (including pastoral land), either alone or jointly with someone else?	Is there a document for any agricultural land you own or hold use rights to that is issued by or registered at the Land Registry/ Cadastral Agency, such as a title deed, certificate of ownership, certificate of hereditary acquisition, lease or rental contract?	What type of documents are there for the agricultural land you own or hold use rights to, and is your name listed on any of the documents as owner or right use holder?	Do you have the right to sell any of the agricultural land you own or hold use rights to, either alone or jointly with someone else?	Do you have the right to bequeath any of the agricultural land you own or hold use rights to, either alone or jointly with someone else?	On a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is not at all likely and 5 is extremely likely, how likely are you to involuntarily lose ownership or use rights to any of the agricultural land you own or hold use rights to in the next 5 years?
	YES...1 NO...2 >> Q8	YES...1 NO...2 >> 5	LIST UP TO 3, SHOW PHOTO AID CODES FOR DOCUMENT TYPE: CODES FOR NAME LISTED? TITLE DEED.....1 YES.....1 CERTIFICATE OF CUSTOMARY OWNERSHIP.....2 NO.....2 CERTIFICATE OF OCCUPANCY.....3 DON'T KNOW..98 CERTIFICATE OF HEREDITARY ACQUISITION LISTED IN REGISTRY.....4 REFUSAL.....99 SURVEY PLAN.....5 RENTAL CONTRACT REGISTERED.....6 LEASE, REGISTERED.....7 OTHER (SPECIFY).....8	YES.....1 NO.....2 DON'T KNOW..98 REFUSAL.....99	YES.....1 NO.....2 DON'T KNOW..98 REFUSAL.....99	NOT AT ALL LIKELY.....1 SLIGHTLY LIKELY.....2 MODERATELY LIKELY.....3 VERY LIKELY.....4 EXTREMELY LIKELY.....5
			DOCUMENT 1 DOCUMENT 2 DOCUMENT 3			
			DOC. NAME DOC. NAME DOC. NAME TYPE LISTED? TYPE LISTED? TYPE LISTED?			

Non-Agricultural Land					
RESPONDENT ID	8.	9.	10.	11.	12.
	Do you currently use, own, or hold use rights for any non-agricultural land, such as land used for residential or commercial purposes, either alone or jointly with someone else?	Is there a document for any non-agricultural land you own or hold use rights to that is issued by or registered at the Land Registry/ Cadastral Agency, such as a title deed, certificate of ownership, certificate of hereditary acquisition, lease or rental contract?	What type of documents are there for the non-agricultural land you own or hold use rights to, and is your name listed on any of the documents as owner or right use holder?	Do you have the right to sell any of the non-agricultural land you own or hold use rights to, either alone or jointly with someone else?	Do you have the right to bequeath any of the non-agricultural land you own or hold use rights to, either alone or jointly with someone else?
	YES...1 NO...2 >> NEXT INDIVIDUAL	YES...1 NO...2 >> 11	LIST UP TO 3, SHOW PHOTO AID CODES FOR DOCUMENT TYPE: CODES FOR NAME LISTED? TITLE DEED.....1 YES.....1 CERTIFICATE OF CUSTOMARY OWNERSHIP.....2 NO.....2 CERTIFICATE OF OCCUPANCY.....3 DON'T KNOW..98 CERTIFICATE OF HEREDITARY ACQUISITION LISTED IN REGISTRY.....4 REFUSAL.....99 SURVEY PLAN.....5 OTHER (SPECIFY).....8 RENTAL CONTRACT REGISTERED.....6 LEASE, REGISTERED.....7	YES.....1 NO.....2 DON'T KNOW..98 REFUSAL.....99	YES.....1 NO.....2 DON'T KNOW..98 REFUSAL.....99
			DOCUMENT #1 DOCUMENT #2 DOCUMENT #3		
			DOC. NAME DOC. NAME DOC. NAME TYPE LISTED? TYPE LISTED? TYPE LISTED?		

- a Proportion of total adult population with secure tenure rights to land, with (a) legally recognized documentation; and (b) who perceive their rights to land as secure, by sex and by type of tenure.
- b (a) proportion of total agricultural population with ownership or secure rights over agricultural land by sex; and (b) share of women among owners or rights bearers of agricultural land, by type of tenure.

Guidance on data entry and reporting	Check that the total land area accessed by the household matches the sum of the land areas with different access types.
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Indicator interpretation and threshold setting	
Limitations	
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• (FAO et al., 2019)

2.4.3. Farmer agency

Indicator	Farmer agency
Theme	Social justice
Purpose of indicator	Individual agency to decide on what to consume, produce, and trade, and how to produce it, is a basic human right for farmers. Monitoring farmer agency provides an indication of the power dynamics influencing major decisions about the farm and food system, and level of social equality (SDG 10, 16).
Data source	Household surveys
Measurement	Ladder of Power and Freedom, from GENNOVATE
Measurement units	Score of 1 to 5, and quotes and insights from analysing qualitative data, for the household and each individual surveyed
Guidance on measurement	<p>The GENNOVATE Ladder of Power and Freedom is a qualitative data collection tool aimed at understanding local men and women farmers' own perceptions of agency and key factors determining levels of agency. Here, agency refers to 'the capacity to make important decisions in one's life and act upon them' (Petesch and Bullock, 2018).</p> <p>The Ladder provides comparative qualitative measures of agency that remain contextually grounded, and can be converted to a single quantitative agency score (but see notes on effectively applying the ladder approach). Data are collected through an individual interview using the ladder visual (see inset), which is a scoreboard showing different levels of agency. Data can also be collected at the community level through a focus group.</p>

Semi-structured individual interview module

Q1. Please imagine a five-step ladder [show figure of ladder], where at the bottom, on the first step, stand individual [sex of respondent] of the community with little capacity to make their own decisions about important affairs in their lives. These [sex of FGD] have little to say about if or where they will work, starting or ending a relationship with a [opposite sex], or starting a new agricultural or other business.

Ladder of Power and Freedom

Step 5: Power & freedom to make most all major life decisions

Step 4: Power & freedom to make many major life decisions

Step 3: Power & freedom to make some major life decisions

Step 2: Only a small amount of power & freedom

Step 1: Almost no power or freedom to make decisions

[The figure on the flipchart only needs to show the ladder and step #. The narrative in this figure is to help facilitators describe the different steps.]

On the highest step, the fifth, stand those who have great capacity to make important decisions for themselves, including about their working life and whether to start or end a relationship in their personal life.

1a. On which step of this ladder would you position yourself today?

1b. And 10 years ago? -----

Q2. What do you think are the main reasons why your rating (increased/stayed the same/decreased)?

Source: (Petesch and Bullock, 2018)

The ladder is applied as follows. The researcher identifies a meaningful historical benchmark, usually 10 years in the past, and provides (or creates) a visual of the five-step ladder on a sheet of paper. The researcher introduces the purpose of the exercise. They will need to explain the five-step ladder, and that step 5 indicates great power and freedom while step 1 indicates very little power and freedom to make important decisions.

For example: *Today we want to talk to you about how much power and freedom [wo]men in this household have to control the household food system – that is, how and what kind of food is produced, where it goes, and how and what kind of food people consume. Please imagine a five-step ladder [show figure], where at the bottom, on the first step, stand the individual [wo]men of this community with little capacity to make their own decisions about food production and consumption. These [wo]men have little to say about the types and varieties of crops, animals, trees, and animals they cultivate, the way they manage their water, land, soil, animals, and wildlife, the markets available to them, and the food source and food choices available to them. On the highest step, the fifth, stand those who have great capacity to make important decisions for themselves, including what they grow, how they manage their land, soil, water, animals, and trees, and what food they buy.*

Request the individual to mark on the ladder the step they think household members of their gender occupy.

Facilitate the discussion on reasons for the step identified. For example:

Q. Why would you place [wo]men on this step? Would you like to volunteer the reasons for your rating?

Q. Would you position different types of [wo]men in different places on this ladder? Older people, younger people, poorer people, single people, etc.? Do women and men differ?

Repeat the rankings and discussion to capture perceptions of power and freedom a decade ago (or at the pre-defined historical benchmark). These sticky notes / cards can fill in the other side of the ladder. These discussions should also be probed deeply to elicit detailed explanations for the trends in agency identified. The goal of the exercise is to understand the factors that shape women's or men's conceptions of power and freedom in their lives, and reasons for changes in these conceptions over time, rather than obtaining exact measurements or absolute values for agency.

Time permitting, facilitate a discussion about the changes the participants would like to see and what would be needed to achieve their vision. For example:

Q. Having talked through this together, are there changes you would like to see to give [wo]men more power and freedom in the future? What would be needed to achieve this? What are the major obstacles?

Record the whole interview and take good notes. During the discussion, listen closely for the reasoning behind votes, root causes of high or low agency, factors that contributed to change, and any differences reported for different groups in the community. Make note of powerful quotes that could be extracted later. Record how many votes are cast for each ladder step for both past and present.

Example responses for data collected at the community level:

Table 1. Highlights indicate the most frequently selected step to represent the ladder position of the majority of local women (if a woman’s FGD) or local men (if a men’s FGD). One women’s and one men’s middle-class focus groups, Amatuma,* Kenya, GENNOVATE dataset.

<i>Ladder Step</i>	Women’s focus group		Men’s focus group	
	<i>Rankings now</i>	<i>10 years ago</i>	<i>Rankings now</i>	<i>10 years ago</i>
5	0	0	0	0
4	2	1	1	3
3	6	1	6	4
2	2	6	3	3
1	0	2	0	0
<i>Mean step**</i>	<i>3.0</i>	<i>2.1</i>	<i>2.8</i>	<i>3.0</i>

*A pseudonym. **Change in perceived agency = mean step now – mean step 10 years ago.

Source: (Petesch and Bullock, 2018)

Notes on effectively applying the ladder approach:

- Researchers should ideally be the same sex as participants.
- Individual surveys should be conducted in a private room without the presence of any members of the household or anyone of the opposite sex.
- Since the tool requires respondents to recall circumstances 10 years ago, the minimum recommended respondent age is 25 years old. However the 10-year timeframe could be reduced if younger respondents are present.
- To assist with recall, it is helpful to identify the year corresponding to 10 years ago (e.g. 2014) and an important event at that time.
- Researchers need to have a good level of skill in qualitative data collection to collect meaningful data on agency using this (or any) method. For example, managing group dynamics in household (or focus group) surveys is important to ensure the perspectives of individuals with lower levels of agency are captured.
- The researcher should probe deeply into individual explanations of ladder rankings to understand the reasons for these rankings.
- Reducing agency to a single score (i.e., the mean step change at household level) risks undermining the relevance and quality of the data collected. Focusing on qualitative data collection and analysis is strongly recommended for a more meaningful and accurate understanding of individual and household agency.

Guidance on data entry and reporting

This indicator collects sensitive data on human subjects. Researchers should obtain ethical approval from a verified review board prior to data collection. Study participants should receive assurances that their testimonies will be provided anonymously and no identifying information shared in any future publications.

Indicator interpretation and threshold setting	
Limitations	
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Petesch and Bullock (2018) (Petesch and Bullock, 2018)• Tavenner and Crane (2022) (Tavenner and Crane, 2022)

2.4.4. Human well-being

Indicator	Personal Wellbeing Index
Theme	Human well-being
Purpose of indicator	This indicator aligns with SDG 3 “Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages”.
Data source	Household survey
Measurement	OECD Personal Wellbeing Index evaluation questions
Measurement units	Likert scale (0-10)
Guidance on measurement	<p>Human well-being encompasses quality of life and the ability of people and societies to contribute to the world with a sense of meaning and purpose. It encompasses a broad range of factors, including material well-being and emotional, physical, and social health(WHO, 2024). While people’s living conditions (e.g., housing, income, employment) are important contributors to well-being, measuring living conditions (i.e. material well-being) alone fails to capture what people think and feel about their lives – i.e., their subjective well-being.</p> <p>OECD’s Personal Wellbeing Index is computed based on responses to the following questions(OECD, 2013, p. 20):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Thinking about your own life and personal circumstances, how satisfied are you with your life as a whole? [0-10] 2. How satisfied are you with your standard of living? [Standard of Living] [0-10] 3. How satisfied are you with your health? [Personal Health] [0-10] 4. How satisfied are you with what you are achieving in life? [Achieving in Life] [0-10] 5. How satisfied are you with your personal relationships? [Personal Relationships] [0-10] 6. How satisfied are you with how safe you feel? [Personal Safety] [0-10] 7. How satisfied are you with feeling part of your community? [Community-Connectedness] [0-10] 8. How satisfied are you with your future security? [Future Security] [0-10] 9. How satisfied are you with the amount of time you have to do the things that you like doing? [0-10] 10. How satisfied are you with the quality of your local environment? [0-10] 11. For respondents who are employed only: How satisfied are you with your job? [0-10]

<p>Guidance on data entry and reporting</p>	<p>Key issues include the need to be careful with question wording, use consistent scales, and appropriate question ordering.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Question wording <p>“Because question wording matters to how people respond to questions on subjective well-being, the translation of questions is of high importance. Potential issues arising from translation cannot be eliminated, but they can be managed through an effective translation process. A robust translation process, including back translation, is therefore essential” (OECD, 2013).</p> 2. Scale design <p>“Variation in response formats can affect data quality and comparability. In the case of evaluative measures, there is empirical support for using a 0-10 point numerical scale, anchored by verbal labels which represent conceptual absolutes (such as completely satisfied/completely dissatisfied). On balance, it is preferable to label scale interval points (between the anchors) with numerical, rather than with verbal, labels” (OECD, 2013).</p> 3. Question order <p>Subjective well-being questions are influenced by context and thus need to be asked in the right place so as not to be influenced by previous questions. Consider randomizing the order in which the well-being questions are asked to reduce ordering-bias.</p>
<p>Indicator interpretation and threshold setting</p>	<p>Note that replies can be strongly affected by individual perceptions about own status compared to neighbors' or friends', so they are expression on a relative -not absolute- condition.</p>
<p>Limitations</p>	<p>An alternative to the OECD subjective wellbeing is the Generalized self-efficacy score used in Pro-WEAI (https://weai.ifpri.info/files/2023/07/Pro-WEAI-Guide.pdf).</p>
<p>References</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (WHO, 2024) • (OECD, 2013) • (International Well-being Group, 2024)

2.5.Economic KPIs

2.5.1. Agricultural productivity

Indicator	Crop and livestock productivity
Theme	Agricultural productivity
Purpose of indicator	Ensuring productivity and closing yield gaps is a primary goal in agricultural systems and vital for achieving global food security (SDG2), and securing livelihoods (SDG1).
Data source	Household survey (farmer recall)
Measurement	For crops: kg/ha (dry weight) of harvested produce; land equivalent ratio for intercropped and agroforestry systems (0 to infinity) For livestock: ## animals slaughtered for consumption/sale/gifts, kg meat/animal, litres (milk)/animal eggs/chicken, manure/animal, wool/animal, skin/animal
Measurement units	Kg/ha; kg/animal; l/animal; land equivalent area
Guidance on measurement	<p><u>Crop productivity through farmer recall</u></p> <p>Harvestable production per unit land area (kg/ha) for at least the three main crops, based on farmer recall for all produce harvested over the past 12 months. In the case of intercropped or agroforestry systems, collect data for all crops present in the plot and compute the land equivalent ratio (LER).</p> <p><u>Livestock productivity</u></p> <p>Production of animal products per unit livestock, for at least the three main livestock species (including fish), based on farmer recall of all products consumed, sold or gifted over the last 12 months.</p> <p>Desirable additional data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Population growth rate: ratio between the production in number of animals and the initial population size • Total annual livestock production = (stock variation +offtake- Intake)/ Initial size • Production of milk : av. production per female (/day)* number of reproductive female* milking period • Skin & hides (from offtake) • Wool : total production per year • Manure : total production (can be collected in declarative)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Productivity indicators: 1) Number of new sub-adults produced per reproductive female per year 2) Number of new adults produced per reproductive female and year <p><u>Crop productivity - detailed measurements (beyond the scope of HOLPA)</u></p> <p>For crops see FAO (2017): https://www.fao.org/3/ca6514en/ca6514en.pdf.</p> <p>For livestock see FAO (2018): https://www.fao.org/3/ca6400en/ca6400en.pdf.</p> <p>Summary for crop yield: Yields of all crops should be measured by randomly demarcating at least three same-size plots in a field, harvesting all produce, then drying the produce and weighing it to determine its dry weight. If possible take into account harvest losses (proportion of diseased, rotten or otherwise unusable produce). Alternatively, yields can be measured based on farmer recall particularly where farmers keep good records, but note that in many cases this method is inaccurate. Alternatively, farmers can be asked to keep crop diaries and record all harvested produce over the cropping season, which produced reliable results for the LSMS but is unsuitable for illiterate farmers. See guide for further details on calculating yields in mixed cropping systems.</p> <p>Crop and pasture areas should be estimated by walking along the perimeter of the farmed areas with a GPS (preferred method) or using the rope-and-compass method. Areas of additional plots that are far away or difficult to access can be estimated by farmers, and verified on Google Earth imagery if possible. Asking farmers to estimate the area of their fields can work well for small parcel sizes in some contexts, but is often unreliable e.g. when farmers are not familiar with the units of measurement or if farmers have incentives to misreport crop area.</p>
Guidance on data entry and reporting	
Indicator interpretation and threshold setting	
Limitations	
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (Dutilly et al., 2020) (Alary et al., 2022)

2.5.2. Labour productivity

Indicator	Labour inputs per unit agricultural land area
Theme	Labour productivity
Purpose of indicator	Labour inputs required for agricultural production is one of the primary factors determining which practices are used, how profitable they are, and the social sustainability of the production system. Distinguishing which productive systems promote sustainable employment contributes to SDG 2 and SDG8.
Data source	Farmer recall during household survey
Measurement	Person hours per year, disaggregated by gender, season, and productive activity
Measurement units	Person hours per year per hectare of cultivated land
Guidance on measurement	<p>This indicator can be computed by collecting data on number of labour hours per year per hectare of land actively used for agricultural purposes. Labour hours should be disaggregated by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • gender • age • type of worker: hired or not hired, permanent or seasonal • type of activity: routine (e.g. manure collection, milking) or seasonal work (e.g. seeding, harvesting, pruning).
Guidance on data entry and reporting	
Indicator interpretation and threshold setting	
Limitations	
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (FAO, 2010)

2.5.3. Total income and income stability

Indicator	Total income; Income stability
Theme	Income
Purpose of indicator	Total income and income stability are indicators of household living standards. Ensuring that agricultural livelihoods provide adequate and stable or increasing incomes contributes to rural development and ending poverty (SDG1).
Data source	Household survey
Measurement	Ratio of household income to national average household income; Likert score
Measurement units	Ratio (unitless); Likert score 1-3 or 1-5
Guidance on measurement	<p>We discuss three measurement approaches used in HOLPA: i) calculating total household income (or asset based proxies for this), ii) qualitative measure of income stability, iii) qualitative measure of income-expenditure ratio.</p> <p>Income level (KPI1) Total income per household is the total amount of profit or net earning a household makes over a given period. Ideally, income should be computed from data collected on all types of income generating activities agricultural or non-agricultural activities, goods and service based) and all types of household expenses, over the last 12 months. In practice, these data can be challenging to accurately collect in systems without digital records because they rely on farmer recall of all incoming and outgoing funds. Data on income should be compared to the national mean income level and used to calculate the ratio of household to mean national income.</p> <p>In addition, collecting data on income sources can be used to assess the level of dependency on single income sources or the capacity to withstand a shock through income diversification(Markowitz, 1952).</p> <p>Income based on assets (alternative KPI1) The asset-based approaches can be a good alternative when income and consumption data are not available or too expensive to collect. Various authors have worked on assets as a measure or proxy of welfare (Barrett and Carter, 2005; Carter and Barrett, 2006; Falkingham and Namazie, 2002). For example, the poverty probability Index (PPI, https://www.povertyindex.org/) is an asset-based approach. It offers a country specific scorecard to estimate the likelihood from a 10—question questionnaire based on 6 domains: durable household assets (e.g., TV, transport means), housing quality (used materials), utilities and infrastructure access (water and electricity access), land and property, livestock asset, and education.</p>

	<p><u>Income stability (qualitative) (KPI2)</u> Respondents are asked ‘How would you rate the stability of household income?’:</p> <p>5 - Income is increasing over time. 4 – Income is stable over time. 3 - Income varies little from year to year. 2 - Income varies from year to year. 1 - Income is on a decreasing trend.</p> <p>This information provides a rapid indication of income trends.</p> <p><u>Income-expenditure balance (complementary indicator, not a KPI)</u> HOLPA collects data on whether expenditures are less than, equal to, or more than income received by the household, over the last 12 months. The responses can be used to give a simple measure of whether the household has sufficient income to meet its needs.</p> <p>Data are collected by asking: In the last 12 months, did the household spend more money on the farm than it earns from the farm?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes - No - I don't know
<p>Guidance on data entry and reporting</p>	<p>For KP1 (total income), discuss income in terms of the local currency during the survey and consistently ask for information from a single time-period. When possible, ask questions on every distinct source of income (e.g. per crop, per buyer) and aggregate these later, to avoid inaccurate estimates or missed income sources (IDH, 2021). For example, if a crop was grown during multiple seasons within one year, it is preferable to ask the question for each season and then evaluate over the year. For livestock activities, distinguish regular income (e.g., milk, eggs per week) and more occasional income from the sale of animals.</p>
<p>Indicator interpretation and threshold setting</p>	<p>Income level depends on occupational activity, but this is not the only determining factor. Income level also reflects consumption, savings, accumulation, and lifestyle behaviors.</p>
<p>Limitations</p>	<p>Total income assessment faces at least three main difficulties:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The attitude of the head of household and her/his family, who are susceptible to: (i) underestimate their net income to avoid taxes, benefit from potential survey-related assistance, avoid social pressures from neighbors, or (ii) overestimate it to display their social success or assert their social position (Angel and Bittschi, 2019; Carletto, 2021). Income being highly confidential and sensitive information, it is best collected by adding up income derived from asking detailed information on household activities and using probing questions to ensure all sources are. It may be better to use proxies (based on

	<p>assets on expenditures, such as alternative KPI1) than rely on potentially inaccurate income data.</p> <p>2.The complexity of income in rural areas, with significant seasonal variability in both earnings and production costs, means that respondents may rely on either recent transactions or their primary activity, neglecting all sources of income derived from other activity.</p> <p>3. The revenues can be earned and manage by the different members of the household who share the same roof or the same meal (household unit). In this case, it is important to make a link between the various activities carried out by all household members.</p> <p>Alternative income indicators to consider in future surveys include monitoring expenditures, since income in rural areas is often composed of market and non-market sales, and self-consumption.</p>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (IDH, 2021) • (Angel et al., 2019) • (Carletto, 2021) • (Carter and Barrett, 2006) • (Falkingham and Namazie, 2002) • (Carletto et al., 2022) • (Parvathi and Nguyen, 2018) • (Markowitz, 1952)

2.5.4. Climate resilience

Indicator	Resilience score							
Theme	Climate resilience							
Purpose of indicator	Climate change is affecting food systems around the world, with temperatures and precipitation anomalies and extreme events leading to crop/livestock losses, altering species ranges, creating agricultural water stress, altering working conditions and triggering human migration. Building farm and food system resilience to climate change and other major stressors (e.g. pandemics, war) is fundamental to prevent food and livelihood insecurity (SDG 1, 2), and avoidable loss of life (SDG 3, 15).							
Data source	Household survey							
Measurement	Resilience score adapted from RIMA							
Measurement units	Score 0-20							
Guidance on measurement	<p>Resilience is the capacity of socioeconomic systems (e.g., households) to withstand shocks through adaptation and transformation.</p> <p>FAO's Resilience Index Measurement and Analysis (RIMA) is one way to measure resilience. FAO computes a Resilience Capacity Index (RCI) based on data collected across four pillars:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Access to basic services (ABS) 2. Assets (AST) 3. Social safety nets (SSN) 4. Adaptive capacity (AC) <p>FAO calculates the RCI using structural equation modelling (SEM), combining Confirmatory Factor Analysis and Path Analysis. There are two steps: 1) estimate resilience of each pillar through Factor Analysis (FA), 2) calculate a resilience index from the pillars, using Ordinary Least Squares with the outcome variable being a food security indicator(s) such as dietary diversity score. The benefit of this approach is that is possible to quantify the contribution of each pillar to the overall resilience. The limitation is that the RCI depends heavily on which indicator is used as the outcome variable which does not capture the variation across the four pillars.</p> <p>For HOLPA, we adapt the FAO approach to directly combine the data from the four pillars into a measure of resilience scaled from 0-20. This can be done by assigning scores of 0-5 to all responses, then taking the mean within each pillar, and summing scores across the four pillars according to the following table:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="488 1717 1414 1791"> <thead> <tr> <th>Pillar</th> <th>Question</th> <th>Score assigned to response</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td> </td> <td> </td> <td> </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Pillar	Question	Score assigned to response			
Pillar	Question	Score assigned to response						

	ABS	Does your farm/household have the following services: 1) Drinking water piped to the household, 2) Toilet with piped sewer or septic tank, 3) Electrical energy, 4) Waste (rubbish) collection service, 5) Mobile phone reception, 6) Internet. [Count services]	5: 3 or more 2.5: 1-2 0: None
	ABS	How far (one way) is the household from the closest accessible and functioning service in minutes (walking): 1) Freshwater source, 2) primary school, 3) public hospital or health facility, 4) livestock market 5) agricultural/crops market, 6) public means of transport, 7) well-maintained road suitable for cars.	For each service: 5: <5 mins 2.5: 5-20 mins 0: > 20 mins
	AST	How many of the following assets do household members own: 1) Car, 2) Motorbike, 3) Bicycle, 4) Gas or electric cooker, 5) Mobile phone, 6) Ox-plough, 7) Tractor, 8) Machete. [Count assets]	5: 5 or more distinct asset types 2.5: 2-4 0: 0-1
	SSN	On average, how many school meals have the children living in the household received per week, during the last month of attending school?	5: 5 meal 4: 4 meal 3: 3 meal 2: 2 meal 1: 1 meal 0: 0 meals
	SSN	Would any of the following individuals or organisations provide your household support in case of need: 1) local farmer associations or cooperatives, 2) other local associations (e.g. women support groups, youth groups), 3) individuals from my community, 4) individuals from a different community, 5) community leaders, 6) NGOs 8) local government, 9) national government, 10) other (please specify). [Count sources]	5: 3 or more 2.5: 1-2 0: None
	AC	Can the head of household read and write in any language?	5: Can read and write 2.5: Can read or write

		0: Cannot read or write, or prefer not to say
AC	On average, how many years have the household members of working age (>14 and <65 years old) attended formal school?	5: ≥7 (Secondary or higher) 2.5:<7 (Primary only) 0:0 (None)
AC	Has any household member received training in the last 12 months?	5: Y 0: N
AC	In the past 12 months, what were all the household's sources of income: : 1) Agriculture, animal breeding, fishing, 2) Other family business, 3) Government salary, 4) private sector salary, 5) Cash transfers (e.g. transfers from absent family members, donations), 6) Other (please specify) [count sources]	5: 3 or more sources 2.5: 2 sources 0: 1 source
AC	In the past 7 days, what percentage of the household's income was used for buying food	5: 0-25% 3.33: 26-50% 1.66: 51-75% 0: 76-100%
AC	In the past 5 years, has your farm/household had access to credit to support investment in your farming business.	5:Y 0:N, or I don't know
AC	How do you feel about your farm/household's ability to meet credit repayments now and until the loans are fully repaid?	5: Full repayments 3.33: Uncertain future repayments 1.66: Uncertain current repayments 0: Uncertain current and future repayments
AC	Do you have access to crop insurance? If yes, what is covered, e.g. losses from weather events, pest outbreaks market shocks?	5:Y 0:N
AC	Do you have access to subsidies for agricultural inputs? If yes, which inputs	5:Y 0:N

	Additionally, HOLPA collects data on household exposure to shocks over the last 12 months and any coping mechanisms employed.
Guidance on data entry and reporting	
Indicator interpretation and threshold setting	
Limitations	<p>The RIMA methodology has been criticized for failing to reliably predict future household resilience in terms of food security (Upton et al. 2022). In a review of resilience indices presented in Upton et al. (2022), the best-performing food security resilience indicator, which was the one developed by Cissé and Barrett (2018), achieved only modest overall accuracy in classifying food-insecure households in their application, whereas other approaches (RIMA and TANGO) performed no better than random chance. Furthermore, none of the resilience measures predicted significantly better than the far simpler approach of using the most recent observed value of wellbeing to predict future wellbeing. Therefore, Upton et al. (2022) argue, the value added in terms of predictive and targeting performance by these measures remains unclear. Overall, Upton et al. (2022) conclude that “the approaches presently in play are all, at best, imperfect, and at worst deeply flawed.”</p> <p>Currently, there is a shortage of alternative resilience indicators suitable for inclusion in a holistic survey (that is, robust yet not requiring time-consuming data collection). The World Bank is working on a Causal machine Learning Approach to Resilience Estimation (CLARE), which is rooted in an impact evaluation framework and causal machine learning algorithms applied to longitudinal household survey data. The indicator is model-agnostic, data-driven, scalable, and normatively anchored to wellbeing thresholds, and can be either shock-specific or a general-purpose resilience metric. CLARE is calculated using data on food consumption, food insecurity, drought, shocks, gender, household size and demographic structure, assets and access to services. However, the reliance on repeat survey data may present a constraint to use in projects with short timespans or limited resources.</p>
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (FAO, 2016) – RIMA • Upton et al. (2022) • (Alloush and Carter, 2024) • (Cerqua et al., 2024) - CLARE

2.6.Complementary indicators

These indicators cannot be calculated from data collected through the standard HOLPA survey, yet are recommended for inclusion as complementary performance indicators for projects with capacity to collect additional data.

2.6.1. Bat, bird and insect diversity

Indicator	Bat, bird and insect diversity
Theme	Biodiversity
Purpose of indicator	Relevant for the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework Target 10 on ‘Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture’. In addition to evaluation of on farm crop and Livestock diversity, this metric will summarise species level diversity of trees, birds and insects within the farm landscape used by farmers. It will combine field transects and use state of the art acoustic monitoring and school-based citizen science monitoring to evaluate, bird, insect and bat diversity across the ALLs.
Data source	Field survey, field based Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM), and citizen science
Measurement	Bird species diversity and guilds, insect diversity, based on acoustic profiles, and bat diversity, based on automatic monitoring.
Measurement units	Bird, Bat and Insect diversity, species number.
Guidance on measurement	<p>This indicator can be calculated by collecting data on the:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total number of bird species, and their guilds (forest species, generalist, rarity). • Total number of detected insect species or complexity of insect acoustic profile. <p>These data can be collected as part of a field survey, and using base stations set up in each ALL. To verify the data, and help to obtain area estimates, users can work with the SoundLab University of Wisconsin or other established analysts.</p>
Guidance on data entry and reporting	Be sure to use the same area units and monitoring acoustic stations for all sites and species/, so that diversity indices can be calculated. Bird, bat and insect species names should be stored in the local language and also using their scientific and English names to enable comparisons across sites.

References

Ross, S.R.J., O'Connell, D.P., Deichmann, J.L., Desjonquères, C., Gasc, A., Phillips, J.N., Sethi, S.S., Wood, C.M. and Burivalova, Z., Passive Acoustic Monitoring provides a fresh perspective on fundamental ecological questions. *Functional Ecology*.(Ross et al., 2023)

2.6.2. Pollinator diversity

Indicator	Insect pollinator diversity
Theme	Biodiversity
Purpose of indicator	Relevant for the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework Goal B on conserving services provided by ecosystems (CBD/COP/15/L.26). Pollinator declines are threatening agricultural production in multiple regions (Millard et al., 2021; Soroye et al., 2020), while pollinator deficits are directly linked to poor human diets and nutrition-related diseases (Smith et al., 2022, 2015). Most fruit and vegetable crops are pollinator-dependent and fruits and vegetables are a vital source of vitamins for people (Chaplin-Kramer et al., 2014).
Data source	Direct measurement in field
Measurement	Sweep netting, pan traps and/or targeted field observations in quadrats
Measurement units	Count with species of pollinator (clearly differentiating between visitor and pollinator) per unit time of observation within a defined area (plot), transect length and number of stops (with standardised number of sweeps/ time period), number of visits to the flowers by the pollinator. For pan traps, collections separated by colour of bowls placed for fixed durations (start and end time to be noted and to be consistent about the time and duration).
Guidance on measurement	<p>For a general insect pollinator diversity and abundance study, sweep netting along a transect (a fixed or variable corridor of flowering plants walked for a set distance and/or time, and pollinators either identified through visual observations, caught for laboratory identification, or a mixture of both approaches) or pan traps (a triplet of plastic bowls of about 350 ml capacity; sprayed with UV fluorescent paint with 1 white, 1 yellow, 1 blue; with each bowl containing 100 ml of water plus a drop of unscented detergent to break surface tension and placed at ground-level, or mounted at surrounding crop flower height, in order to trap bees for subsequent laboratory identifications) along transects can be used to collect pollinator data in non-cropped areas, while targeted field observations on small quadrats / plots (a fixed plot of flowers observed for a fixed amount of time where the visitors can either be identified visually and/or caught for laboratory identification) and/ or pan traps can be used to collect pollinator data on cropped land.</p> <p>Sweep netting is effective for catching a wide range of pollinators. Sweep netting requires killing insects, but to reduce mortalities, experienced enumerators could release common pollinators. However inexperienced enumerators will need to retain all insects so these can be correctly identified.</p> <p>On fields where farmers do not want us to sweep net, pan traps can be used instead. Pan traps are effective for monitoring flying insects as long as there is water access on field and the pans don't get stolen or</p>

	<p>damaged (elephants and other wildlife can be a problem). Samples need to be harvested on a timely basis, because they rapidly deteriorate. Pan traps require minor funding for installation.</p> <p>Targeted observations on small quadrats / plots involves using a frame of a defined size (size large enough to be able to observe by 1 observer based on the pollinator activity and observability of the researcher, Ex: 50*50 cm plot), number of floral units within the plot, or fixed number of branches or flowers depending on the type of plants being observed. The investment is minimal but requires some amount of training.</p> <p>Ideally pollinators should be identified to genus or species level with the assistance of trained experts. Local universities could be contacted to identify such experts.</p> <p>Pan traps are better for solitary bees and hoverflies, while transects or plots are better for social bees and other insects. The methods will have to be adapted based of the crop type or pollinators of interest.</p> <p>The floral resources available per unit area can also be recorded.</p> <p><i>Note on other methods</i> Sticky traps are an easy and often cheap option, but are less suitable to monitoring a diverse set of flower visitors.</p>
<p>Guidance on data entry and reporting</p>	<p>The data will have to be recorded based on the method employed. Record crop type/ type of habitat being observed, field and plot number, replication, time of observation for all methods. Additionally, for-</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Transect: Length of the transect, number stops, time spent per stop and number of sweeps need to be consistent. Record species collected/ observed, stored species to be labelled for further identification. 2. Pan traps: Number of traps, colour combination, distance between two trap stations, replications (or transect length)- need to be consistent. Segregate species collected based on trap colours and trap station and transect number. Record the species and number of individuals while sorting at the lab. 3. Targeted observations on plots: Plot size, replications (within plot and within field), extent of time observed needs to be consistent. Number of visits (a visit is counted only if the insect makes contact with the floral reproductive organ) and species visiting the target species per plot/ branch/ flower.
<p>References</p>	<p>O'Connor et al. (2019)(O'Connor et al., 2019) Hicks et al. (2016)(Hicks et al., 2016)</p>

2.6.3. Soil health (SOCLA)

Indicator	Soil health
Theme	Soil health
Purpose of indicator	Healthy soils underpin healthy and productive agroecosystems. This indicator contributes to Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) indicator 2.4.1 which includes a sub-indicator on ‘prevalence of soil degradation’, and SDG indicator 15.3.1 on ‘proportion of degraded land’.
Data source	Field measurement
Measurement	Latin American Society for Agroecology (SOCLA) indicators of soil health, adapted by TAPE
Measurement units	Score from 1 to 5, representing the mean indicator value across 10 indicators
Guidance on measurement	<p>Soil health can be determined through field surveys with values for 10 indicators of soil health determined jointly by the farmer and enumerator. The proposed indicators were developed by the Latin American Society for Agroecology (SOCLA) and described in Nicholls et al. (2004)(Nicholls et al., 2004b).</p> <p>Data are collected by digging or picking up a small amount of soil to examine it more closely, in each of the same 10x10m square plots used to assess biodiversity. The SOCLA 10 indicators of soil health are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Soil structure 2. Degree of compaction 3. Soil depth 4. Status of residues 5. Colour, odour and organic matter 6. Water retention 7. Soil cover 8. Signs of erosion 9. Presence of invertebrates 10. Microbiological activity <p>Note, for the SOCLA analysis of soil health, you will require a wire flag (length ~50 cm, thickness ~0.08 mm) and hydrogen peroxide (volume ~100 ml). The measurement of compaction (indicator number 2) requires a wire flag which is pressed vertically into the soil, and the level of compaction is determined based on the depth at which the wire bends due to the resistance in the soil caused by compaction. Measuring microbiological activity (indicator number 10) requires hydrogen peroxide, which is poured in small quantities to assess the effervescence in soil.</p>

Little or no effervescence indicates soil with little organic matter and poor microbial activity, while high effervescence indicates rich organic matter and greater microbial activity(Nicholls et al., 2004b).

Each indicator is scored from 1 to 10 based on the following guidelines(Nicholls et al., 2004b):

Indicators of soil quality	Established value	Characteristics
Structure	1	Loose, powdery soil without visible aggregates
	5	Few aggregates that break with little pressure
	10	Well-formed aggregates – difficult to break
Compaction	1	Compacted soil, flag bends readily
	5	Thin compacted layer, some restrictions to a penetrating wire
	10	No compaction, flag can penetrate all the way into the soil
Soil depth	1	Exposed subsoil
	5	Thin superficial soil
	10	Superficial soil (> 10 cm)
Status of residues	1	Slowly decomposing organic residues
	5	Presence of last year's decomposing residues
	10	Residues in various stages of decomposition, most residues well-decomposed
Color, odor, and organic matter	1	Pale, chemical odor, and no presence of humus
	5	Light brown, odorless, and some presence of humus
	10	Dark brown, fresh odor, and abundant humus
Water retention (moisture level after irrigation or rain)	1	Dry soil, does not hold water
	5	Limited moisture level available for short time
	10	Reasonable moisture level for a reasonable period of time
Soil cover	1	Bare soil
	5	Less than 50% soil covered by residues or live cover
	10	More than 50% soil covered by residues or live cover
Erosion	1	Severe erosion, presence of small gullies
	5	Evident, but low erosion signs
	10	No visible signs of erosion
Presence of invertebrates	1	No signs of invertebrate presence or activity
	5	A few earthworms and arthropods present
	10	Abundant presence of invertebrate organisms
Microbiological activity	1	Very little effervescence after application of water peroxide
	5	Light to medium effervescence
	10	Abundant effervescence

When the scoring of the indicators is complete, the values assigned to the indicators are added and divided by the number of measured indicators to obtain a mean value between 1-10.

Guidance on data entry and reporting

Record the score from 1 to 10. Be sure to take a GPS point and keep a record of the geographic coordinates where soil samples were taken to allow follow-up surveys in the same locations.

References

- 4.1.1. Nicholls et al. (2004)(Nicholls et al., 2004b)
- 4.1.2. FAO (2019)(FAO, 2019)

2.6.4. Nutrient use efficiency

Indicator	Nutrient use efficiency
Theme	Nutrient management
Purpose of indicator	Nutrient use efficiency (NUE) is important indicator in nutrient management as it provides information on the efficiency of inputs use, which has important implications for crop productivity, economic viability, and environmental sustainability. By monitoring NUE, farmers and agronomists can determine if the current inputs are meeting the nutrient needs of the crop and if adjustments are needed to optimize inputs use and reduce nutrient losses to the environment. This indicator is also related to a number of Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) e.g SDG 2 on zero hunger and SDG 15 life on land.
Data source	Field measurements, farm surveys (interviews and questionnaires), extension and agricultural officers
Measurement	Nutrient use efficiency (uptake and losses) in the production system
Measurement units	Harvested produce (kg) per unit N input (kg) per year, disaggregated by organic or chemical inputs. Can be presented as a ratio or as a percentage (%) of output removal over inputs.
Guidance on measurement	<p>Nutrient use efficiency as an indicator can be determined at the three levels i.e. plot level (the level of individual crops), farm level (the level of a whole farm and its cropping system), and landscape level (a larger area e.g. region or watershed).</p> <p>Data can be collected on growth parameters considering key stages of crop cycle as different stages have varied needs of nutrients uptake and utilization. Growth rate, change in biomass (root and above ground biomass). Nutrient uptake can be estimated by multiplying the N concentration of the plant by its biomass.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Nutrient input- amount of nutrient (such as nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), or potassium (K)) that is added to the farm system, either through fertilization or other means. ii. Nutrient uptake- amount of nutrient that is taken up by the crops and other plants growing in the farm system. iii. Boundary definition: extent of the system being studied, and includes the inputs and outputs that are considered in the NUE calculation. iv. Crop yield: total biomass produced by the crops in the farm system. Crop yield can be used to estimate nutrient uptake, as nutrient uptake is proportional to crop yield. <p>Plant tissue analysis: analysis of plant tissue samples, such as leaves or stems, to determine the nutrient concentration and biomass of the plants growing in the farm system.</p>

	<p>At plot level it is important that regular measurements of the plant growth and nutrient uptake are done using standardized methods. e.g. Kjeldahl digestion for N content or the calorimetric methods.</p> <p>At farm level, a standardized data collection and analysis method across multiple plots is required. With accurate recordings of crop rotations, soil management and nutrient inputs.</p> <p>Farm definitions and specialization of system being studied e.g arable farms, horticultural farms, mixed crop-livestock. The spatial and temporal limits may include study the whole farm or during a growing season or over number years. Most recommended should be in yearly basis ($\text{kg ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$).</p> <p>NUE at landscape level will include a standardized method of data collection and analysis from multiple farms, proper delineation of boundaries of different farm practices (e.g arable, horticultural, mixed crop-livestock) including environmental and socio-economic factors to account for farm heterogeneity.</p> <p>The method to determine NUE at all scales is $\text{NUE} = \text{N output} / \text{N input}$. At all scales, it is good to consider all possible sources of inputs into the system to avoid under or overestimation of the NUE.</p> <p>Specific survey questions should address the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the amount of nutrient input, such as nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), or potassium (K), added to the farm system through fertilization or other means? In kg ha^{-1} • How many crop cycles or seasons do you have in a year and different crops in specific plots considering rotations • Yield obtained in the farm (tha^{-1}) edible portion +stover yield categorized for each product grown in the farm /plot • For farm surveys we need specific concentration/content of nutrients in the harvested products – secondary co-efficient can be obtained from literature or specific analysis can be done on sampled products.
<p>Guidance on data entry and reporting</p>	<p>Uniform data entry and all conversion of inputs and output to be reported in $\text{kg ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$. Define the unit of measurement (e.g. $\text{kg N uptake per kg N applied}$, % N, etc) and make sure all data is reported consistently using the same unit.</p>
<p>References</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dobermann, (2007)(Dobermann, 2007) • European Union Nitrogen Use Efficiency (NUE) (2016)(EU Nitrogen Expert Panel, 2016)

2.6.1. Nutrient balance

Indicator	Nutrient balance
Theme	Nutrient management
Purpose of indicator	Nutrient balance is the difference between the nutrient inputs entering a farming system (mainly livestock manure and fertilisers) and the nutrient outputs leaving the system (the uptake of nutrients for crop and pasture production). A nutrient deficit indicates declining soil fertility. A nutrient surplus indicates a risk of polluting soil, water, and air. Nutrient balances are important indicators of land degradation and water pollution, relevant to SDG 6, 15, and the UNCCD.
Data source	Field measurements, farm surveys (interviews and questionnaires), extension and agricultural officers
Measurement	Mass balance of inputs and outputs in the systems (including all sources of inputs and all sources of output in a defined system)
Measurement units	Kg of N per ha
Guidance on measurement	<p>The OECD system calculates nutrient loadings for nitrogen and phosphorus to agricultural soils. It is a fairly complex system based on wide range of data sources. Nutrient inputs and offtakes are estimated by applying coefficients to physical data. The physical data covers livestock numbers, crop areas, crop yields and fertiliser use. The relevant coefficients have been developed by empirical research by experts (e.g. ADAS) within a large programme of research projects.</p> <p>Input indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mineral fertiliser consumption - Cropping/livestock patterns (active pasture land, area of potentially fertilized land) - Farm management practices (seed and planting materials, crop residues, manure production and use) <p>Output indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ammonia emissions - Emissions of methane and nitrous oxide - Nitrates/pesticides in water

- Share of agriculture in nitrate contamination

Issues to be aware of:

- Estimates for offtake from pasture are based on average pasture yields and an assumed rate of grazing. Pasture represents a very significant part of the overall offtake and improvements in these estimates would greatly improve the overall accuracy of the balance sheets.
- Estimates of fertiliser use at below national level are based on a national average application rate for each crop type. Due to regional variation in practice, estimates would be improved if regional level application rates for each crop type could be estimated.
- The land to be used in the scope of the balance sheets must be correctly defined. If unfertilised land is included, the balance sheets will underestimate the total nutrient loadings. Reflecting this, the UK excluded land identified as “rough grazing” from the balance sheets.
- Manure is assumed to be applied to the same parcel of land on which the livestock are grazed/reared. This assumption is robust at aggregated levels but may not be valid at finer spatial scales, particularly at a holding level.

Questions to guide data collection in surveys

- What crops are grown on the farm and in what rotation?
- What is the typical cropping period for each crop?
- What type of fertilizers/inputs are used on the farm?
- How are the fertilizers /inputs applied (e.g., broadcast, banded)?
- How often are fertilizers /inputs applied and in what amounts?
- What is the source of nitrogen inputs to the farm (e.g., fertilizer, organic matter)?
- What is the amount of nutrient input per hectare and per year?
- How is the nitrogen input managed (e.g., application rate, timing, method)?
- What is the amount of nitrogen taken up by crops per hectare and per year-this can be determined by knowing the yield (stover/grain- tha^{-1})?

Guidance on data entry and reporting	Data recorded on input and output as kg ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹
References	OECD/Eurostat Methodology and Handbook (2014)(OECD and Eurostat, 2014)

2.6.2. Greenhouse gas emissions

Indicator	Greenhouse gas emissions
Theme	Climate mitigation
Purpose of indicator	Relevant for global climate mitigation goals (Paris Agreement) and nationally determined contributions (NDCs).
Data source	Farmer survey, literature review, and/or field measurements
Measurement	Emissions of nitrous oxide, methane and CO ₂ (the main greenhouse gases, GHGs) minus carbon storage and sequestration by above-ground biomass
Measurement units	t C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹
Guidance on measurement	<p>Measuring GHG emissions</p> <p>We discuss two options for measurement, i) using emission factors, ii) direct measurement.</p> <p><i>Using emission factors</i></p> <p><i>lan</i></p> <p>This method is based on guidelines provided by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC 2006). GHGs are estimated by multiplying the activity data for the activity of interest with emission factors.</p> <p>To apply this approach in estimating GHGs, the activity data for the area of interest needs to be well documented. This can be done as part of the household survey and supplemented with information from literature. For example, to estimate direct N₂O emissions from agricultural soils in a certain region, one would require information on the use of fertilizers and manure, amount of N fixed by crops, amount of crop residues returned to soils, N-fixing crops, area of the cultivated crop and two emission factors, i.e. one for N inputs into soil and one for cultivation of organic soils. Detailed guidelines, examples, and training materials on how to apply the emission factors methodology to estimate GHGs can be found in the Non-Annex I training package (https://unfccc.int/resource/cd_roms/na1/ghg_inventories/index.htm).</p>

For livestock, much of the information required to calculate GHG emissions will be collected as part of the Animal health and welfare survey.

Step-by-step procedure:

1. Within the area of study (e.g. the ALL), identify the major land uses, crops and livestock species.
2. For each crop and livestock species selected, gather spatially-explicit management information (plot level information for crops and individual animal level information for livestock) together with associated soil and climatic information. Include as many plots/livestock number as possible to make the data representative for the area of interest.
3. Gather total crop area and livestock number (segregated by type, breed, sex, age etc) within the smallest geographical unit (e.g. district)
4. By using the management information collected in step 2, use the IPCC tier 1 emission factors co-efficients to estimate the emissions.

Direct measurement

For direct measurement of greenhouse gas emissions at farm level, use the “Static chamber method” and procedures as described in Rosenstock et al. (2016)(Rosenstock et al., 2016).

Briefly, the chambers, made of plastic and of known dimensions are inserted into the soil to certain depths (forming bases), approximately one week before planting. About 3-5 chamber bases are inserted per plot per replicate. Base height dimensions are taken, the bases are then covered with special lids (vented, fitted with thermometers, fans, batteries and gas sampling ports) and are tightly clamped. Gas samples are collected following certain considerations (i.,e, timing, intervals, storage, etc) and taken to the laboratory for gas chromatography (GC) analysis to detect the three GHG (nitrous oxide, methane and CO₂).

Sampling requires some level of skills/expertise, i.e., drawing the gas from the chambers using the syringes should not be rushed but also not be done too slowly. When transferring the gases to the vials (evacuated) from the syringes, part of the gas (about 30 mls) should be used to push out the pre-existing gases in those vials and the remaining 30 ml retained in the tightly sealed vial (this is the one taken to the lab for GC). Training will be needed for these procedures, which will need just one day.

<p>Guidance on data entry and reporting</p>	<p>Direct measurement at plot level</p> <p>For direct plot measurements, proper frequency of gas sampling should be observed; guided by the prevailing environmental conditions. Under normal conditions, sampling should be done once per week. However, the frequency of sampling can be increased to 2 times per week under periods of expected high emissions in the field e.g., after rainfall, fertilization or soil disturbances like weeding. Sampling should be done between 9am to noon. In each sampling activity from the plot level, the following data should be entered:</p> <p>Name of recorder, Date of sampling; Land use type; Name of site/experiment; Plot number; Air temperature and Air pressure. 3-4 chambers can be used per plot. In each of the 3 or 4 chambers bases installed, record the chamber heights (h1, h2, h3 and h4). When sampling begins, for each chamber base, record the start temperature (T1) and the stop temperature (T4) for every chamber. In each chamber, gas withdrawal (sampling) intervals can be timed at either 10 or 15 minutes, or what is feasible. Gas samples should be taken at 4 time intervals, starting from T0. At every time interval (I.e, T0, T15, T30 or T45 mins), record the start time, stop time and properly label the gas vial after transferring the gas sample. Other additional parameters to record would be the soil moisture and soil temperature per plot in every sampling activity.</p> <p>The measurement unit is t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹.</p>
<p>References</p>	<p>Rosenstock et al. (2016)(Rosenstock et al., 2016) IPCC 2006, 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, Prepared by the National Greenhouse Gas Inventories Programme, Eggleston H.S., Buendia L., Miwa K., Ngara T. and Tanabe K. (eds). Published: IGES, Japan. https://unfccc.int/resource/cd_roms/na1/ghg_inventories/index.htm https://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/public/2019rf/vol4.html https://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/public/2019rf/index.html</p>

2.6.3. Enteric methane emission intensity

Indicator	Enteric methane emission intensity (emission per unit of product and emission per unit of fodder dry matter intake)
Theme	Climate mitigation
Purpose of indicator	In Sub Saharan Africa, a large diversity of diets (forage + staple food crop residues or other agricultural byproducts) is used by ruminants herders in different production systems. It is reported that feeding strategies could help to reduce enteric methane (eCH ₄) in ruminants by up to 55%. We aimed to measure <i>in vivo</i> eCH ₄ emission in ruminants during each season of the year in order to test different feeding strategies and to and to assess their potential to mitigate eCH ₄ emission.
Data source	Herders survey on feeding strategies and feeding practices, literature review, Data from ongoing projects, and field measurements
Measurement	Daily fodder intake, fodder digestibility, fodder quality, enteric methane emission (eCH ₄)
Measurement units	(gDMI/LW, g/kgDMI, eCH ₄ /TLU/year)
Guidance on measurement	<p><i>Direct measurement</i></p> <p>For direct measurement of enteric methane emission at animal level, use the GreenFeed system as described in (Hristov et al., 2015). In SSA, GF is actually in experiment in Burkina Faso (Ouermi et al., 2022; Gbénou et al., 2022a, 2022b).</p> <p>GreenFeed (GF) system is a device that can be used at pasture to measure eCH₄ of cattle individually (K. J. Hammond et al., 2016; Mombach et al., 2018; Zhao et al., 2020). It is equipped with an automatic baiting system which drop attracted pelleted feed in a tray. Animals are free in their movement and eating behavior to feed on pasture and in the GF. Emission is measured when animals visit to the system to consume bait. The system sucks air through the animal's nose and mouth into a duct with airflow measured (Huhtanen et al., 2015). Most methane is eructated at 40–120s intervals. Animals can visit the unit at any time according to timing of feed availability and distribution of eCH₄ measurements across various times of the day programing by investigators (Hristov et al., 2015). Pellet is generally dropped each 30s or 1min. Programming of eCH₄ measurements must take account of eating behavior (feeding, rumination, walk, drinking, calm) and will allows to implicate all daily activities on pasture. To be sure to not modify food intake by cattle on pasture and have best or good data, bait may contain forage that animals are grazing. Few times between 3-7 min by visit are significant to have a good measurement (Hristov et al., 2015). A significant correlation ($R^2 = 0.92$) between the eCH₄ measurements with GF and RC was revealed (Huhtanen et al., 2019). On pasture, animals don't graze at night. GF can be moved to animals parking at night do complete measure. GF can be used to describe diurnal eCH₄ emissions.</p>

Guidance on data entry and reporting	Database accessible for different feeding strategies
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hristov, A.N., Oh, J., Giallongo, F., Frederick, T., Weeks, H., Zimmerman, P.R., Harper, M.T., Hristova, R.A., Zimmerman, R.S., Branco, A.F., 2015. The Use of an Automated System (GreenFeed) to Monitor Enteric Methane and Carbon Dioxide Emissions from Ruminant Animals. JoVE 52904. https://doi.org/10.3791/52904(Hristov et al., 2015) • Hristov, A.N., Ott, T., Tricarico, J., Rotz, A., Waghorn, G., Adesogan, A., Dijkstra, J., Montes, F., Oh, J., Kebreab, E., Oosting, S.J., Gerber, P.J., Henderson, B., Makkar, H.P.S., Firkins, J.L., 2013. SPECIAL TOPICS — Mitigation of methane and nitrous oxide emissions from animal operations: III. A review of animal management mitigation options1. Journal of Animal Science 91, 5095–5113. https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2013-6585(Hristov et al., 2013) • Gbenou, G. X., Assouma, M. H., Zampaligre, N., Bois, B., Kiendrebeogo, T., Martin, C., ... & Dossa, L. H. (2022, December). Emission of enteric methane in cold dry season in sudanians peulh zebus in west africa. In 26. Rencontres autour des Recherches sur les Ruminants.(Gbenou et al., 2022)

3. Calculating indicator scores from survey responses

3.1. Agroecology indicators

HOLPA users can convert all responses in the Agroecology module to a score from 1 to 5, using Table 1. For each of the 13 principles, users can calculate the median score, excluding missing data. This represents the agroecology integration indicator score for each principle. To obtain a single score representing the level of agroecology adherence, take the median across the 13 indicators.

Table 1: Scores to assign to agroecology module responses

PRINCIPLE	#	QUESTION	ANSWER	SCORE
RECYCLING	1	Where do you source most of your seeds?	<i>All seeds are self-produced, exchanged with other farmers or managed collectively.</i>	5
			<i>25% of seeds are purchased from the market, the other 75% is self-produced or exchanged.</i>	4
			<i>50% of seeds are purchased from the market, the other 50% is self-produced or exchanged.</i>	3
			<i>75% of seeds are purchased from the market, the other 25% are self-produced or exchanged.</i>	2
			<i>All seeds are purchased from the market (e.g., agrovet, seed stores, farmers' cooperatives, seed suppliers, etc.).</i>	1
	2	Where do you source most of your manure and compost?	<i>All manure and compost are self-produced, exchanged with other farmers or managed collectively.</i>	5
			<i>25% of the manure and compost are purchased from the market, the other 75% is self-produced or exchanged.</i>	4
			<i>50% of the manure and compost purchased from the market, the other 50% is self-produced or exchanged.</i>	3
			<i>75% of the manure and compost are purchased from the market, the other 25% are self-produced or exchanged.</i>	2
			<i>All manure and compost are purchased from the market.</i>	1
	3	Where do you source most of your livestock?	<i>All animal genetic resources are self-produced, exchanged with other farmers or managed collectively.</i>	5
			<i>25% of animal genetic resources are purchased from the market, the other 75% is self-produced or exchanged.</i>	4
			<i>50% of the breeding are purchased from the market, the other 50% is self-produced or exchanged with neighboring farms.</i>	3
			<i>75% of animal genetic resources are purchased from the market, the other 25% are self-produced or exchanged.</i>	2

PRINCIPLE	#	QUESTION	ANSWER	SCORE	
	4	Where do you source most of your spawn, fry or fingerling species and varieties?	<i>All animal genetic resources (e.g., chicks, young animals, semen) are purchased from the market.</i>	1	
			<i>All fish genetic resources are self-produced, exchanged with other farmers or managed collectively.</i>	5	
			<i>25% of fish genetic resources are purchased from the market, the other 75% is self-produced or exchanged.</i>	4	
			<i>50% of fish genetic resources are purchased from the market, the other 50% is self-produced or exchanged with neighboring farms.</i>	3	
			<i>75% of fish genetic resources are purchased from the market, the other 25% are self-produced or exchanged.</i>	2	
			<i>All fish genetic resources (e.g., spawn, fry, fingerling species and varieties) are purchased from the market.</i>	1	
	5	Where do you source most of your energy?	<i>All energy is self-produced, exchanged with other farmers or managed collectively.</i>	5	
			<i>25% of energy is purchased from the market, the other 75% is self-produced or exchanged.</i>	4	
			<i>50% of energy is purchased from the market, the other 50% produced on farm/within the agroecosystem or exchanged with other members of the community.</i>	3	
			<i>75% of energy is purchased from the market, the other 25% is produced on farm/within the agroecosystem or exchanged with other members of the community.</i>	2	
			<i>All energy is purchased from the market.</i>	1	
	INPUT REDUCTION	1	Over the past 12 months, what did you do to improve soil fertility of cropland?	<i>No ecological practices, chemical or organic fertilizer were applied.</i>	5
				<i>Only ecological practices are applied</i>	5
				<i>Combination of ecological practices and organic fertilizers or manure are applied. Or only organic fertilizers or manure are applied.</i>	4

PRINCIPLE	#	QUESTION	ANSWER	SCORE
			<i>Combination of ecological practices and organic fertilizers or manure and/or chemical fertilizers is applied</i>	3
			<i>Combination of chemical fertilizers and organic fertilizers or manure are applied</i>	2
			<i>Only chemical fertilizers applied</i>	1
	2	Over the past 12 months, what did you do to manage pests in cropland?	<i>Only ecological practices are applied</i>	5
			<i>Combination of ecological practices and non-chemical pesticides. Or only non-chemical pesticides</i>	4
			<i>Combination of chemical and non-chemical pesticides and/or ecological practices</i>	3
			<i>Combination of chemical and non-chemical pesticides</i>	2
			<i>Only chemical pesticides are applied</i>	1
	3	Are livestock fed with dry feed (e.g., grains, hay)?	<i>Never</i>	5
			<i>Rarely</i>	4
			<i>Sometimes</i>	3
			<i>Often</i>	2
			<i>All the time</i>	1
	4	What types of fish feed did you primarily use in the last 12 months?	<i>Only natural feeds used</i>	5
			<i>Combination of natural and prepared organic feed used. Or only organic feed used.</i>	4
			<i>Combination of natural, preprepared organic feeds and prepared chemical feeds used</i>	3
			<i>Combination of prepared organic and chemical feeds used</i>	2
			<i>Only chemical feeds used</i>	1
	5	Over the past 12 months, how did you manage livestock diseases.	<i>No action taken.</i>	5
			<i>Only ecological practices/treatments (e.g., quarantine measures, genetic selection for disease resistance).</i>	5
<i>Combination of ecological practices/treatments and organic inputs OR only organic inputs (e.g., herbal remedies or traditional medicine, organic treatments,).</i>			4	
<i>Combination of ecological practices/treatments, and chemical and organic inputs.</i>			3	

PRINCIPLE	#	QUESTION	ANSWER	SCORE
			<i>Combination of chemical and organic inputs. .</i>	2
			<i>Only chemical inputs (e.g., antibiotics, vaccination).</i>	1
	6	Over the past 12 months, how did you manage fish diseases	<i>No action taken.</i>	5
			<i>Only ecological practices/treatments.</i>	5
			<i>Combination of ecological practices/treatments and organic inputs. Or only organic inputs</i>	4
			<i>Combination of ecological practices/treatments, and chemical and organic inputs.</i>	3
			<i>Combination of chemical and organic inputs.</i>	2
<i>Only chemical inputs.</i>	1			
SOIL HEALTH	1	Which ecological practices do you use on cropland to improve soil quality and health?	<i>Implementing 4 or more practices.</i>	5
			<i>Implementing 3 practices.</i>	4
			<i>Implementing 2 practices.</i>	3
			<i>Implementing 1 practice.</i>	2
			<i>Not implementing any practice.</i>	1
ANIMAL HEALTH	1	Are the animals on your farm healthy and happy?	<i>Animals do not suffer from stress, hunger, thirst, pain, or diseases, and are slaughtered in a way to avoid unnecessary pain.</i>	5
			<i>Animals do not suffer from hunger, thirst or diseases but can experience stress, especially at slaughter.</i>	4
			<i>Animals do not suffer from hunger or thirst, but suffer from stress, may be prone to diseases and can suffer from pain at slaughter.</i>	3
			<i>Animals suffer periodically/seasonally from hunger and thirst, stress or diseases, and are slaughtered without avoiding unnecessary pain.</i>	2
			<i>Animals suffer from hunger and thirst, stress and diseases all year long, and are slaughtered without avoiding unnecessary pain.</i>	1
	2	What do you do on the farm to keep animals healthy and happy?	<i>Implementing 4 or more practices.</i>	5
			<i>Implementing 3 practices.</i>	4
			<i>Implementing 2 practices.</i>	3

PRINCIPLE	#	QUESTION	ANSWER	SCORE
			<i>Implementing 1 practice.</i>	2
			<i>No action taken.</i>	1
	3	On the fish production land, did you apply in the last 12 months any of the following practices?	<i>Implementing 4 or more practices.</i>	5
			<i>Implementing 3 practices.</i>	4
			<i>Implementing 2 practices.</i>	3
			<i>Implementing 1 practice.</i>	2
			<i>No action taken.</i>	1
BIODIVERSITY	1	In the last 12 months, how many different crops species (including perennial crops) were produced on your farm?	<i>Between the 76th and 100th percentile of crop species per farm, across the ALL</i>	5
			<i>Between the 51st and 75th percentile</i>	3.67
			<i>Between the 26th and 50th percentile</i>	2.34
			<i>Between the 1st and 25th percentile</i>	1
	2	In the last 12 months, which different livestock species did you keep?	<i>Between the 76th and 100th percentile of livestock species per farm, across the ALL</i>	5
			<i>Between the 51st and 75th percentile</i>	3.67
			<i>Between the 26th and 50th percentile</i>	2.34
			<i>Between the 1st and 25th percentile</i>	1
	3	Over the past 12 months, how many different fish species did you produce?	<i>Between the 76th and 100th percentile of fish species per farm, across the ALL</i>	5
			<i>Between the 51st and 75th percentile</i>	3.67
			<i>Between the 26th and 50th percentile</i>	2.34
			<i>Between the 1st and 25th percentile</i>	1
	4	How would you describe the diversity of trees (or perennial woody plants) on your farm?	<i>High: five or more species with different heights, woodiness, or flowering seasons.</i>	5
			<i>Medium: two to four species.</i>	3.67
			<i>Low: only one species.</i>	2.34
			<i>No trees or other woody perennials.</i>	1
	5	How would you describe the plant diversity (i.e., number of plant species) in natural and semi-natural vegetation [on land owned, rented or used by the household]? Include any natural or semi-natural vegetation (bushland, fallow land, hedgerows, natural grassland, ponds, lakes, forest patches etc.)	<i>High: five or more species with different heights, woodiness, or flowering seasons.</i>	5
			<i>Medium: two to four species.</i>	3.67
			<i>Low: only one species.</i>	2.34
			<i>No natural or semi-natural vegetation on-farm</i>	1

PRINCIPLE	#	QUESTION	ANSWER	SCORE
SYNERGY	1	<p>Count of all agroecological practices implemented, based on the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In the past, did you use any of these practices on your cropland? Which practices do you use on cropland to improve soil quality and health? What practices did you apply in the last 12 months on the farm to manage crop pests? On the grazing land (owned, leased or shared), did you apply in the last 12 months any of the following practices? On the fish production land, did you apply in the last 12 months any of the following practices? In addition to actions, you mentioned previously, is there anything else you do on your farm to make sure there are positive relationships between animals, crops, trees, soil and water? 	<p><i>Implementing four or more agroecological practices including:</i></p> <p><i>Agroforestry</i> <i>Cover crops</i> <i>Crop rotation</i> <i>Fallow (leave land unproductive)</i> <i>Hedgerows/Live fences</i> <i>Homegarden</i> <i>Intercropping</i> <i>Mulching</i> <i>Natural strips/vegetation</i> <i>Pollinator/Flower strips</i> <i>Pull-push</i> <i>Other (please specify)</i></p> <p><i>(Exclude:</i> <i>Monoculture with annual crops</i> <i>Monoculture with perennial crops</i> <i>Burning crop residues</i> <i>Land clearing for agriculture</i> <i>Overgrazing)</i></p>	5
			<p><i>Implementing three agroecological practices</i></p>	4
			<p><i>Implementing two agroecological practices</i></p>	3
			<p><i>Implementing one agroecological practice</i></p>	2

PRINCIPLE	#	QUESTION	ANSWER	SCORE
			<i>No agroecological practices</i>	1
ECONOMIC DIVERSIFICATION	1	Please select all the income sources your household has	<i>Five or more methods of income generation.</i>	5
			<i>Four methods of income generation.</i>	4
			<i>Three methods of income generation.</i>	3
			<i>Two methods of income generation.</i>	2
			<i>One method of income generation.</i>	1
CO-CREATION OF KNOWLEDGE	1	In the last 12 months, how many times has your household exchanged information with the following food system stakeholders to create new or improved solutions to your or others' farming problems? (Agricultural advisory services, consumers, food traders, government, NGOs, other farmers, researchers.)	<i>5 or more times per year.</i>	5
			<i>4 times per year.</i>	4
			<i>2 to 3 times per year.</i>	3
			<i>1 time per year.</i>	2
			<i>Never.</i>	1
	2	In the last 12 months, how many times has your household exchanged information with the following food system stakeholders to create new or improved solutions to your or others' farming problems?	<i>5 or more times per year.</i>	5
			<i>4 times per year.</i>	4
			<i>2 to 3 times per year.</i>	3
			<i>1 time per year.</i>	2
			<i>Never.</i>	1
	3	In the last 12 months, how many times has your household exchanged information with the following food system stakeholders to create new or improved solutions to your or others' farming problems?	<i>5 or more times per year.</i>	5
			<i>4 times per year.</i>	4
			<i>2 to 3 times per year.</i>	3
			<i>1 time per year.</i>	2
			<i>Never.</i>	1
	4	In the last 12 months, how many times has your	<i>5 or more times per year.</i>	5
			<i>4 times per year.</i>	4

PRINCIPLE	#	QUESTION	ANSWER	SCORE
		household exchanged information with the following food system stakeholders to create new or improved solutions to your or others' farming problems?	2 to 3 times per year.	3
			1 time per year.	2
			Never.	1
	5	In the last 12 months, how many times has your household exchanged information with the following food system stakeholders to create new or improved solutions to your or others' farming problems?	5 or more times per year.	5
			4 times per year.	4
			2 to 3 times per year.	3
			1 time per year.	2
			Never.	1
	6	In the last 12 months, how many times has your household exchanged information with the following food system stakeholders to create new or improved solutions to your or others' farming problems?	5 or more times per year.	5
			4 times per year.	4
			2 to 3 times per year.	3
			1 time per year.	2
			Never.	1
	7	In the last 12 months, how many times has your household exchanged information with the following food system stakeholders to create new or improved solutions to your or others' farming problems?	5 or more times per year.	5
			4 times per year.	4
2 to 3 times per year.			3	
1 time per year.			2	
Never.			1	
SOCIAL VALUES AND DIETS	1	Do you and your family have access to enough healthy food?	Good access.	5
			Fairly good.	4
			Moderate access.	3
			Limited access.	2
			No access at all.	1
	2	Do you and your family have access to enough diversified food?	Good access.	5
			Fairly good.	4
			Moderate access.	3
			Limited access.	2

PRINCIPLE	#	QUESTION	ANSWER	SCORE	
	3	Do you and your family have access to enough seasonal foods?	No access at all.	1	
			Good access.	5	
			Fairly good.	4	
			Moderate access.	3	
			Limited access.	2	
			No access at all.	1	
	4	Do you and your family have access to enough traditional food?	Good access.	5	
			Fairly good.	4	
			Moderate access.	3	
			Limited access.	2	
	FAIRNESS	1	Do you get a fair price for your produced CROPS?	Always get a fair price.	5
				Usually get a fair price, depending on the product.	4
				Occasionally get a fair price, depending on the product.	3
				Rarely get a fair price.	2
Never get a fair price. /I don't know				1	
2		Do you get a fair price for your produced LIVESTOCK?	Always get a fair price.	5	
			Usually get a fair price, depending on the product.	4	
			Occasionally get a fair price, depending on the product.	3	
			Rarely get a fair price.	2	
			Never get a fair price. /I don't know	1	
3		Do you get a fair price for your produced FISH?	Always get a fair price.	5	
			Usually get a fair price, depending on the product.	4	
			Occasionally get a fair price, depending on the product.	3	
			Rarely get a fair price.	2	
	Never get a fair price. /I don't know		1		
4	Do you get a fair price for your produced wood, bark, rubber, etc. (from TREES)?	Always get a fair price.	5		
		Usually get a fair price, depending on the product.	4		
		Occasionally get a fair price, depending on the product.	3		

PRINCIPLE	#	QUESTION	ANSWER	SCORE
			<i>Rarely get a fair price.</i>	2
			<i>Never get a fair price. /I don't know</i>	1
	5	Do you get a fair price for your produced HONEY?	<i>Always get a fair price.</i>	5
			<i>Usually get a fair price, depending on the product.</i>	4
			<i>Occasionally get a fair price, depending on the product.</i>	3
			<i>Rarely get a fair price.</i>	2
			<i>Never get a fair price. /I don't know</i>	1
	6	Do you get a fair price for your produced OTHER products?	<i>Always get a fair price.</i>	5
			<i>Usually get a fair price, depending on the product.</i>	4
<i>Occasionally get a fair price, depending on the product.</i>			3	
<i>Rarely get a fair price.</i>			2	
<i>Never get a fair price./I don't know</i>			1	
CONNECTIVITY	1	When you sell the produced CROPS, at least part of your production is sold to..	<i>Directly to consumers.</i>	5
			<i>To farmers organization / cooperative.</i>	4
			<i>To retailers such as supermarkets, grocery stores, or restaurants.</i>	3
			<i>To a middle man / aggregator.</i>	2
			<i>No products are sold.</i>	1
	2	When you sell the produced LIVESTOCK, at least part of your production is sold to..	<i>Directly to consumers.</i>	5
			<i>To farmers organization / cooperative.</i>	4
			<i>To retailers such as supermarkets, grocery stores, or restaurants.</i>	3
			<i>To a middle man / aggregator.</i>	2
			<i>No products are sold.</i>	1
	3	When you sell the produced FISH, at least part of your production is sold to..	<i>Directly to consumers.</i>	5
			<i>To farmers organization / cooperative.</i>	4
			<i>To retailers such as supermarkets, grocery stores, or restaurants.</i>	3
			<i>To a middle man / aggregator.</i>	2
			<i>No products are sold.</i>	1
	4	When you sell the produced wood, bark, rubber, etc.	<i>Directly to consumers.</i>	5
<i>To farmers organization / cooperative.</i>			4	

PRINCIPLE	#	QUESTION	ANSWER	SCORE
		(from TREES), at least part of your production is sold to..	<i>To retailers such as supermarkets, grocery stores, or restaurants.</i>	3
			<i>To a middle man / aggregator.</i>	2
			<i>No products are sold.</i>	1
	5	When you sell the produced HONEY, at least part of your production is sold to..	<i>Directly to consumers.</i>	5
			<i>To farmers organization / cooperative.</i>	4
			<i>To retailers such as supermarkets, grocery stores, or restaurants.</i>	3
			<i>To a middle man / aggregator.</i>	2
			<i>No products are sold.</i>	1
	6	When you sell OTHER products, at least part of your production is sold to..	<i>Directly to consumers.</i>	5
			<i>To farmers organization / cooperative.</i>	4
			<i>To retailers such as supermarkets, grocery stores, or restaurants.</i>	3
			<i>To a middle man / aggregator.</i>	2
LAND AND NATURAL RESOURCE GOVERNANCE	1	How often does your household participate in activities and meetings related to the management of your community's land and natural resources?	<i>Always participates.</i>	5
			<i>Most of the times participates.</i>	4
			<i>Sometimes participates.</i>	3
			<i>Rarely participates.</i>	2
			<i>Never participates.</i>	1
	2	How often does your household influence the decision-making that goes into the management of your community's land and natural resources?	<i>Contribute to all the decisions.</i>	5
			<i>Contribute to almost all the decisions.</i>	4
			<i>Contribute to some decisions.</i>	3
			<i>Contribute to few decisions.</i>	2
			<i>Did not contribute to any decision.</i>	1
	3	In your opinion, are your community's land and natural resources well-managed?	<i>Extremely well-managed.</i>	5
			<i>Well-managed.</i>	4
			<i>Moderately managed.</i>	3
			<i>Poorly managed.</i>	2
			<i>Not at all well-managed.</i>	1
PARTICIPATION	1	In your opinion, how effective are farmer associations/organizations at supporting farmers in business?	<i>Associations/organizations demonstrate exceptional effectiveness in supporting farmers' business ventures, offering comprehensive assistance, fostering growth, and ensuring long-term success.</i>	5
			<i>Associations/organizations play a significant role in supporting farmers' businesses, providing valuable resources,</i>	4

PRINCIPLE	#	QUESTION	ANSWER	SCORE
			<i>market opportunities, and essential services.</i>	
			Associations/organizations offer satisfactory support to farmers, aiding them in various aspects of their businesses (e.g., market access, information sharing, and capacity development).	3
			<i>Associations/organizations provide limited support to farmers in business, with marginal impact on their overall success.</i>	2
			<i>Associations/organizations offer no support to farmers' businesses.</i>	1
			<i>I don't know.</i>	1

3.2. Performance indicators

HOLPA users can calculate key performance indicator scores using Table 2 for each of the 18 performance themes. Users can then use Table 3 to convert indicator scores onto a standardised scale from 0 to 100 to calculate an overall performance score.

Table 2: Method for calculating key performance indicators

Performance theme (indicator #)	ID	Question	Response with assigned scores	Indicator calculation method	Indicator	Indicator units
Crop health (1)	1.1	What percentage of the total crop production was lost or damaged in the last 12 months?	[%]	n/a	% crops damaged or lost	%
Crop health (2)	1.2	How would you describe crop health from a score of 1 (lowest) to 5 (highest), for each of the following indicators? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appearance • Crop growth • Disease incidence • Insect pest incidence • Natural enemy abundance and diversity • Weed competition and pressure • Actual or potential yield • Vegetational diversity • Natural surrounding vegetation • Management system 	Likert scale 1-5 for each crop health indicator	Take median	Crop health, on a score of 1 (poor) to 5 (good)	Continuous in range 1-5

Performance theme (indicator #)	ID	Question	Response with assigned scores	Indicator calculation method	Indicator	Indicator units
Animal health	2.1	What was the extent of injury, illness, or death of livestock due to diseases in the last 12 months?	5-None 3.66-Low 2.34-Medium 1-High	Take the median value	Extent of injury, illness or death	Continuous in range 1 to 5
	2.2	What was the extent of injury, illness or death of fish due to diseases in the last 12 months?	5-None 3.66-Low 2.34-Medium 1-High			
Soil health (1)	3.1	What is the soil organic carbon content of soils on the farm?	[%, from three composite soil samples per farm]	Use established formulas to calculate the saturation of soil organic carbon (%) for each sample, and take the median	% saturation of soil organic carbon	%
	3.2	What is the share of clay, sand and silt of soils on the farm?	[%, from three composite soil samples per farm]			
Soil health (2)	3.3	How would you describe the fertility of soil on your farmland?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highly fertile (score 5) • Moderately fertile (score 3.66) • Low fertility (score 2.33) • Infertile (score 1). 	Take the median	Perception of soil erosion and fertility, from 1 (infertile and major soil erosion) to 5 (highly fertile with no soil erosion), by taking the median across the fertility and erosion responses	Continuous in range 1-5
	3.4	How would you describe the level of soil erosion problems on your farmland?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil erosion is a major problem on my farm (score 1) • Soil erosion is a minor problem on my farm (score 3) • Soil erosion is not a problem on 			

Performance theme (indicator #)	ID	Question	Response with assigned scores	Indicator calculation method	Indicator	Indicator units
			my farm (score 5)			
Nutrient use	4.1	Over the past 12 months, how much CHEMICAL FERTILIZER was applied to cropland?	[amount applied in kg; area it was applied to in hectares or acres]	Convert the amount applied to kg and the areas to hectares if needed. Divide to get the total kg fertilizer applied per ha	Total fertilizer applied per unit of cropland. Can be presented as a ratio of recommended fertilizer input intensity in the landscape obtained from extension services and literature	Kg/ha (or a ratio)
	4.2	Over the past 12 months, how much ORGANIC FERTILIZER was applied to cropland?	[amount applied in kg; area it was applied to in hectares or acres]			
Biodiversity (1)	5.1	How would you describe the diversity of insect pollinators on your farm?	5-High diversity: Abundant presence with a wide variety of species. 3.66-Medium diversity: Regularly seen with several species. 2.33-Low diversity: Rarely seen or limited to a few species. 1-None: No insects observed.	Take the median value	Diversity of animal species from 1 (no animals) to 5 (high diversity of animals)	Continuous in range 1-5
	5.2	How would you describe the diversity of crops	5-High diversity: Abundant			

Performance theme (indicator #)	ID	Question	Response with assigned scores	Indicator calculation method	Indicator	Indicator units
5.3		and livestock pest enemies on your farm?	presence with a wide variety of species. 3.66-Medium diversity: Regularly seen with several species. 2.33-Low diversity: Rarely seen or limited to a few species. 1-None: No insects observed.			
	5.3	How would you describe the diversity of crops and livestock pests on your farm?	5-High diversity: Abundant presence with a wide variety of species. 3.66-Medium diversity: Regularly seen with several species. 2.33-Low diversity: Rarely seen or limited to a few species. 1-None: No birds observed.			
	5.4	How would you describe the diversity of mammals on your farm?	5-High diversity: Abundant presence with a wide variety of species.			

Performance theme (indicator #)	ID	Question	Response with assigned scores	Indicator calculation method	Indicator	Indicator units
			3.66-Medium diversity: Regularly seen with several species. 2.33-Low diversity: Rarely seen or limited to a few species. 1-None: No mammals observed.			
Biodiversity (2)	5.5	How would you describe the amount of trees (or perennial woody crops) on your farm?	5-More than 50 trees (and/or other woody perennials) per hectare / acre. 3.66-21-50 trees (and/or other woody perennials) per hectare / acre. 2.33-1-20 trees (and/or other woody perennials) per hectare / acre. 1-No trees or other woody perennials.	Take the median	Diversity of trees from 1 (no trees) to 5 (high tree diversity)	Continuous in range 1-5
	5.6	How would you describe the diversity of trees (or perennial woody plants) on your farm?	5- High: five or more species with different heights, woodiness, or flowering seasons. 3.67- Medium: two			

Performance theme (indicator #)	ID	Question	Response with assigned scores	Indicator calculation method	Indicator	Indicator units
			to four species. 2.34- Low: only one species. 1- No trees or other woody perennials.			
Agrobiodiversity (1)	6.1	In the last 12 months, how many different crops species (including perennial crops) were produced on your farm?	Calculate the richness per farm.	Divide by the maximum richness found on any farm in the ALL.	Crop species richness relative to landscape maximum	Continuous
Agrobiodiversity (2)	6.2	In the last 12 months, how many different livestock species were owned by the household?	Calculate the richness per household.	Divide by the maximum richness found on any farm in the ALL.	Livestock species richness relative to landscape maximum	Continuous
Agrobiodiversity (3)	6.3	In the last 12 months, how many different fish species were kept on the farm?	Calculate the richness per farm.	Divide by the maximum richness found on any farm in the ALL.	Fish species richness relative to landscape maximum	Continuous
Agrobiodiversity (4)	6.4	Do the crops you grow come from certified quality seeds or locally adapted varieties (e.g., traditional cultivars, landraces)?	5: Only or mainly locally adapted varieties are grown. 4: Some certified seeds and some locally adapted varieties are grown (e.g., traditional cultivars, landraces). 3: Mainly certified seeds and	Take the median value	Use of local and certified crop varieties and livestock breeds from 1 (no known use) to 5 (dominant use)	Continuous from 1-5 (or Likert scale 1-5 if farm has only crops, or only livestock)

Performance theme (indicator #)	ID	Question	Response with assigned scores	Indicator calculation method	Indicator	Indicator units
Performance theme (indicator #)			<p>some locally adapted varieties are grown (e.g., traditional cultivars, landraces).</p> <p>2: Only or mainly certified quality seeds are grown.</p> <p>1: I don't know, or seeds are neither certified or locally adapted</p>			
	6.3	Are the livestock you keep exotic or local?	<p>5: Only or mainly local breeds are kept.</p> <p>4: 75% are local breeds, and 25% are exotic breeds and</p> <p>3: 75% are exotic breeds and 25% are local breeds.</p> <p>2: Equal numbers of exotic breeds and local breeds are kept.</p> <p>1: Only exotic breeds are kept.</p> <p>No data- No exotic or local breeds are kept; I don't know.</p>			

Performance theme (indicator #)	ID	Question	Response with assigned scores	Indicator calculation method	Indicator	Indicator units
Landscape complexity	7.1	How much land area is covered by natural and semi-natural vegetation on land owned, rented or used by the household?	5: More than 50% 4: 21-50% 3: 11-20% 2: 1-10% 1: None (0%)	Take the median	Landscape complexity from 1 (low complexity) to 5 (high complexity)	Continuous in range 1-5
	7.2	How would you describe the plant diversity (i.e., number of plant species) in natural and semi-natural vegetation [on land owned, rented or used by the household]?	5- High- five or more species with different heights, woodiness, or flowering seasons. 3.67- Medium- two to four species. 2.34: Low- only one species. 1: None			
Landscape complexity (alternative)	7.3	[Digitize from Google Earth imagery or calculate from <100m resolution imagery for a land cover maps, for a 1x1km square area around each field site GPS point. See the indicator protocol]	%	n/a	Share of farmland with natural or semi-natural vegetation	%
Climate mitigation	8.1	In the past 12 months, did you use any of these practices for crop production on your cropland? If yes, provide the average land area in hectares / acres: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monoculture • Agroforestry 	See indicator protocol for guidelines on classifying a net greenhouse gas emissions score (Likert from 1 to 5) for each practice	Calculate a weighted average of net emission scores, weighting by the share of farmland area under the practice	Score from 1 to 5, where 1 represents a farm with high emission and low sequestering practices, and 5 a	Continuous in range 1-5

Performance theme (indicator #)	ID	Question	Response with assigned scores	Indicator calculation method	Indicator	Indicator units
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Burning crop residues • Cover crops • Crop rotation • Fallow (leave land unproductive) • Hedgerows/Live fences • Home garden • Intercropping • Land clearing for agriculture • Mulching • Other (please specify the name of the practice) 			farm with low emission and high sequestration practices	
Climate mitigation (alternative)	8.2	For three field survey sites per farm, use tree and soil data to calculate carbon in above and below-ground biomass and in soil, converting to tonnes of carbon per hectare per year. Use IPCC and literature sources to calculate the carbon storage as a share of the maximum potential carbon storage on farmland. See indicator protocol.	%	Take the median	Tonnes of carbon in above and below ground biomass and in soils, per hectare per year, as a share of the maximum potential.	%
Water	9.1	During which months of the year do you find it difficult to access enough water for your agricultural needs (e.g., growing crops, drinking water for livestock), in a normal year?	Count of months, per year	# months with agricultural water stress per year divided by 12	Proportion of months of agricultural water stress	%

Performance theme (indicator #)	ID	Question	Response with assigned scores	Indicator calculation method	Indicator	Indicator units
Energy use	10.1	What types of energy do you use for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Irrigation (select all relevant) • Tillage, sowing or harvesting (select all relevant) • Cooking (select all relevant) • Cleaning, processing, or transporting harvested food (select all relevant) 	5- All renewable 3- Renewable and non-renewable 1- Non-renewable	Take the median	Sustainability of energy use with scores from 1 (Non-renewable and externally produced) to 5 (Renewable and self-produced)	Continuous in range 1 to 5
	10.2	Where do you source most of your energy?	5 - All energy is self-produced, exchanged with other farmers or managed collectively. 4 - 25% of energy is purchased from the market, the other 75% is self-produced or exchanged. 3 - 50% of energy is purchased from the market, the other 50% produced on farm/within the agroecosystem or exchanged			

Performance theme (indicator #)	ID	Question	Response with assigned scores	Indicator calculation method	Indicator	Indicator units
			with other members of the community. 2 - 75% of energy is purchased from the market, the other 25% is produced on farm/within the agroecosystem or exchanged with other members of the community. 1 - All energy is purchased from the market.			
Income (1)	11.1	Total household income in the last 12 months	[Value in local currency]	Calculate the ratio between the total household income and the national average household income	Total household income in the last 12 months, relative to national average	Continuous
Income (2)	11.2	How would you rate the stability of household income?	5 - Income is increasing over time 4 - Income is stable over time 3 - Income varies little from year to year	n/a	Income stability from 1 (income declining) to 5 (income increasing)	Likert 1-5

Performance theme (indicator #)	ID	Question	Response with assigned scores	Indicator calculation method	Indicator	Indicator units
			2 - Income varies from year to year 1 - Income is on a decreasing trend			
Income (3)	11.3	In the last 12 months, did the household spend more money on the farm than it earns from the farm?	1 - Yes 0 - No n/a - I don't know			
Income (4)	11.4	Does the household earn enough income from farming to support the family?	Yes, all needs are met, and savings are regular. Yes, needs for food are covered, and surplus generates cash for essentials and sporadic savings. Yes, needs for food are covered, but no surplus for savings. No, only needs for food are covered, no surplus for income. No, needs for food and other essentials are not met.			
Agricultural productivity	12.1	Harvested produce per unit area (or per animal) for at least the three main	Kg/ha or Liters/ha (per crop) or kg/animal	For each crop, calculate the yield gap using local data on	Yield gap (0% to 99%)	Continuous

Performance theme (indicator #)	ID	Question	Response with assigned scores	Indicator calculation method	Indicator	Indicator units
		crops (or livestock/fish), optionally disaggregated by management system	(per livestock/fish) or litres/animal or eggs/animal or hours/animal (per livestock)	actual attainable yields. Take the mean yield gap across the three crops.		
Labour productivity	13.1	Number of person hours worked per year (optionally disaggregated by gender, age, contract type)	[Number of hours]	Divide the total number of person hours by agricultural land area	Person hours worked per hectare of agricultural land	Continuous
	13.2	Total land area owned, rented or used by the household for agricultural purposes	[Area converted to hectares]			
Climate resilience	14.1	[See indicator protocol]	Continuous in range 1-5, for each of the four resilience pillars: 1) access to basic services, 2) assets, 3) social safety networks, and 4) adaptive capacity.	Take the median	Resilience score from 1 (low resilience) to 5 (high resilience)	Continuous in range 1 to 5
Diet quality	15.1	1. Foods made from grains 2. Whole grains 3. White roots, tubers, and plantains 4. Pulses	1 (consumed) or 0 (not consumed)	Group the following questions, and assign a group score of 1 if any of the question responses are 1, and 0	Household Food Group Diversity Score (FGDS) (0-10)	Integer 0-10

Performance theme (indicator #)	ID	Question	Response with assigned scores	Indicator calculation method	Indicator	Indicator units
		5. Vitamin A-rich orange vegetables 6. Dark green leafy vegetables 7. Other vegetables 8. Vitamin A-rich fruits 9. Citrus 10. Other fruits 11. Baked / grain-based sweets 12. Other sweets 13. Eggs 14. Cheese 15. Yogurt 16. Processed meats 17. Unprocessed red meat (ruminant) 18. Unprocessed red meat (non-ruminant) 19. Poultry 20. Fish and seafood 21. Nuts and seeds 22. Packaged ultra-processed salty snacks 23. Instant noodles 24. Deep fried foods 25. Fluid milk 26. Sweet tea / coffee / cocoa 27. Fruit juice and fruit-flavored drinks 28. Sugar-sweetened beverages (soft drinks, energy drinks, sports drinks) 29. Fast food		otherwise. Sum the values. Group1: Qs 1, 2, 3 Group2: Q4 Group3: Q21 Group4: Qs14,15,25 Group5: Qs16,17,18,19, 2 Group6: Q13 Group7: Q6 Group8: Qs5,8 Group9: Q7 Group10: Qs 9,10		
Farmer agency	16.1	On which step of the ladder would you position the majority	5-Power and freedom to make all	Take the median value	Self-evaluated decision-	Likert 1-5

Performance theme (indicator #)	ID	Question	Response with assigned scores	Indicator calculation method	Indicator	Indicator units
		of women in your household today?	major life decisions.		making agency	
	16.2	On which step of the ladder would you position the majority of men in your household today?	4-Power and freedom to make many major life decisions. 3-Power and freedom to make some major life decisions. 2-Only a small amount of power and freedom. 1-Almost no power or freedom to make decisions.		from 1 (almost no power and freedom) to 5 (complete power and freedom)	
Land tenure (1)	17.1	Do you perceive that you could involuntarily lose ownership or use rights to any of the land you currently own or hold use rights to in the next 5 years?	5 - Not at all 4- Slightly likely 3 - Moderately likely 2 - Very likely 1 - Extremely likely	n/a	Likelihood of losing land access from 1 (extremely likely) to 5 (extremely unlikely)	Continuous in range 1-5
Land tenure (2)	17.2	What is the area of agricultural land used by the household which at least one member of the household owns, defined as land for which a household member has their name on a legally recognized document OR has the right to sell OR has the right to bequeath?	[values provided in hectares or acres]	((Land area for which individuals in agricultural households have their name on a legally recognized document OR have the right to sell OR bequeath agricultural land)/(Total land area used	Proportion of land owned by household	%

Performance theme (indicator #)	ID	Question	Response with assigned scores	Indicator calculation method	Indicator	Indicator units
				by the household))*100		
Human well-being	18.1	Think about your own life and personal circumstances, how satisfied are you with your life as a whole?	5- Completely satisfied 4- Somewhat satisfied. 3 - Neutral 2- Somewhat dissatisfied 1 - Completely dissatisfied	Take the median value, excluding zero scores	Self-evaluated level of life satisfaction from 1 (completely dissatisfied) to 5 (completely satisfied)	Continuous in range 1-5
	18.2	How satisfied are you with your standard of living?	1 - Completely dissatisfied			
	18.3	How satisfied are you with your health?	0 - I don't know			
	18.4	How satisfied are you with what you are achieving in life?				
	18.5	How satisfied are you with your personal relationships?				
	18.6	How satisfied are you with how safe you feel?				
	18.7	How satisfied are you with feeling part of your community?				
	18.8	How satisfied are you with your economic security?				
	18.9	How satisfied are you with your nutritional security?				

Performance theme (indicator #)	ID	Question	Response with assigned scores	Indicator calculation method	Indicator	Indicator units
	18.10	How satisfied are you with the amount of time you have to do the things that you like doing?				
	18.11	How satisfied are you with the quality of your local environment?				
	18.12	How satisfied are you with your occupation?				

Table 3 provides a method for transforming key performance indicator values to a unified scale, from 0 to 100.

Table 3: Method for converting key performance indicators from their original formats to a standardized 0 to 100 scale

Performance theme	Indicator	Score units	Min threshold	Max threshold	Scaling method	Scaled score format
Crop health (1)	% crops damaged or lost	%	0	100	n/a	Continuous
Crop health (2)	Crop health, on a score of 1 (poor) to 5 (good)	Continuous in range 1-5	1	5	$(x-\text{min})/(\text{max}-\text{min}) * 100$	Continuous
Animal health	% of livestock/fish population with injury, illness or death	%	0	100	n/a	Continuous
Soil health (1)	Saturation of soil organic carbon	%	0	100	n/a	Continuous
Soil health (2)	Perception of soil erosion and fertility	Continuous in range 1-5	1	5	$(x-\text{min})/(\text{max}-\text{min}) * 100$	Continuous
Nutrient use	Quantity of fertilizer applied per hectare	Kg/ha	0	[TBC]	$(x-\text{min})/(\text{max}-\text{min}) * 100$	Continuous
Biodiversity (1)	Diversity of animal species from 1 (no animals) to 5 (high diversity of animals)	Continuous in range 1-5	1	5	$(x-\text{min})/(\text{max}-\text{min}) * 100$	Continuous
Biodiversity (2)	Diversity of trees from 1 (no trees) to 5 (high tree diversity)	Continuous in range 1-5	1	5	$(x-\text{min})/(\text{max}-\text{min}) * 100$	Continuous
Agrobiodiversity (1)	Diversity from 1 (low diversity) to 5 (high diversity) of crops, fish and/or livestock	Continuous in range 1-5	1	5	$(x-\text{min})/(\text{max}-\text{min}) * 100$	Continuous
Agrobiodiversity (2)	Diversity from 1 (low diversity) to 5 (high diversity) of crop varieties and/or livestock breeds	Continuous in range 1-5	1	5	$(x-\text{min})/(\text{max}-\text{min}) * 100$	Continuous
Landscape complexity	Landscape complexity from 1 (low complexity) to 5 (high complexity)	Continuous in range 1-5	1	5	$(x-\text{min})/(\text{max}-\text{min}) * 100$	Continuous
Climate mitigation	Climate mitigation score from 1 to 5, where 1 represents a farm with high	Continuous in range 1-5	1	5	$(x-\text{min})/(\text{max}-\text{min}) * 100$	Continuous

Performance theme	Indicator	Score units	Min threshold	Max threshold	Scaling method	Scaled score format
	emission and low sequestrating practices, and 5 a farm with low emission and high sequestration practices					
Water	Proportion of months of agricultural water stress	%	0	100	n/a	Continuous
Energy use	Sustainability of energy use with scores from 1 (Non-renewable and externally produced) to 5 (Renewable and self-produced)	Continuous in range 1-5	1	5	$(x-min)/(max-min)*100$	Continuous
Income (1)	Total household income in the last 12 months, relative to national average	Continuous	0	1.1 (10% above national average)	$(x-min)/(max-min)*100$	Continuous
Income (2)	Income stability from 1 (income declining) to 5 (income increasing)	Likert 1-5	1	5	$(x-min)/(max-min)*100$	Integer (0, 25, 50, 75, 100)
Agricultural productivity	Yield gap	Continuous	0	1	$(x-min)/(max-min)*100$	Continuous
Labour productivity	Number of person hours worked per year per hectare	Continuous	Dataset minimum	Dataset maximum	$(x-min)/(max-min)*100$	Continuous
Climate resilience	Resilience score from 1 (low resilience) to 5 (high resilience)	Continuous in range 1-5	1	5	$(x-min)/(max-min)*100$	Continuous
Diet quality	Household Food Group Diversity Score (FGDS) (0-10)	Integer 0-10	0	10	$(x-min)/(max-min)*100$	Integer (0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, 100)
Farmer agency	Self-evaluated decision-making agency from 1 (almost no power and freedom) to 5	Likert 1-5	1	5	$(x-min)/(max-min)*100$	Integer (0, 25, 50, 75, 100)

Performance theme	Indicator	Score units	Min threshold	Max threshold	Scaling method	Scaled score format
	(complete power and freedom)					
Land tenure (1)	Likelihood of losing land access from 1 (extremely likely) to 5 (extremely unlikely)	Continuous in range 1-5	1	5	$(x-\text{min})/(\text{max}-\text{min}) * 100$	Continuous
Land tenure (2)	Proportion of land owned by household	%	0	100	n/a	Continuous
Human well-being	Self-evaluated level of life satisfaction from 1 (completely dissatisfied) to 5 (completely satisfied)	Continuous in range 1-5	1	5	$(x-\text{min})/(\text{max}-\text{min}) * 100$	Continuous

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Appendix 1. Farm-household level HOLPA household survey

4.1.Context module

4.1.1. Consent

We are conducting farm-household surveys as part of the CGIAR's Transformational Agroecology across Food, Land and Water Systems initiative. This initiative aims to develop and scale agroecological innovations with small-scale farmers and other agricultural and food system actors in seven low- and middle-income countries. Here, agroecology is an approach to achieving sustainable agri-food systems, grounded in a set of principles that emphasize the need to work with not against nature, and to achieve social justice by co-creating knowledge, increasing farmer and multi-actor participation and agency in decision-making, while better connecting producers to consumers.

One goal of the initiative is to better understand the social, economic and environmental outcomes in farm-households that are more agroecological compared to those that are less agroecological. As part of this, we are conducting farm-household survey with approximately 200 households in each of eight countries. The countries are Burkina Faso, India, Kenya, Laos, Peru, Senegal, Tunisia, and Zimbabwe.

You are invited to participate in one such survey. The survey includes an interview with you which will take approximately 1.5 hours, followed by a walk across the farm to observe vegetation, wildlife, and, with your permission, take some photographs and collect a few soil samples. The interview will involve us asking a series of questions about your household, your farm, and your opinion on agroecology, as well as questions related to the social, economic and environmental outcomes associated with your farming activities.

We realise this interview is taking place during your working day and really appreciate you taking the time to talk to us. Please feel free to pause or reschedule the interview at any point if you need to in order to minimize inconvenience to you.

The information collected during the interviews will be summarized in a project report and academic paper. We will completely anonymize interview responses before analysis so that participants cannot be individually identified. No personal or sensitive information about participants will be published.

Your participation is entirely voluntary and you can leave at any time.

➤ **Are you happy to continue with the interview?**

Hint: If the response is "No", end the interview.

➤ Yes

- No

Before we start, I would like to audio record the interview. The recording will only be used by me and my colleagues to help with interpreting the responses, and will not be shared beyond the project team.

➤ **Is it ok with you if I now start recording?**

- Yes
- No

➤ **Are you assessing the performance of a farm or landscape?**

- Farm
- Landscape

As I mentioned, we would like to take some photos of your farm. These photos will be used to help interpret the data we collect and could be included in publications as examples of farms and households in your area.

➤ **Do you agree for us to take photos, including of you or other people on your farm?**

- Yes
- No

➤ **Do you agree for us to use these photos in publications?**

- Yes
- No

➤ **Enumerator name (first name and last name)**

4.1.2. Household location

➤ **Country**

➤ **Location (municipality, province, village)**

➤ **Farm-household ID**

*Please enter unique enumerator and farm-household identifier e.g.
enumerator1_location1_household001*

➤ **Take the GPS point of the household location.**

If the GPS point you just took was not at the location of the household, please specify where it was taken

4.1.3. Respondent characteristics

➤ **Respondent name (first name, last name)**

Hint: Enumerator, the survey should be conducted with the main family member(s) of the HH, or someone who takes major agricultural and/or HH decisions.

➤ **What is your relationship with the head of household?**

- *I am the Head (male or female) of household.*
- *I am the HH head's partner (spouse, partner).*
- *I am the HH head's child / stepchild.*
- *I am the HH head's son-in-law / daughter-in-law.*
- *I am the HH head's grandchild.*
- *I am the HH head's father / mother.*
- *I am the HH head's father-in-law / mother-in-law.*
- *I am the HH head's sibling / stepbrother / stepsister.*
- *I am the HH head's brother-in-law / mother-in-law.*
- *Other relative (please specify).*
- *Other non-relative (please specify).*

➤ **What is your relationship with the person responsible for making decision on farm activities?**

- *I am the farmer / person responsible for the farm.*
- *I am an employee on the farm.*
- *I am a family member working on the farm.*
- *Other (please specify).*

➤ **For how many years have you lived in this community?**

➤ **Year of birth**

➤ **Gender**

- *Male*
- *Female*
- *Non-binary*
- *Prefer not to say*

➤ **Marital status**

- *Married*
- *Partner (not-married)*
- *Single*
- *Divorced / Separated*
- *Widower*
- *Prefer not to say*
- *Other (please specify)*

- **Ethnicity**
- **Can you read and write in any language?**
 - *Can read and write.*
 - *Can read only.*
 - *Can write only.*
 - *Can't read or write.*
 - *Prefer not to say.*
- **What is the highest level of school you attended?**
 - *None*
 - *Primary*
 - *Secondary*
 - *Higher*
- **What is the highest [YEAR/CLASS] you completed at that level?**
- **What was your main occupation in the last 12 months?**
 - *Agricultural and/or livestock work on your own land.*
 - *Permanent salaried work on other people's land.*
 - *Seasonal wage labor on other people's land.*
 - *Public administration.*
 - *Company (landowner).*
 - *Salaried (non-agricultural work).*
 - *Study/education/training.*
 - *Homemaker.*
 - *Can't work.*
 - *Prefer not to say.*
 - *Other (please specify).*
- **What was your other occupation(s) in the last 12 months?**
 - *Agricultural and/or livestock work on your own land.*
 - *Permanent salaried work on other people's land.*
 - *Seasonal wage labor on other people's land.*
 - *Public administration.*
 - *Company (landowner).*
 - *Salaried (non-agricultural work).*
 - *Study/education/training.*
 - *Homemaker.*
 - *Can't work.*
 - *Prefer not to say.*
 - *No additional occupation*
 - *Other (please specify).*

4.1.4. Household characteristics

- **Now we would like to ask the number of members of the household:**
 - How many Male adults of working age (≥ 18 and ≤ 65 years old) live in the household? #
 - How many Female adults of working age (≥ 18 and ≤ 65 years old) live in the household? #
 - How many Male adults not of working age (> 65 years old) live in the household? #
 - How many Female adults not of working age (> 65 years old) live in the household? #
 - How many Male children (< 18 years old) live in the household? #
 - How many Female children (< 18 years old) live in the household? #
- **Please indicate the highest level of school attended by most MALE household members of working age (≥ 18 and ≤ 65 years old)**
- **Please indicate the highest level of school attended by most FEMALE household members of working age (≥ 18 and ≤ 65 years old)**
- **Are you or anyone in your household currently involved in any agricultural research or development project? If yes, please specify the name of the project.**
 - Yes
 - No

4.1.5. Farm characteristics

- **What is the total area in hectares (or acres) of land (agricultural or not) that your household:**

Hint: Select preferred area unit.

 - **Currently OWNS:**

Hint: Please include the land for which your household has legal ownership documented in a recognized document OR has the right to sell, irrespective of whether the land is currently used by you or another household member.
 - **Currently LEASES from another person:**
 - **Currently HOLDS USE RIGHTS, either alone or jointly with someone else:**

Hint: e.g., land borrowed for free, shared or communal grazing land, shared cropland.
- **From the total hectares/acres of land that your household OWNS, please specify how much is owned by:**

- **A MALE member/members:** *Hectares / Acres*
- **A FEMALE member/members:** *Hectares / Acres*
- **From the total hectares/acres of land that your household LEASES from another person, please specify how much is rented by:**
 - **A MALE member/members:** *Hectares / Acres*
 - **A FEMALE member/members:** *Hectares / Acres*
- **From the total hectares/acres of land that your household HOLDS USE RIGHTS, either alone or jointly with someone else, please specify how much is held by:**
 - **A MALE member/members:** *Hectares / Acres*
 - **A FEMALE member/members:** *Hectares / Acres*
- **How would you describe the slope of your farmland?**
 - *Steep*
 - *Moderately steep*
 - *Slightly steep*
 - *Flat*
- **In the last 12 months, what did you produce on your farm?**
Hint: please select all relevant.
 - *Crops (including perennial crops)*
 - *Livestock*
 - *Fish*
 - *Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber)*
 - *Honey*
 - *Other (please specify)*
- **What does the produced CROPS (including perennial crops) get used for?**
Hint: Select the share of harvested produce by used.

<input type="radio"/> Household consumption	<i>None</i>	<i>1-25%</i>	<i>26-50%</i>	<i>51-75%</i>	<i>76-100%</i>
<input type="radio"/> Own livestock consumption	<i>None</i>	<i>1-25%</i>	<i>26-50%</i>	<i>51-75%</i>	<i>76-100%</i>
<input type="radio"/> Sales	<i>None</i>	<i>1-25%</i>	<i>26-50%</i>	<i>51-75%</i>	<i>76-100%</i>
<input type="radio"/> Gifts	<i>None</i>	<i>1-25%</i>	<i>26-50%</i>	<i>51-75%</i>	<i>76-100%</i>

- | | | | | | |
|---|-------------|--------------|---------------|---------------|----------------|
| ○ Wasted/lost | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ○ Other use (please specify) | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ➤ What does the produced LIVESTOCK get used for? | | | | | |
| ○ Household consumption | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ○ On-farm use | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ○ Sales | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ○ Gifts | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ○ Wasted/lost | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ○ Other use (please specify) | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ➤ What does the produced FISH get used for? | | | | | |
| ○ Household consumption | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ○ Own livestock consumption | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ○ Sales | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ○ Gifts | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ○ Wasted/lost | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ○ Other use (please specify) | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ➤ What does the produced wood, bark, rubber, etc. (from TREES) get used for? | | | | | |
| ○ Household use for cooking | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ○ Household use for building | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ○ Household use for heating | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ○ Household other use | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ○ Sales | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ○ Gifts | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |
| ○ Wasted/lost | <i>None</i> | <i>1-25%</i> | <i>26-50%</i> | <i>51-75%</i> | <i>76-100%</i> |

- **Other use (please specify)** *None* 1-25% 26-50% 51-75% 76-100%

➤ **What does the produced HONEY get used for?**

- **Household consumption** *None* 1-25% 26-50% 51-75% 76-100%
- **Sales** *None* 1-25% 26-50% 51-75% 76-100%
- **Gifts** *None* 1-25% 26-50% 51-75% 76-100%
- **Wasted/lost** *None* 1-25% 26-50% 51-75% 76-100%
- **Other use (please specify)** *None* 1-25% 26-50% 51-75% 76-100%

➤ **What do the produced OTHER products get used for?**

- **Household consumption** *None* 1-25% 26-50% 51-75% 76-100%
- **Own livestock consumption** *None* 1-25% 26-50% 51-75% 76-100%
- **On-farm use** *None* 1-25% 26-50% 51-75% 76-100%
- **Sales** *None* 1-25% 26-50% 51-75% 76-100%
- **Gifts** *None* 1-25% 26-50% 51-75% 76-100%
- **Wasted/lost** *None* 1-25% 26-50% 51-75% 76-100%
- **Other use (please specify)** *None* 1-25% 26-50% 51-75% 76-100%

➤ **Over the past 12 months, how much CHEMICAL FUNGICIDES/PESTICIDES/HERBICIDES was applied to cropland?**

○ Name of the main product used:
○ Amount applied: <i>Hint: please specify the applied unit</i>
○ Specify the surface area affected in hectares/acres:

➤ **Over the past 12 months, how much NON-CHEMICAL FUNGICIDES/PESTICIDES/HERBICIDES was applied to cropland?**

○ Name of the main product used:

- **Amount applied:**

Hint: please specify the applied unit

- **Specify the surface area affected in hectares/acres:**

➤ **Over the past 12 months, how did you manage livestock diseases?**

- *Vaccination.*
- *Antibiotics.*
- *Organic treatments.*
- *Quarantine measures.*
- *Genetic selection for disease resistance.*
- *Herbal remedies or traditional medicine.*
- *No action taken.*
- *Other (please specify).*

➤ **Over the past 12 months, how did you manage fish diseases?**

- *Vaccination.*
- *Antibiotics.*
- *Organic treatments.*
- *Quarantine measures.*
- *Genetic selection for disease resistance.*
- *Herbal remedies or traditional medicine.*
- *No action taken.*
- *Other (please specify).*

4.1.6. Climate change

➤ **Do you perceive that the temperature has changed over the last 30 years?**

- *Increased*
- *No change*
- *Decreased*
- *I am not sure*

➤ **Do you perceive that the amount of rainfall has changed over the last 30 years?**

- *Increased*
- *No change*
- *Decreased*
- *I am not sure*

➤ **Do you perceive that the timing of rainfall has changed over the last 30 years?**

- *Rainfall starts later*
- *Rainfall starts earlier*
- *Rainfall stops earlier*

- *Rainfall stops later*
- *Rainfall start and/or stop are no longer predictable*
- *No change*
- *I am not sure*

➤ **In the last 12 months, have you experienced any flood conditions on your farmland?**

- *Yes*
- *No*

➤ **In the last 12 months, have you experienced any drought conditions on your farmland?**

- *Yes*
- *No*

4.1.7. Motivation to transition

➤ **Do you know what Agroecology means?**

- *Yes, I have a clear understanding of Agroecology.*
- *I have some knowledge about Agroecology, but I would like to learn more.*
- *No, I am not familiar with the term Agroecology.*

Enumerator, please take the time to explain what Agroecology means.

Agroecology is an approach to achieving sustainable agri-food systems, grounded in a set of principles that emphasize the need to work with not against nature, and to achieve social justice by co-creating knowledge, increasing farmer and multi-actor participation and agency in decision-making, while better connecting producers to consumers.

➤ **Now we would like to ask a few questions about your perspective on agroecology. Please indicate how far you agree with the following statements.**

○ **I care a lot about nature.**

- *5 - Completely agree.*
- *4 - Somewhat agree.*
- *3 - Neutral.*
- *2- Somewhat disagree.*
- *1 - Completely disagree.*
- *0 - I don't know.*

○ **Being in nature benefits me.**

- *5 - Completely agree.*
- *4 - Somewhat agree.*
- *3 - Neutral.*
- *2- Somewhat disagree.*
- *1 - Completely disagree.*
- *0 - I don't know.*

- **I live in a place where most people take good care of the land and nature.**
 - 5 - *Completely agree.*
 - 4 - *Somewhat agree.*
 - 3 - *Neutral.*
 - 2- *Somewhat disagree.*
 - 1 - *Completely disagree.*
 - 0 - *I don't know.*

- **I take care of the land and nature on my farm.**
 - 5 - *Completely agree.*
 - 4 - *Somewhat agree.*
 - 3 - *Neutral.*
 - 2- *Somewhat disagree.*
 - 1 - *Completely disagree.*
 - 0 - *I don't know.*

- **I identify myself as an agroecological farmer.**
 - 5 - *Completely agree.*
 - 4 - *Somewhat agree.*
 - 3 - *Neutral.*
 - 2- *Somewhat disagree.*
 - 1 - *Completely disagree.*
 - 0 - *I don't know.*

- **I have power and freedom to change farm production practices if I want to.**
 - 5 - *Completely agree.*
 - 4 - *Somewhat agree.*
 - 3 - *Neutral.*
 - 2- *Somewhat disagree.*
 - 1 - *Completely disagree.*
 - 0 - *I don't know.*

- **If I work together with others in my community, we have power and freedom to solve problems facing farmers.**
 - 5 - *Completely agree.*
 - 4 - *Somewhat agree.*
 - 3 - *Neutral.*
 - 2- *Somewhat disagree.*
 - 1 - *Completely disagree.*
 - 0 - *I don't know.*

- **I make decisions about what food to buy based primarily on price.**
 - 5 - *Completely agree.*
 - 4 - *Somewhat agree.*
 - 3 - *Neutral.*

- 2- Somewhat disagree.
- 1 - Completely disagree.
- 0 - I don't know.

○ **I would prefer to eat food that is produced without chemical inputs.**

- 5 - Completely agree.
- 4 - Somewhat agree.
- 3 - Neutral.
- 2- Somewhat disagree.
- 1 - Completely disagree.
- 0 - I don't know.

○ **I would prefer to eat food that is grown locally.**

Hint: Food grown locally at the ALL-level.

- 5 - Completely agree.
- 4 - Somewhat agree.
- 3 - Neutral.
- 2- Somewhat disagree.
- 1 - Completely disagree.
- 0 - I don't know.

○ **I would prefer that the food I buy is produced and processed in ways that provide a fair wage and good conditions for workers.**

- 5 - Completely agree.
- 4 - Somewhat agree.
- 3 - Neutral.
- 2- Somewhat disagree.
- 1 - Completely disagree.
- 0 - I don't know.

○ **I think shifting to agroecological farming is a sensible business decision.**

- 5 - Completely agree.
- 4 - Somewhat agree.
- 3 - Neutral.
- 2- Somewhat disagree.
- 1 - Completely disagree.
- 0 - I don't know.

○ **Most farmers think current farming systems are working well and do not need changing.**

- 5 - Completely agree.
- 4 - Somewhat agree.
- 3 - Neutral.
- 2- Somewhat disagree.
- 1 - Completely disagree.

➤ 0 - I don't know.

DRAFT

4.2. Agroecology module

4.2.1. Recycling

4.2.1.1. Seeds

➤ **Where do you source most of your seeds?**

- 5 - All seeds are self-produced, exchanged with other farmers or managed collectively.
- 4 - 25% of seeds are purchased from the market, the other 75% is self-produced or exchanged.
- 3 - 50% of seeds are purchased from the market, the other 50% is self-produced or exchanged.
- 2 - 75% of seeds are purchased from the market, the other 25% are self-produced or exchanged.
- 1 - All seeds are purchased from the market (e.g., agrovet, seed stores, farmers' cooperatives, seed suppliers, etc.).

4.2.1.2. Nutrients

➤ **Where do you source most of your manure and compost?**

Hint: Choose the option that best represents.

- 5 - All manure and compost are self-produced, exchanged with other farmers or managed collectively.
- 4 - 25% of the manure and compost are purchased from the market, the other 75% is self-produced or exchanged.
- 3 - 50% of the manure and compost purchased from the market, the other 50% is self-produced or exchanged.
- 2 - 75% of the manure and compost are purchased from the market, the other 25% are self-produced or exchanged.
- 1 - All manure and compost are purchased from the market.

4.2.1.3. Breeds

➤ **Where do you source most of your livestock?**

- 5 - All animal genetic resources are self-produced, exchanged with other farmers or managed collectively.
- 4 - 25% of animal genetic resources are purchased from the market, the other 75% is self-produced or exchanged.

- 3 - 50% of the breeding are purchased from the market, the other 50% is self-produced or exchanged with neighboring farms.
- 2 - 75% of animal genetic resources are purchased from the market, the other 25% are self-produced or exchanged.
- 1 - All animal genetic resources (e.g., chicks, young animals, semen) are purchased from the market.

4.2.1.4. Fish

➤ Where do you source most of your spawn, fry or fingerling species and varieties?

- 5 - All fish genetic resources are self-produced, exchanged with other farmers or managed collectively.
- 4 - 25% of fish genetic resources are purchased from the market, the other 75% is self-produced or exchanged.
- 3 - 50% of fish genetic resources are purchased from the market, the other 50% is self-produced or exchanged with neighboring farms.
- 2 - 75% of fish genetic resources are purchased from the market, the other 25% are self-produced or exchanged.
- 1 - All fish genetic resources (e.g., spawn, fry, fingerling species and varieties) are purchased from the market.

➤ Where do you source your fish feed?

- Natural feed from the aquatic environment.
- Obtained from other farmers for free.
- Purchased from other farmers.
- Self-produced on the farm.
- Commercial feed suppliers.
- Other (Please specify).

4.2.2. Input reduction

➤ Over the past 12 months, what did you do to improve soil fertility of cropland?

- Used of Ecological practices (e.g., cover crops, plant legumes, mulching, etc.).
- Application of Organic fertilisers or Manure.
- Application of Chemical fertilisers.
- No ecological practices, chemical or organic fertilizer were applied.

➤ Over the past 12 months, what did you do to manage pests in cropland?

- *Ecological practices (e.g., crop rotation, planting repelling plants).*
- *Non-chemical fungicides/pesticides/herbicides.*
- *Chemical fungicides/pesticides/herbicides.*
- *No ecological practices, chemical or non-chemical pesticides were applied.*

➤ **Are livestock fed with dry feed (e.g., grains, hay)?**

- *All the time*
- *Often*
- *Sometimes*
- *Rarely*
- *Never*

➤ **What types of fish feed did you primarily use in the last 12 months?**

- *Natural feed (i.e., feeds that occur naturally or introduced in the aquatic environment).*
- *Prepared organic feeds (i.e., feeds that are produced using natural ingredients).*
- *Prepared chemical feeds (i.e., feeds that contain specific chemical compounds or additives).*
- *Other (please specify).*

4.2.3. Soil health

➤ **Which practices do you use on cropland to improve soil quality and health?**

- *Add inoculants (fungi, bacteria).*
- *Biochar.*
- *Leave crop residues on ground after harvesting.*
- *Fertilizer micro dosing.*
- *Mulching.*
- *No tillage.*
- *Plant cover crops.*
- *Plant legumes.*
- *Planting basins.*
- *Reduced tillage.*

- *Other (please specify).*

4.2.4. Animal health

➤ **Are the animals on your farm healthy and happy?**

- *5 - Animals do not suffer from stress, hunger, thirst, pain, or diseases, and are slaughtered in a way to avoid unnecessary pain.*
- *4 - Animals do not suffer from hunger, thirst or diseases but can experience stress, especially at slaughter.*
- *3 - Animals do not suffer from hunger or thirst, but suffer from stress, may be prone to diseases and can suffer from pain at slaughter.*
- *2 - Animals suffer periodically/seasonally from hunger and thirst, stress or diseases, and are slaughtered without avoiding unnecessary pain.*
- *1 - Animals suffer from hunger and thirst, stress and diseases all year long, and are slaughtered without avoiding unnecessary pain.*

➤ **What do you do on the farm to keep animals healthy and happy?**

- *Provide consistent access to adequate food.*
- *Provide diversified diets.*
- *Provide consistent access to clean drinking water.*
- *Provide shelter.*
- *Conduct regular checks for injuries/diseases.*
- *Provide hygienic surroundings.*
- *Provide medical assistance when needed.*
- *No action taken.*
- *Other (please describe).*

4.2.5. Biodiversity

➤ **In the last 12 months, how many different crops species (including perennial crops) were produced on your farm?**

➤ **In the last 12 months, which different livestock species did you keep?**

- *Cattle*

- Sheep
- Goats
- Horses
- Donkeys
- Mules
- Camels
- Chickens
- Ducks
- Beehives
- Other (please specify)

➤ **Over the past 12 months, how many different fish species did you produce?**

➤ **How would you describe the diversity of trees (or perennial woody crops) on your farm?**

Hint: Include trees and woody plants found in any productive fields used for crops or livestock on the farm, including tree and shrub crops or trees, shrubs and lianas grown in the field or at field edges. Exclude trees in forest patches on or adjacent to the farm.

- *High: five or more species with different heights, woodiness, or flowering seasons.*
- *Medium: two to four species.*
- *Low: only one species.*
- *No trees or other woody perennials.*

➤ **How would you describe the plant diversity (i.e., number of plant species) in natural and semi-natural vegetation [on land owned, rented or used by the household]?** Include any natural or semi-natural vegetation (bushland, fallow land, hedgerows, natural grassland, ponds, lakes, forest patches etc.)

Hint: Choose the option that best represent for the following features

○ **Bushland patches**

- *High: five or more species with different heights, woodiness, or flowering seasons.*
- *Medium: two to four species.*
- *Low: only one species.*

➤ *None*

○ **Fallow land which is unproductive for at least 1 year**

- *High: five or more species with different heights, woodiness, or flowering seasons.*
- *Medium: two to four species.*
- *Low: only one species.*
- *None*

○ **Hedgerows/Live fences**

- *High: five or more species with different heights, woodiness, or flowering seasons.*
- *Medium: two to four species.*
- *Low: only one species.*
- *None*

○ **Natural grassland**

- *High: five or more species with different heights, woodiness, or flowering seasons.*
- *Medium: two to four species.*
- *Low: only one species.*
- *None*

○ **Remnant forest patches**

- *High: five or more species with different heights, woodiness, or flowering seasons.*
- *Medium: two to four species.*
- *Low: only one species.*
- *None*

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Wetlands <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>High: five or more species with different heights, woodiness, or flowering seasons.</i> ➤ <i>Medium: two to four species.</i> ➤ <i>Low: only one species.</i> ➤ <i>None</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Woodlots <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>High: five or more species with different heights, woodiness, or flowering seasons.</i> ➤ <i>Medium: two to four species.</i> ➤ <i>Low: only one species.</i> ➤ <i>None</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Other landscape feature (please specify) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>High: five or more species with different heights, woodiness, or flowering seasons.</i> ➤ <i>Medium: two to four species.</i> ➤ <i>Low: only one species.</i> ➤ <i>None</i>

4.2.6. Synergies

- **What practices did you apply in the last 12 months on the farm to manage crop pests?**
 - *Cultural control (plants and fruits presenting signs of disease are removed manually).*
 - *Plantation of natural repelling plants.*
 - *Use of cover crops/intercropping/crop rotation to increase biological interactions.*
 - *Favor the reproduction of beneficial organisms for biological-control.*
 - *Favor biodiversity and spatial diversity within the agroecosystem.*
 - *Plant improved or resistant crop varieties.*

➤ *Other (please specify).*

➤ **On the grazing land (owned, leased, or shared), did you apply in the last 12 months any of the following practices?**

Hint: Select all the practices that apply

- *Fodder shrubs.*
- *Pasture rehabilitation.*
- *No manure management.*
- *Exclosures.*
- *Pasture fertilization.*
- *Biogas production.*
- *Silvo pastoralism.*
- *Overgrazing.*
- *Producing feed legumes.*
- *Reducing grazing pressure.*
- *Keeping improve breeds.*
- *Manure collection.*
- *Improve manure storage.*
- *Composting.*
- *Inclosures.*
- *None.*
- *Other (please specify).*

➤ **On the fish production land, did you apply in the last 12 months any of the following practices?**

- *Agro-aquaculture: Combining fish farming with crop cultivation.*
- *Aquaponics: Integrating fish farming with hydroponic plant cultivation).*
- *Eco-friendly pond designs.*
- *Efficient water management.*
- *Improved feed formulation.*
- *Integrated fish-poultry farming: Fish and poultry coexist in the same system.*
- *Livestock-fish farming.*
- *Selective breeding for climate resilience.*
- *None.*

➤ *Other (please specify).*

➤ **In addition to actions you mentioned previously, is there anything else you do on your farm to make sure there are positive relationships between animals, crops, trees, soil and water?**

- *Planting natural vegetation between fields like live fences, hedgerows, flower strips.*
- *Crop irrigation from harvested rainwater.*
- *Sowing along contour lines.*
- *Animals and crops in the same field (at same time, or in rotation).*
- *Planting or conserving trees on agricultural land (cropland or pasture).*
- *Avoid or limit grass fires (do not burn every year).*
- *None*
- *Other (please specify)*

4.2.7. Economic diversification

➤ **Please select all the sources of income for your household:**

- *Crop production.*
- *Livestock production.*
- *Fish production.*
- *Other family business.*
- *Casual labour.*
- *Formal labour office job.*
- *Cash transfers.*
- *Leasing agricultural or non-agricultural land.*
- *Subsidy (please specify which subsidy).*
- *Other (please specify).*

4.2.8. Co-creation of knowledge

- **In the last 12 months, how many times has your household exchanged information with the following food system stakeholders to create new or improved solutions to your or others' farming problems?**

Hint: Please, provide the approximate number of visits/contacts in the last 12 months.

- **Agricultural extension workers**

Hint: Include any advisory services that the household has contact with (private, public, or other)

- **Consumers**
- **Food traders**
- **Government**
- **NGOs**
- **Other farmers**
- **Researchers**

4.2.9. Governance

- **How often does your household participate in activities and meetings related to the management of your community's land and natural resources?**

- *5 - Always participates.*
- *4 - Most of the time participates.*
- *3 - Sometimes participates.*
- *2 - Rarely participates.*
- *1 - Never participates.*

- **How often does your household influence the decision-making that goes into the management of your community's land and natural resources?**

- *5 - Contribute to all the decisions.*

- 4 - *Contribute to almost all the decisions.*
- 3 - *Contribute to some decisions.*
- 2 - *Contribute to few decisions.*
- 1 - *Did not contribute to any decision.*

➤ **In your opinion, are your community's land and natural resources well-managed?**

- 5 - *Extremely well-managed.*
- 4 - *Well-managed.*
- 3 - *Moderately managed.*
- 2 - *Poorly managed.*
- 1 - *Not at all well-managed.*

4.2.10. Social values and diets

➤ **Do you and your family have access to enough healthy, diversified, seasonal and traditional foods?**

○ **Healthy food:**

- 5 - *Good access.*
- 4 - *Fairly good.*
- 3 - *Moderate access.*
- 2 - *Limited access.*
- 1 - *No access at all.*

○ **Diversified food:**

- 5 - *Good access.*
- 4 - *Fairly good.*
- 3 - *Moderate access.*
- 2 - *Limited access.*
- 1 - *No access at all.*

○ **Seasonal food:**

- 5 - *Good access.*

- 4 - Fairly good.
- 3 - Moderate access.
- 2 - Limited access.
- 1 - No access at all.

○ **Traditional food:**

- 5 - Good access.
- 4 - Fairly good.
- 3 - Moderate access.
- 2 - Limited access.
- 1 - No access at all.

4.2.11. Fairness

➤ **Does your household earn enough income from farming to support the family?**

Hint: Please, consider all types of assets, including crops, animals, perennial trees etc.

- 5 - Yes, all needs are met, and savings are regular.
- 4 - Yes, needs for food are covered, and surplus generates cash for essentials and sporadic savings.
- 3 - Yes, needs for food are covered, but no surplus for savings.
- 2 - No, only needs for food are covered, no surplus for income.
- 1 - No, the need for food and other essentials are not met.

➤ **Do you get a fair price for your produced CROPS?**

Hint: Choose the option that best represents the farm-household. Here, a fair price usually refers to whether the cost is sufficient to recover the investment made to produce the product.

- 5 - Always get a fair price.
- 4 - Usually get a fair price, depending on the product.
- 3 - Occasionally get a fair price, depending on the product.
- 2 - Rarely get a fair price.
- 1 - Never get a fair price.

➤ **Do you get a fair price for your produced LIVESTOCK?**

Hint: Choose the option that best represents the farm-household. Here, a fair price usually refers to whether the cost is sufficient to recover the investment made to produce the product.

- 5 - Always get a fair price.
- 4 - Usually get a fair price, depending on the product.
- 3 - Occasionally get a fair price, depending on the product.
- 2 - Rarely get a fair price.
- 1 - Never get a fair price.

➤ **Do you get a fair price for your produced FISH?**

Hint: Choose the option that best represents the farm-household. Here, a fair price usually refers to whether the cost is sufficient to recover the investment made to produce the product.

- 5 - Always get a fair price.
- 4 - Usually get a fair price, depending on the product.
- 3 - Occasionally get a fair price, depending on the product.
- 2 - Rarely get a fair price.
- 1 - Never get a fair price.

➤ **Do you get a fair price for your produced wood, bark, rubber, etc. (from TREES)?**

Hint: Choose the option that best represents the farm-household. Here, a fair price usually refers to whether the cost is sufficient to recover the investment made to produce the product.

- 5 - Always get a fair price.
- 4 - Usually get a fair price, depending on the product.
- 3 - Occasionally get a fair price, depending on the product.
- 2 - Rarely get a fair price.
- 1 - Never get a fair price.

➤ **Do you get a fair price for your produced HONEY?**

Hint: Choose the option that best represents the farm-household. Here, a fair price usually refers to whether the cost is sufficient to recover the investment made to produce the product.

- 5 - Always get a fair price.

- 4 - Usually get a fair price, depending on the product.
- 3 - Occasionally get a fair price, depending on the product.
- 2 - Rarely get a fair price.
- 1 - Never get a fair price.

➤ **Do you get a fair price for your produced OTHER products?**

Hint: Choose the option that best represents the farm-household. Here, a fair price usually refers to whether the cost is sufficient to recover the investment made to produce the product.

- 5 - Always get a fair price.
- 4 - Usually get a fair price, depending on the product.
- 3 - Occasionally get a fair price, depending on the product.
- 2 - Rarely get a fair price.
- 1 - Never get a fair price.

4.2.12. Connectivity

➤ **When you sell the produced CROPS, who do you sell to?**

- *Directly to consumers.*
- *To farmers organization / cooperative.*
- *To retailers such as supermarkets, grocery stores, or restaurants.*
- *To a middle man / aggregator.*
- *Other (please, specify).*

➤ **When you sell the produced LIVESTOCK, who do you sell to?**

- *Directly to consumers.*
- *To farmers organization / cooperative.*
- *To retailers such as supermarkets, grocery stores, or restaurants.*
- *To a middle man / aggregator.*
- *Other (please, specify).*

➤ **When you sell the produced FISH, who do you sell to?**

- *Directly to consumers.*
- *To farmers organization / cooperative.*
- *To retailers such as supermarkets, grocery stores, or restaurants.*
- *To a middle man / aggregator.*
- *Other (please, specify).*

➤ **When you sell the produced wood, bark, rubber, etc. (from TREES), who do you sell to?**

- *Directly to consumers.*
- *To farmers organization / cooperative.*
- *To retailers such as supermarkets, grocery stores, or restaurants.*
- *To a middle man / aggregator.*
- *Other (please, specify).*

➤ **When you sell the produced HONEY, who do you sell to?**

- *Directly to consumers.*
- *To farmers organization / cooperative.*
- *To retailers such as supermarkets, grocery stores, or restaurants.*
- *To a middle man / aggregator.*
- *Other (please, specify).*

➤ **When you sell OTHER products, who do you sell to?**

- *Directly to consumers.*
- *To farmers organization / cooperative.*
- *To retailers such as supermarkets, grocery stores, or restaurants.*
- *To a middle man / aggregator.*
- *Other (please, specify).*

4.2.13. Participation

➤ **Select all the associations/organizations of which you or other HH members are a part of:**

- *Agriculture/trade organization*

- *Cooperative.*
- *Environmental group.*
- *Farmer producer organization.*
- *Farmers' association.*
- *NGO.*
- *Women association.*
- *Youth association.*
- *Political organization.*
- *Village board.*
- *Cultural/health/school group.*
- *Other (please specify)*
- *Not a member of any organization.*
- *I don't know.*

➤ **In your opinion, how effective are farmer associations/organizations at supporting farmers in business?**

- *5 - Associations/organizations demonstrate exceptional effectiveness in supporting farmers' business ventures, offering comprehensive assistance, fostering growth, and ensuring long-term success.*
- *4 - Associations/organizations play a significant role in supporting farmers' businesses, providing valuable resources, market opportunities, and essential services.*
- *3 - Associations/organizations offer satisfactory support to farmers, aiding them in various aspects of their businesses (e.g., market access, information sharing, and capacity development).*
- *2 - Associations/organizations provide limited support to farmers in business, with marginal impact on their overall success.*
- *1 - Associations/organizations offer no support to farmers' businesses.*
- *0 - I don't know.*

○ **Would you like to explain why?**

4.3. Performance module

4.3.1. Agricultural

4.3.1.1. Crop health

- **What percentage of the total crop production was lost or damaged in the last 12 months.**
- **What was the main cause of crop loss or damage?**

4.3.1.2. Animal health

- **What was the extent of injury, illness, or death of livestock due to diseases in the last 12 months?**
 - *None*
 - *Low*
 - *Medium*
 - *High*
- **What was the extent of injury, illness or death of fish due to diseases in the last 12 months?**
 - *None*
 - *Low*
 - *Medium*
 - *High*

4.3.1.3. Soil health

- **How would you describe the level of soil erosion problem on your farmland?**
 - *Soil erosion is a major problem on my farm.*
 - *Soil erosion is a minor problem on my farm.*

➤ *Soil erosion is not a problem on my farm.*

➤ **How would you describe the fertility of your soil on your farmland?**

- *Highly fertile*
- *Moderately fertile*
- *Low fertility*
- *Infertile*

4.3.1.4. Nutrient use

➤ **Over the past 12 months, how much CHEMICAL FERTILIZER was applied to cropland.**

Amount applied:

Hint: please specify the applied unit

Specify the surface area affected in hectares/acres:

➤ **Over the past 12 months, how much ORGANIC FERTILIZER OR MANURE GENERATED ON-FARM was applied to cropland.**

Amount applied:

Hint: please specify the applied unit

Specify the surface area affected in hectares/acres:

➤ **Over the past 12 months, how much ORGANIC FERTILIZER OR MANURE FROM OTHER SOURCES (from the market or exchange) was applied to cropland.**

Amount applied:

Please specify the applied unit

- **Specify the surface area affected in hectares/acres:**

4.3.2. Environmental

4.3.2.1. Biodiversity

➤ **How would you describe the diversity of insect pollinators on your farm?**

*Hint: Describe the diversity found in the majority of productive fields used for crops or livestock** on the farm.*

- *High diversity: Abundant presence with a wide variety of species.*
- *Medium diversity: Regularly seen with several species.*
- *Low diversity: Rarely seen or limited to a few species.*
- *None: No insects observed.*

➤ **How would you describe the diversity of crop and livestock pests on your farm?**

*Hint: Describe the diversity found in the majority of productive fields used for crops or livestock** on the farm.*

- *High diversity: Abundant presence with a wide variety of species.*
- *Medium diversity: Regularly seen with several species.*
- *Low diversity: Rarely seen or limited to a few species.*
- *None: No insects observed.*

➤ **How would you describe the diversity of natural crop and livestock pest enemies on your farm?**

*Hint: Describe the diversity found in the majority of productive fields used for crops or livestock** on the farm.*

- *High diversity: Abundant presence with a wide variety of species.*
- *Medium diversity: Regularly seen with several species.*
- *Low diversity: Rarely seen or limited to a few species.*
- *None: No insects observed.*

➤ **How would you describe the diversity of mammals on your farm?**

*Hint: Describe the diversity found in the majority of productive fields used for crops or livestock** on the farm.*

- *High diversity: Abundant presence with a wide variety of species.*
- *Medium diversity: Regularly seen with several species.*
- *Low diversity: Rarely seen or limited to a few species.*
- *None: No mammals observed.*

➤ **How would you describe the amount of trees (or perennial woody crops) on your farm?**

Hint: Include trees and woody plants found in any productive fields used for crops or livestock on the farm, including tree and shrub crops or trees, shrubs and lianas grown in the field or at field edges. Exclude trees in forest patches on or adjacent to the farm.

- *More than 50 trees (and/or other woody perennials) per hectare / acre.*
- *21-50 trees (and/or other woody perennials) per hectare / acre.*
- *1-20 trees (and/or other woody perennials) per hectare / acre.*
- *No trees or other woody perennials.*

➤ **How would you describe the diversity of trees (or perennial woody crops) on your farm?**

Hint: Include trees and woody plants found in any productive fields used for crops or livestock on the farm, including tree and shrub crops or trees, shrubs and lianas grown in the field or at field edges. Exclude trees in forest patches on or adjacent to the farm.

- *High: five or more species with different heights, woodiness, or flowering seasons.*
- *Medium: two to four species.*
- *Low: only one species.*
- *No trees or other woody perennials.*

4.3.2.2. Agrobiodiversity

➤ **In the last 12 months, how many different crops species (including perennial crops) were produced on your farm?**

➤ **In the last 12 months, which different livestock species did you keep?**

- *Cattle*
- *Sheep*
- *Goats*

- *Horses*
- *Donkeys*
- *Mules*
- *Camels*
- *Chickens*
- *Ducks*
- *Beehives*
- *Other (please specify)*

- **Over the past 12 months, how many different fish species did you produce?**

4.3.2.3. Landscape complexity

- **How much land area is covered by natural and semi-natural vegetation on land owned, rented or used by the household?**
 - o Any natural or semi-natural vegetation (bushland, fallow land, hedgerows, natural grassland, ponds, lakes, forest patches etc.)
 - *51-100%*
 - *21-50%*
 - *11-20%*
 - *1-10%*
 - *No presence or occurrence.*
 - o Bushland patches
 - *51-100%*
 - *21-50%*
 - *11-20%*
 - *1-10%*
 - *No presence or occurrence.*
 - o Fallow land which is unproductive for at least 1 year
 - *51-100%*
 - *21-50%*

- 11-20%
- 1-10%
- No presence or occurrence.

o Hedgerows/Live fences

- 51-100%
- 21-50%
- 11-20%
- 1-10%
- No presence or occurrence.

o Natural grassland (*i.e., Natural grasslands are characterized by herbaceous vegetation that predominantly consists of gramineous species and reaches a maximum height of 150 cm. These areas cover at least 50% of the surface and may also include shrub formations, scattered trees, and mineral outcrops. They are frequently designated for nature conservation purposes.*)

- 51-100%
- 21-50%
- 11-20%
- 1-10%
- No presence or occurrence.

o Ponds or lakes

- 51-100%
- 21-50%
- 11-20%
- 1-10%
- No presence or occurrence.

o Remnant forest patches

- 51-100%
- 21-50%

- 11-20%
- 1-10%
- No presence or occurrence.

o Wetlands

- 51-100%
- 21-50%
- 11-20%
- 1-10%
- No presence or occurrence.

o Woodlots (i.e., A restricted area of woodland usually privately maintained as a source of fuel, posts, and lumber.)

- 51-100%
- 21-50%
- 11-20%
- 1-10%
- No presence or occurrence.

o Other landscape feature (please specify)

- 51-100%
- 21-50%
- 11-20%
- 1-10%
- No presence or occurrence.

4.3.2.4. Climate mitigation

➤ **Since when has your household been farming this land?**

Hint: If it was since before the respondent's lifetime but they do not know the exact year, put 5555. If the respondent doesn't know, put 9999.

➤ **What was the main previous land cover?**

Hint: Enumerator: if the respondent doesn't know, please mark "9999"

➤ **In the past 12 months, did you use any of these practices for crop production on your cropland?**

Hint: Please specify the following information for all the practices applied

o Practices	o Average land area
- Monoculture	<i>Hectares / acres</i>
- Agroforestry	<i>Hectares / acres</i>
- Burning crop residues:	<i>Hectares / acres</i>
- Cover crops:	<i>Hectares / acres</i>
- Crop rotation:	<i>Hectares / acres</i>
- Fallow (leave land unproductive):	<i>Hectares / acres</i>
- Hedgerows/Live fences:	<i>Hectares / acres</i>
- Home garden:	<i>Hectares / acres</i>
- Intercropping:	<i>Hectares / acres</i>
- Land clearing for agriculture:	<i>Hectares / acres</i>
- Mulching:	<i>Hectares / acres</i>
- Natural strips/vegetation:	<i>Hectares / acres</i>
- Pollinator/Flower strips:	<i>Hectares / acres</i>

- Pull-push:	<i>Hectares / acres</i>
- Other (please specify the name of the practice):	<i>Hectares / acres</i>

4.3.2.5. Water

➤ **Do you irrigate your cropland?**

- Yes
- No

If the answer to the previous question is “Yes”, please answer the following questions:

➤ **What methods of irrigation do you use?**

Hint: Select all methods of irrigation used.

- Drip.
- Flood.
- Hose-pipe.
- Ridges.
- Sprinkler.
- Watering can or bucket.
- Other (please specify).

➤ **Where do you source your water for irrigation?**

Hint: Select all water sources of irrigation used.

- Dam/lake.
- Groundwater.
- Piped regional water.
- Rainwater harvesting.
- Rivers.
- Wetland.

➤ *Other (please specify).*

➤ **What percentage of your cropland do you irrigate during each season?**

○ **SEASON # 1**

- **Select the months corresponding to this season:**

JAN FEB MAR ABR MAY JUN JUL AGO SEP OCT NOV DEC

- **Percentage of irrigated cropland:**

○ **SEASON # 2**

...

○ **SEASON # 3**

..

➤ **Where do you source your water for drinking water for livestock?**

- *Dam/lake.*
- *Groundwater.*
- *Piped regional water.*
- *Rainwater harvesting.*
- *Rivers.*
- *Wetland.*
- *Other (please specify).*

➤ **Do you have any of the following rainwater harvesting systems in place?**

- *On-farm rainwater storage of runoff from roofs or similar*
- *On-farm dams or ponds designed to capture rainwater*
- *On-farm floodwater storage when watercourses (e.g., rivers, streams, canals) overflow*
- *None*

➤ *Other (please specify)*

➤ **During which months of the year do you find it difficult to access enough water for your agricultural needs (e.g., growing crops, drinking water for livestock):**

○ **During a normal year:**

JAN FEB MAR ABR MAY JUN JUL AGO SEP OCT NOV DEC

○ **During a flood year:**

JAN FEB MAR ABR MAY JUN JUL AGO SEP OCT NOV DEC

○ **During a drought year:**

JAN FEB MAR ABR MAY JUN JUL AGO SEP OCT NOV DEC

4.3.2.6. Energy use

➤ **What types of energy do you use for:**

○ **Irrigation (select all relevant)**

- *Electricity (national grid)*
- *Wind turbine*
- *Solar panel*
- *Burning plant materials*
- *Gas*
- *Coal*
- *Petrol or diesel*
- *Cow dung cakes*
- *Other (please specify)*

○ **Tillage, sowing or harvesting (select all relevant)**

- *Electricity (national grid)*

- Gas
- Petrol or diesel
- Animal traction
- Human power/by hand only
- Other (please specify)

○ **Cooking (select all relevant)**

- Electricity (national grid)
- Wind turbine
- Solar panel
- Burning plant materials
- Biogas
- Gas LPG
- Coal
- Oil
- Other (please specify)

○ **Cleaning, processing, or transporting harvested food (select all relevant)**

- Electricity (national grid)
- Wind turbine
- Solar panel
- Burning plant materials
- Biogas
- Gas LPG
- Coal
- Petrol or diesel
- Animal traction
- Other (please specify)

➤ **Where do you source most of your energy?**

- 5 - All energy is self-produced, exchanged with other farmers or managed collectively.
- 4 - 25% of energy is purchased from the market, the other 75% is self-produced or exchanged.

- 3 - 50% of energy is purchased from the market, the other 50% produced on farm/within the agroecosystem or exchanged with other members of the community.
- 2 - 75% of energy is purchased from the market, the other 25% is produced on farm/within the agroecosystem or exchanged with other members of the community.
- 1 - All energy is purchased from the market.

4.3.3. Economic

4.3.3.1. Income

- In the past 12 months, approximately how much income in [local currency] did the household make from the following sources.

<input type="radio"/> Crop production	<i>Income</i>
<input type="radio"/> Livestock production	<i>Income</i>
<input type="radio"/> Fish production	<i>Income</i>
<input type="radio"/> Other family business	<i>Income</i>
<input type="radio"/> Casual labour	<i>Income</i>
<input type="radio"/> Formal labour office job	<i>Income</i>
<input type="radio"/> Cash transfers	<i>Income</i>
<input type="radio"/> Leasing agricultural or non-agricultural land	<i>Income</i>
<input type="radio"/> Subsidy	<i>Income</i>
Other source of income	<i>Income</i>

➤ **How would you rate the stability of the household income?**

Hint: Please choose the option that best represent

- 5 - Income is increasing over time.
- 4 - Income is stable over time.
- 3 - Income varies little from year to year.
- 2 - Income varies from year to year.
- 1 - Income is on a decreasing trend.

➤ **In the last 12 months, did the household spend more money on the farm than it earns from the farm?**

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

➤ **If the answer is “Yes”, Could you please provide some insights into the reasons behind the excess expenditure and approximately how much money was spent in excess?**

➤ **Please observe the farmer's main household and ask, what material is the roof of the house made of?**

- Bamboo
- Concrete, brick, stone
- Fibrous cements
- Galvanized iron or aluminum or other metal sheets
- Thatch/leaves/grass
- Tiles
- Other (please specify)

➤ **Please observe the farmer's main household and ask, what material are the walls of the house made of?**

- Asbestos
- Bricks
- Iron sheet
- Mud

- *Plastered*
- *Stones*
- *Wood*
- *Other (please specify)*

➤ **In the past 12 months, what percentage of the household's income was generated by the following sources.**

- **Agricultural production:** %
- **Livestock production:** %
- **Fishing production:** %
- **Other family business:** %
- **Casual labour:** %
- **Formal labour office job:** %
- **Cash transfers (e.g., transfers from absent family members, donations):** %
- **Leasing agricultural or non-agricultural land:** %
- **Subsidy (e.g., education subsidies, government social programs):** %
- **Other (please specify):** %

➤ **In the past 7 days, what percentage of the household's income was used for buying food?**

- *None*
- *1-25%*
- *26-50%*

- 51-75%
- 76-100%

4.3.3.2. Agricultural productivity

- **What is the total area of land used for growing crops in hectares / acres?**
- **List the main 3 crops produced in the last 12 months, in terms of harvested area.**

○ **CROP # 1**

- **Name of the crop species:**
- **Number of varieties produced:**
- **Area of land under production in hectares / acres:**
- **Total production (Please specify the unit of production):**
- **What does the production get used for**

Hint: Please, allocate the amount produced for the following uses:

- *Human consumption:*
- *Own livestock consumption:*
- *Sold on-farm direct to consumers:*
- *Sold to a cooperative:*
- *Sold in the marketplace:*
- *Sold to a trader or supermarket:*
- *Gifts:*
- *Wasted/lost:*
- *Other (please specify other use):*
- **Specify the price of the produce sold:**
 - *On-farm direct to consumers [currency/unit of production]:*
 - *To a cooperative [currency/unit of production]:*

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>In the marketplace [currency/unit of production]:</i> ➤ <i>To a trader or supermarket [currency/unit of production]:</i>
○ CROP # 2
...
○ CROP # 3
...

➤ **Do the crops you grow come from certified quality seeds or locally adapted varieties (e.g., traditional cultivars, landraces)?**

- 5- Only or mainly locally adapted varieties are grown.
- 4 - Some certified seeds and some locally adapted varieties are grown (e.g., traditional cultivars, landraces).
- 3 - Mainly certified seeds and some locally adapted varieties are grown (e.g., traditional cultivars, landraces).
- 2 - Only or mainly certified quality seeds are grown.
- 1 - I don't know, or seeds are neither certified or locally adapted.

➤ **What is the area of land used for livestock production in hectares / acres?**

○ Land you own:	<i>Hectares / Acres</i>
○ Share grazing land:	<i>Hectares / Acres</i>

➤ **List the main 3 livestock species produced in the last 12 months, in terms of animal numbers.**

○ LIVESTOCK # 1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Name of the animal species: - Number of different breeds raised: - Total number of animals raised in the last 12 months:

- **Total production (Please specify the unit of production):**
- **What did the livestock get raised for?**

Hint: Please, allocate the amount produced for the following purposes:

❖ **Meat production** (please specify the production unit)

- *Human consumption (on-farm):*
- *Sold on-farm direct to consumer:*
Provide the price at which was sold:
- *Sold to a cooperative:*
Provide the price at which was sold:
- *Sold in the marketplace:*
Provide the price at which was sold:
- *Sold to a trader or supermarket:*
Provide the price at which was sold:
- *Gifts:*
- *Wasted/lost:*
- *Other (please specify):*

❖ **Dairy production** (please specify the production unit)

- *Human consumption:*
- *Sold on-farm direct to consumer:*
Provide the price at which was sold:
- *Sold to a cooperative:*
Provide the price at which was sold:
- *Sold in the marketplace:*
Provide the price at which was sold:
- *Sold to a trader or supermarket:*
Provide the price at which was sold:
- *Gifts:*
- *Wasted/lost:*
- *Other use (please specify):*

❖ **Eggs production** (please specify the production unit)

- Human consumption:
- Sold on-farm direct to consumer:
Provide the price at which was sold:
- Sold to a cooperative:
Provide the price at which was sold:
- Sold in the marketplace:
Provide the price at which was sold:
- Sold to a trader or supermarket:
Provide the price at which was sold:
- Gifts:
- Wasted/lost:
- Other use (please specify):

❖ **Fibre production** (please specify the production unit)

- On-farm use:
- Sold on-farm direct to consumer:
Provide the price at which was sold:
- Sold to a cooperative:
Provide the price at which was sold:
- Sold in the marketplace:
Provide the price at which was sold:
- Sold to a trader or supermarket:
Provide the price at which was sold:
- Gifts:
- Wasted/lost:
- Other use (please specify):

❖ **Livestock breeding production** (please specify the production unit)

- On-farm use:
- Sold on-farm direct to consumer:
Provide the price at which was sold:

- *Sold to a cooperative:*
Provide the price at which was sold:
- *Sold in the marketplace:*
Provide the price at which was sold:
- *Sold to a trader or supermarket:*
Provide the price at which was sold:
- *Gifts:*
- *Wasted/lost:*
- *Other use (please specify):*

❖ ***Manure production (please specify the production unit)***

- *On-farm use:*
- *Sold on-farm direct to consumer:*
Provide the price at which was sold:
- *Sold to a cooperative:*
Provide the price at which was sold:
- *Sold in the marketplace:*
Provide the price at which was sold:
- *Sold to a trader or supermarket:*
Provide the price at which was sold:
- *Gifts:*
- *Wasted/lost:*
- *Other use (please specify):*

❖ ***Transportation (please specify the production unit)***

- *On-farm use:*
- *Sold on-farm direct to consumer:*
Provide the price at which was sold:
- *Sold to a cooperative:*
Provide the price at which was sold:
- *Sold in the marketplace:*
Provide the price at which was sold:

➤ *Sold to a trader or supermarket:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

➤ *Gifts:*

➤ *Wasted/lost:*

➤ *Other use (please specify):*

❖ **Honey production** (please specify the production unit)

➤ *Human consumption:*

➤ *Sold on-farm direct to consumer:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

➤ *Sold to a cooperative:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

➤ *Sold in the marketplace:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

➤ *Sold to a trader or supermarket:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

➤ *Gifts:*

➤ *Wasted/lost:*

➤ *Other use (please specify):*

❖ **Draft power** (please specify the production unit)

➤ *On-farm use:*

➤ *Sold on-farm direct to consumer:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

➤ *Sold to a cooperative:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

➤ *Sold in the marketplace:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

➤ *Sold to a trader or supermarket:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

➤ *Gifts:*

➤ *Wasted/lost:*

➤ *Other use (please specify):*

❖ ***Other produce (please specify) (please specify the production unit)***

➤ *Human consumption (on-farm):*

➤ *On-farm use:*

➤ *Sold on-farm direct to consumer:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

➤ *Sold to a cooperative:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

➤ *Sold in the marketplace:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

➤ *Sold to a trader or supermarket:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

➤ *Gifts:*

➤ *Wasted/lost:*

➤ *Other use (please specify):*

○ **LIVESTOCK # 2**

...

○ **LIVESTOCK # 3**

...

➤ **Are the livestock you keep exotic or local?**

- *Only or mainly local breeds are kept.*
- *75% are local breeds, and 25% are exotic breeds and*
- *75% are exotic breeds and 25% are local breeds.*
- *Equal numbers of exotic breeds and local breeds are kept.*
- *Only exotic breeds are kept.*
- *No exotic or local breeds are kept.*
- *I don't know.*

➤ **Have the livestock received any vaccinations in the last 12 months?**

- Yes
- No

➤ **Have the livestock received preventative antibiotics in the last 12 months?**

- Yes
- No

➤ **In the last 12 months, where was fish production carried out?**

- Wetland
- Paddy field
- Other (please specify)

➤ **What is the total surface area in hectares / acres of water bodies, wetlands, paddy fields or other aquaculture systems used for producing fish?**

➤ **List the main 3 fish species produced in the last 12 months, in terms of animal numbers.**

○ **FISH # 1**

- **Name of the fish species:**
- **Total number kept in the last 12 months:**
- **What did the fish get kept for?**

Hint: Please, allocate the amount produced for the following purposes:

❖ ***Meat production (please specify the production unit)***

- *Human consumption (on-farm):*
- *Own livestock consumption:*
- *Sold on-farm direct to consumer:*
Provide the price at which was sold:
- *Sold to a cooperative:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

- *Sold in the marketplace:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

- *Sold to a trader or supermarket:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

- *Gifts:*
- *Wasted/lost:*
- *Other (please specify):*

❖ **Breeding production** (please specify the production unit)

- *On-farm use*
- *Sold on-farm direct to consumer:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

- *Sold to a cooperative:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

- *Sold in the marketplace:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

- *Sold to a trader or supermarket:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

- *Gifts:*
- *Wasted/lost:*
- *Other use (please specify):*

❖ **Ornamental production** (please specify the production unit)

- *On-farm use:*
- *Sold on-farm direct to consumer:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

- *Sold to a cooperative:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

- *Sold in the marketplace:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

- *Sold to a trader or supermarket:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

- *Gifts:*
- *Wasted/lost:*
- *Other use (please specify):*

❖ **Other produce** (please specify the production unit)

- *Human consumption (on-farm):*
- *On-farm use:*
- *Own livestock consumption:*
- *Sold on-farm direct to consumer:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

- *Sold to a cooperative:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

- *Sold in the marketplace:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

- *Sold to a trader or supermarket:*

Provide the price at which was sold:

- *Gifts:*
- *Wasted/lost:*
- *Other use (please specify):*

○ **FISH # 2**

...

○ **FISH # 3**

...

➤ **Labour productivity**

➤ **Household members working PERMANENTLY (all year around) on your farm:**

Household members	Number of workers	Average number of hours worked per day	In what production activities did these household members work?	Select the activities perform for CROP production (including perennial crops):	Select the activities perform for LIVESTOCK production:	Select the activities perform for FISH production:	Select the activities perform for TREES production (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber):	Select the activities perform for HONEY production:
o Male adults of working age (≥18 and ≤65 years old)	#	Hours	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Crops (including perennial crops) ➤ Livestock ➤ Fish ➤ Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber) ➤ Honey ➤ Other (please specify) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Land preparation. ➤ Planting. ➤ Weeding. ➤ Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities. ➤ Harvesting. ➤ Supervision. ➤ Shelling / Threshing / Peeling. ➤ Sorting. ➤ Drying. ➤ Cleaning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Animal feeding ➤ Health care and veterinary services ➤ Pasture management ➤ Herd management ➤ Milking and dairy management ➤ Waste management ➤ Wool management ➤ Management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly). ➤ Stocking. ➤ Feeding and nutrition. ➤ Water quality management ➤ Disease prevention and health management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Soil preparation. ➤ Seedling production or sourcing. ➤ Planting and transplanting ➤ Irrigation and water management ➤ Fertilization and nutrient management ➤ Pruning and training. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Hive management ➤ Bee colony management ➤ Bee health management ➤ Honey extraction. ➤ Honey processing. ➤ Packaging and labeling. ➤ Marketing and sales. ➤ Other activity

o Female adults of working age (≥18 and ≤65 years old)

#

Hours

- Crops (including perennial crops)
- Livestock
- Fish
- Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber)
- Honey
- Other (please specify)

- Land preparation.
- Planting.
- Weeding.
- Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities.
- Harvesting.
- Supervision.
- Shelling / Threshing / Peeling.
- Sorting.
- Drying.

- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management
- Waste management
- Wool management

- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management
- Disease prevention and health management

- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization and nutrient management

- Hive management
- Bee colony management
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.
- Honey processing.
- Packaging and labeling.
- Marketing and sales.

- Processing (milling, grinding, grating, etc.).
- Protection from losses.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs)
- Egg collection
- Marketing and sales
- Other activity (Please specify)

- Harvesting.
- Filleting and processing.
- Record keeping.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- Pest and disease management
- Weed control.
- Market and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).

(Please specify).

o Male adults not of working age (>65 years old)

#

Hours

- Crops (including perennial crops)
- Livestock
- Fish
- Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber)
- Honey
- Other (please specify)

- Land preparation.
- Planting.
- Weeding.
- Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities.
- Harvesting.
- Supervision.
- Shelling / Threshing / Peeling.

- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management
- Waste management

- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management
- Disease prevention and health

- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization and nutrient

- Hive management
- Bee colony management
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.
- Honey processing.
- Packaging and labeling.

- Cleaning.
- Processing (milling, grinding, grating, etc.).
- Protection from losses.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- Management of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs)
- Egg collection
- Marketing and sales
- Other activity (Please specify)
- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management
- Waste management

- Harvesting.
- Filleting and processing.
- Record keeping.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management
- Disease prevention and health

- Pruning and training.
- Pest and disease management
- Weed control.
- Market and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization and nutrient

- Other activity (Please specify).

o Female adults not of working age (>65 years old)

#

Hours

- Crops (including perennial crops)
- Livestock
- Fish
- Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber)
- Honey
- Other (please specify)

- Land preparation.
- Planting.
- Weeding.
- Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities.
- Harvesting.
- Supervision.

- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management

- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management

- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization

- Hive management
- Bee colony management
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.
- Honey processing.

- Sorting.
- Drying.
- Cleaning.
- Processing (milling, grinding, grating, etc.).
- Protection from losses.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- Wool management
- Management of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs)
- Egg collection
- Marketing and sales
- Other activity (Please specify)

- management
- Harvesting.
- Filleting and processing.
- Record keeping.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- management
- Pruning and training.
- Pest and disease management
- Weed control.
- Market and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).

o Male children (<18 years old)

#

Hours

- Shelling / Threshing / Peeling.
- Sorting.
- Drying.
- Cleaning.
- Processing (milling, grinding, grating, etc.).
- Protection from losses.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Waste management
- Wool management
- Management of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs)
- Egg collection
- Marketing and sales
- Other activity (Please specify)
- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Disease prevention and health management
- Harvesting.
- Filleting and processing.
- Record keeping.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality
- and nutrient management
- Pruning and training.
- Pest and disease management
- Weed control.
- Market and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Packaging and labeling.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Hive management
- Bee colony management
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.

➤ Other
(please
specify)

➤ Supervision.
➤ Shelling /
Threshing /
Peeling.
➤ Sorting.
➤ Drying.
➤ Cleaning.
➤ Processing
(milling,
grinding,
grating, etc.).
➤ Protection
from losses.
➤ Other
activity
(Please
specify).

➤ Milking
and dairy
management
➤ Waste
management
➤ Wool
management
➤ Management
of housing
and shelter
(e.g.,
cleaning,
repairs)
➤ Egg
collection
➤ Marketing
and sales
➤ Other
activity
(Please
specify)

management
.
➤ Disease
prevention
and health
management
.
➤ Harvesting.
➤ Filleting
and
processing.
➤ Record
keeping.
➤ Marketing
and sales.
➤ Other
activity
(Please
specify).

➤ Fertilization
and nutrient
management
.
➤ Pruning
and training.
➤ Pest and
disease
management
.
➤ Weed
control.
➤ Market
and sales.
➤ Other
activity
(Please
specify).

➤ Honey
processing.
➤ Packaging
and labeling.
➤ Marketing
and sales.
➤ Other
activity
(Please
specify).

o Female children (<18 years old)

#

Hours

- | | | | | | |
|---|---|---|--|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Crops (including perennial crops) ➤ Livestock ➤ Fish ➤ Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber) ➤ Honey ➤ Other (please specify) | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Land preparation. ➤ Planting. ➤ Weeding. ➤ Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities. ➤ Harvesting. ➤ Supervision. ➤ Shelling / Threshing / Peeling. ➤ Sorting. ➤ Drying. ➤ Cleaning. ➤ Processing (milling, grinding, etc.). ➤ Protection from losses. ➤ Other activity (Please specify). | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Animal feeding ➤ Health care and veterinary services ➤ Pasture management ➤ Herd management ➤ Milking and dairy management ➤ Waste management ➤ Wool management ➤ Management of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs) ➤ Egg collection ➤ Marketing and sales ➤ Other activity | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly). ➤ Stocking. ➤ Feeding and nutrition. ➤ Water quality management ➤ Disease prevention and health management ➤ Harvesting. ➤ Filleting and processing. ➤ Record keeping. ➤ Marketing and sales. ➤ Other activity (Please specify). | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Soil preparation. ➤ Seedling production or sourcing. ➤ Planting and transplanting ➤ Irrigation and water management ➤ Fertilization and nutrient management ➤ Pruning and training. ➤ Pest and disease management ➤ Weed control. ➤ Market and sales. ➤ Other activity (Please specify). | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Hive management ➤ Bee colony management ➤ Bee health management ➤ Honey extraction. ➤ Honey processing. ➤ Packaging and labeling. ➤ Marketing and sales. ➤ Other activity (Please specify). |
|---|---|---|--|---|--|

*(Please
specify)*

DRAFT

➤ Household members working SEASONALLY (only during peak periods) on your farm:

SEASON 1 Select the months worked per year for SEASON 1: JAN FEB MAR ABR MAY JUN JUL AGO SEP OCT NOV DEC

Household members	Number of workers	Average number of hours worked per day	In what production activities did these household members work?	Select the activities perform for CROP production (including perennial crops):	Select the activities perform for LIVESTOCK production:	Select the activities perform for FISH production:	Select the activities perform for TREES production (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber):	Select the activities perform for HONEY production:
o Male adults of working age (≥18 and ≤65 years old)	#	Hours	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Crops (including perennial crops) ➤ Livestock ➤ Fish ➤ Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber) ➤ Honey ➤ Other (please specify) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Land preparation. ➤ Planting. ➤ Weeding. ➤ Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities. ➤ Harvesting. ➤ Supervision. ➤ Shelling / Threshing / Peeling. ➤ Sorting. ➤ Drying. ➤ Cleaning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Animal feeding ➤ Health care and veterinary services ➤ Pasture management ➤ Herd management ➤ Milking and dairy management ➤ Waste management ➤ Wool management ➤ Management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly). ➤ Stocking. ➤ Feeding and nutrition. ➤ Water quality management ➤ Disease prevention and health management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Soil preparation. ➤ Seedling production or sourcing. ➤ Planting and transplanting ➤ Irrigation and water management ➤ Fertilization and nutrient management ➤ Pruning and training. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Hive management ➤ Bee colony management ➤ Bee health management ➤ Honey extraction. ➤ Honey processing. ➤ Packaging and labeling. ➤ Marketing and sales.

o Female adults of working age (≥18 and ≤65 years old)

#

Hours

- Crops (including perennial crops)
- Livestock
- Fish
- Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber)
- Honey
- Other (please specify)

- Processing (milling, grinding, grating, etc.).
- Protection from losses.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- Land preparation.
- Planting.
- Weeding.
- Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities.
- Harvesting.
- Supervision.
- Shelling / Threshing / Peeling.
- Sorting.
- Drying.

- Processing of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs)
- Egg collection
- Marketing and sales
- Other activity (Please specify)

- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management
- Waste management
- Wool management

- Harvesting.
- Filleting and processing.
- Record keeping.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management
- Disease prevention and health management

- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization and nutrient management

- Pest and disease management
- Weed control.
- Market and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- Hive management
- Bee colony management
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.
- Honey processing.
- Packaging and labeling.
- Marketing and sales.

- Other activity (Please specify).
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.
- Honey processing.
- Packaging and labeling.
- Marketing and sales.

o Male adults not of working age (>65 years old)

#

Hours

- Crops (including perennial crops)
- Livestock
- Fish
- Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber)
- Honey
- Other (please specify)

- Land preparation.
- Planting.
- Weeding.
- Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities.
- Harvesting.
- Supervision.
- Shelling / Threshing / Peeling.

- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management
- Waste management

- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management
- Disease prevention and health

- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization and nutrient

- Hive management
- Bee colony management
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.
- Honey processing.
- Packaging and labeling.

- Cleaning.
- Processing (milling, grinding, grating, etc.).
- Protection from losses.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- Management of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs)
- Egg collection
- Marketing and sales
- Other activity (Please specify)
- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management
- Waste management

- Harvesting.
- Filleting and processing.
- Record keeping.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management
- Disease prevention and health

- Pruning and training.
- Pest and disease management
- Weed control.
- Market and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization and nutrient

- Other activity (Please specify).

o Female adults not of working age (>65 years old)

#

Hours

- Crops (including perennial crops)
- Livestock
- Fish
- Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber)
- Honey
- Other (please specify)

- Land preparation.
- Planting.
- Weeding.
- Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities.
- Harvesting.
- Supervision.

- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management

- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management

- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization

- Hive management
- Bee colony management
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.
- Honey processing.

- Sorting.
- Drying.
- Cleaning.
- Processing (milling, grinding, grating, etc.).
- Protection from losses.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- Wool management
- Management of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs)
- Egg collection
- Marketing and sales
- Other activity (Please specify)
- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management

- management
- Harvesting.
- Filleting and processing.
- Record keeping.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management

- management
- Pruning and training.
- Pest and disease management
- Weed control.
- Market and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization

- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Hive management
- Bee colony management
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.
- Honey processing.

o Male children (<18 years old)

#

Hours

- Crops (including perennial crops)
- Livestock
- Fish
- Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber)
- Honey

- Land preparation.
- Planting.
- Weeding.
- Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities.
- Harvesting.

- Shelling / Threshing / Peeling.
- Sorting.
- Drying.
- Cleaning.
- Processing (milling, grinding, grating, etc.).
- Protection from losses.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- Waste management
- Wool management
- Management of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs)
- Egg collection
- Marketing and sales
- Other activity (Please specify)
- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management

- Disease prevention and health management
- Harvesting.
- Filleting and processing.
- Record keeping.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality

- and nutrient management
- Pruning and training.
- Pest and disease management
- Weed control.
- Market and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management

- Packaging and labeling.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Hive management
- Bee colony management
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.

➤ *Other*
(please
specify)

➤ Supervision.
➤ Shelling /
Threshing /
Peeling.
➤ Sorting.
➤ Drying.
➤ Cleaning.
➤ Processing
(milling,
grinding,
grating, etc.).
➤ Protection
from losses.
➤ Other
activity
(Please
specify).

➤ Milking
and dairy
management
➤ Waste
management
➤ Wool
management
➤ Management
of housing
and shelter
(e.g.,
cleaning,
repairs)
➤ Egg
collection
➤ Marketing
and sales
➤ Other
activity
(Please
specify)

management
.
➤ Disease
prevention
and health
management
.
➤ Harvesting.
➤ Filleting
and
processing.
➤ Record
keeping.
➤ Marketing
and sales.
➤ Other
activity
(Please
specify).

➤ Fertilization
and nutrient
management
.
➤ Pruning
and training.
➤ Pest and
disease
management
.
➤ Weed
control.
➤ Market
and sales.
➤ Other
activity
(Please
specify).

➤ Honey
processing.
➤ Packaging
and labeling.
➤ Marketing
and sales.
➤ Other
activity
(Please
specify).

o Female children (<18 years old)

#

Hours

- | | | | | | |
|---|---|---|--|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Crops (including perennial crops) ➤ Livestock ➤ Fish ➤ Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber) ➤ Honey ➤ Other (please specify) | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Land preparation. ➤ Planting. ➤ Weeding. ➤ Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities. ➤ Harvesting. ➤ Supervision. ➤ Shelling / Threshing / Peeling. ➤ Sorting. ➤ Drying. ➤ Cleaning. ➤ Processing (milling, grinding, etc.). ➤ Protection from losses. ➤ Other activity (Please specify). | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Animal feeding ➤ Health care and veterinary services ➤ Pasture management ➤ Herd management ➤ Milking and dairy management ➤ Waste management ➤ Wool management ➤ Management of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs) ➤ Egg collection ➤ Marketing and sales ➤ Other activity | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly). ➤ Stocking. ➤ Feeding and nutrition. ➤ Water quality management ➤ Disease prevention and health management ➤ Harvesting. ➤ Filleting and processing. ➤ Record keeping. ➤ Marketing and sales. ➤ Other activity (Please specify). | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Soil preparation. ➤ Seedling production or sourcing. ➤ Planting and transplanting ➤ Irrigation and water management ➤ Fertilization and nutrient management ➤ Pruning and training. ➤ Pest and disease management ➤ Weed control. ➤ Market and sales. ➤ Other activity (Please specify). | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Hive management ➤ Bee colony management ➤ Bee health management ➤ Honey extraction. ➤ Honey processing. ➤ Packaging and labeling. ➤ Marketing and sales. ➤ Other activity (Please specify). |
|---|---|---|--|---|--|

(Please specify)

SEASON 2 Select the months worked per year for SEASON 1: *JAN FEB MAR ABR MAY JUN JUL AGO SEP OCT NOV DEC*

Household members	Number of workers	Average number of hours worked per day	In what production activities did these household members work?	Select the activities perform for CROP production (including perennial crops):	Select the activities perform for LIVESTOCK production:	Select the activities perform for FISH production:	Select the activities perform for TREES production (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber):	Select the activities perform for HONEY production:
...

SEASON 3 Select the months worked per year for SEASON 1: *JAN FEB MAR ABR MAY JUN JUL AGO SEP OCT NOV DEC*

Household members	Number of workers	Average number of hours worked per day	In what production activities did these household members work?	Select the activities perform for CROP production (including perennial crops):	Select the activities perform for LIVESTOCK production:	Select the activities perform for FISH production:	Select the activities perform for TREES production (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber):	Select the activities perform for HONEY production:
...
SEASON 4	Select the months worked per year for SEASON 1: JAN FEB MAR ABR MAY JUN JUL AGO SEP OCT NOV DEC							
Household members	Number of workers	Average number of hours worked per day	In what production activities did these household members work?	Select the activities perform for CROP production (including perennial crops):	Select the activities perform for LIVESTOCK production:	Select the activities perform for FISH production:	Select the activities perform for TREES production (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber):	Select the activities perform for HONEY production:
...

➤ Hired/Free/Exchange Labourers working PERMANENTLY (all year around) on your farm:

Hired / Free / Exchange Labourers	Number of workers	Average number of hours worked per day	In what production activities did these household members work?	Select the activities perform for CROP production (including perennial crops):	Select the activities perform for LIVESTOCK production:	Select the activities perform for FISH production:	Select the activities perform for TREES production (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber):	Select the activities perform for HONEY production:
o Male adults of working age (≥18 and ≤65 years old)	#	Hours	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Crops (including perennial crops) ➤ Livestock ➤ Fish ➤ Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber) ➤ Honey ➤ Other (please specify) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Land preparation. ➤ Planting. ➤ Weeding. ➤ Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities. ➤ Harvesting. ➤ Supervision. ➤ Shelling / Threshing / Peeling. ➤ Sorting. ➤ Drying. ➤ Cleaning. ➤ Processing (milling, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Animal feeding ➤ Health care and veterinary services ➤ Pasture management ➤ Herd management ➤ Milking and dairy management ➤ Waste management ➤ Wool management ➤ Management of housing and shelter (e.g., 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly). ➤ Stocking. ➤ Feeding and nutrition. ➤ Water quality management ➤ Disease prevention and health management ➤ Harvesting. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Soil preparation. ➤ Seedling production or sourcing. ➤ Planting and transplanting ➤ Irrigation and water management ➤ Fertilization and nutrient management ➤ Pruning and training. ➤ Pest and disease 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Hive management ➤ Bee colony management ➤ Bee health management ➤ Honey extraction. ➤ Honey processing. ➤ Packaging and labeling. ➤ Marketing and sales. ➤ Other activity (Please specify).

o Female adults of working age (≥18 and ≤65 years old)

#

Hours

- | | | | | | | |
|--|---|---|--|--|--|---|
| | | grinding, grating, etc.).
➤ Protection from losses.
➤ Other activity (Please specify). | cleaning, repairs)
➤ Egg collection
➤ Marketing and sales
➤ Other activity (Please specify) | ➤ Filleting and processing.
➤ Record keeping.
➤ Marketing and sales.
➤ Other activity (Please specify). | management
.
➤ Weed control.
➤ Market and sales.
➤ Other activity (Please specify). | |
| | ➤ Crops (including perennial crops)
➤ Livestock
➤ Fish
➤ Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber)
➤ Honey
➤ Other (please specify) | ➤ Land preparation.
➤ Planting.
➤ Weeding.
➤ Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities.
➤ Harvesting.
➤ Supervision.
➤ Shelling / Threshing / Peeling.
➤ Sorting.
➤ Drying.
➤ Cleaning. | ➤ Animal feeding
➤ Health care and veterinary services
➤ Pasture management
➤ Herd management
➤ Milking and dairy management
➤ Waste management
➤ Wool management
➤ Management of housing | ➤ Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
➤ Stocking.
➤ Feeding and nutrition.
➤ Water quality management
.
➤ Disease prevention and health management
.
➤ Harvesting. | ➤ Soil preparation.
➤ Seedling production or sourcing.
➤ Planting and transplanting
Irrigation and water management
.
➤ Fertilization and nutrient management
.
➤ Pruning and training. | ➤ Hive management
.
➤ Bee colony management
.
➤ Bee health management
.
➤ Honey extraction.
➤ Honey processing.
➤ Packaging and labeling.
➤ Marketing and sales.
➤ Other activity |

o Male adults not of working age (>65 years old)

#

Hours

- | | | | | | | |
|--|---|---|---|---|--|--|
| | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Processing (milling, grinding, grating, etc.). ➤ Protection from losses. ➤ Other activity (Please specify). | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs) ➤ Egg collection ➤ Marketing and sales ➤ Other activity (Please specify) | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Filleting and processing. ➤ Record keeping. ➤ Marketing and sales. ➤ Other activity (Please specify). | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Pest and disease management ➤ Weed control. ➤ Market and sales. ➤ Other activity (Please specify). | (Please specify). | |
| | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Crops (including perennial crops) ➤ Livestock ➤ Fish ➤ Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber) ➤ Honey ➤ Other (please specify) | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Land preparation. ➤ Planting. ➤ Weeding. ➤ Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities. ➤ Harvesting. ➤ Supervision. ➤ Shelling / Threshing / Peeling. ➤ Sorting. ➤ Drying. ➤ Cleaning. | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Animal feeding ➤ Health care and veterinary services ➤ Pasture management ➤ Herd management ➤ Milking and dairy management ➤ Waste management ➤ Wool management ➤ Management | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly). ➤ Stocking. ➤ Feeding and nutrition. ➤ Water quality management ➤ Disease prevention and health management | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Soil preparation. ➤ Seedling production or sourcing. ➤ Planting and transplanting ➤ Irrigation and water management ➤ Fertilization and nutrient management ➤ Pruning and training. | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Hive management ➤ Bee colony management ➤ Bee health management ➤ Honey extraction. ➤ Honey processing. ➤ Packaging and labeling. ➤ Marketing and sales. ➤ Other activity |

o Female adults not of working age (>65 years old)

#

Hours

- Crops (including perennial crops)
- Livestock
- Fish
- Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber)
- Honey
- Other (please specify)

- Land preparation.
- Planting.
- Weeding.
- Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities.
- Harvesting.
- Supervision.
- Shelling / Threshing / Peeling.
- Sorting.
- Drying.

- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management
- Waste management
- Wool management

- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management
- Disease prevention and health management

- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization and nutrient management

- Hive management
- Bee colony management
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.
- Honey processing.
- Packaging and labeling.
- Marketing and sales.

- Processing (milling, grinding, grating, etc.).
- Protection from losses.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs)
- Egg collection
- Marketing and sales
- Other activity (Please specify)

- Harvesting.
- Filleting and processing.
- Record keeping.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- Pest and disease management
- Weed control.
- Market and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).

(Please specify).

o Male children (<18 years old)

#

Hours

- Crops (including perennial crops)
- Livestock
- Fish
- Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber)
- Honey
- Other (please specify)

- Land preparation.
- Planting.
- Weeding.
- Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities.
- Harvesting.
- Supervision.
- Shelling / Threshing / Peeling.

- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management
- Waste management

- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management
- Disease prevention and health

- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization and nutrient

- Hive management
- Bee colony management
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.
- Honey processing.
- Packaging and labeling.

- Cleaning.
- Processing (milling, grinding, grating, etc.).
- Protection from losses.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- Management of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs)
- Egg collection
- Marketing and sales
- Other activity (Please specify)
- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management
- Waste management

- Harvesting.
- Filleting and processing.
- Record keeping.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management
- Disease prevention and health

- Pruning and training.
- Pest and disease management
- Weed control.
- Market and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization and nutrient

- Other activity (Please specify).

o Female children (<18 years old)

#

Hours

- Crops (including perennial crops)
- Livestock
- Fish
- Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber)
- Honey
- Other (please specify)

- Land preparation.
- Planting.
- Weeding.
- Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities.
- Harvesting.
- Supervision.

- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management

- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management

- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization

- Hive management
- Bee colony management
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.
- Honey processing.

- Sorting.
- Drying.
- Cleaning.
- Processing (milling, grinding, grating, etc.).
- Protection from losses.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- Wool management
- Management of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs)
- Egg collection
- Marketing and sales
- Other activity (Please specify)
- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management

- management
- Harvesting.
- Filleting and processing.
- Record keeping.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management

- management
- Pruning and training.
- Pest and disease management
- Weed control.
- Market and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization

- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Hive management
- Bee colony management
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.
- Honey processing.

- Shelling / Threshing / Peeling.
- Sorting.
- Drying.
- Cleaning.
- Processing (milling, grinding, grating, etc.).
- Protection from losses.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Waste management
- Wool management
- Management of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs)
- Egg collection
- Marketing and sales
- Other activity (Please specify)
- Disease prevention and health management
- Harvesting.
- Filleting and processing.
- Record keeping.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- and nutrient management
- Pruning and training.
- Pest and disease management
- Weed control.
- Market and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Packaging and labeling.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).

➤ **Hired / Free / Exchange Labourers working SEASONALLY (only during peak periods) on your farm:**

SEASON 1 Select the months worked per year for **SEASON 1:** JAN FEB MAR ABR MAY JUN JUL AGO SEP OCT NOV DEC

Hired / Free / Exchange Labourers	Number of workers	Average number of hours worked per day	In what production activities did these household members work?	Select the activities perform for CROP production (including perennial crops):	Select the activities perform for LIVESTOCK production:	Select the activities perform for FISH production:	Select the activities perform for TREES production (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber):	Select the activities perform for HONEY production:
o Male adults of working age (>14 and <65 years old)	#	Hours	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Crops (including perennial crops) ➤ Livestock ➤ Fish ➤ Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber) ➤ Honey ➤ Other (please specify) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Land preparation. ➤ Planting. ➤ Weeding. ➤ Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities. ➤ Harvesting. ➤ Supervision. ➤ Shelling / Threshing / Peeling. ➤ Sorting. ➤ Drying. ➤ Cleaning. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Animal feeding care and veterinary services ➤ Pasture management ➤ Herd management ➤ Milking and dairy management ➤ Waste management ➤ Wool management ➤ Management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly). ➤ Stocking. ➤ Feeding and nutrition. ➤ Water quality management ➤ Disease prevention and health management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Soil preparation. ➤ Seedling production or sourcing. ➤ Planting and transplanting ➤ Irrigation and water management ➤ Fertilization and nutrient management ➤ Pruning and training. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Hive management ➤ Bee colony management ➤ Bee health management ➤ Honey extraction. ➤ Honey processing. ➤ Packaging and labeling. ➤ Marketing and sales. ➤ Other activity

o Female adults of working age (>14 and <65 years old)

#

Hours

- Crops (including perennial crops)
- Livestock
- Fish
- Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber)
- Honey
- Other (please specify)

- Land preparation.
- Planting.
- Weeding.
- Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities.
- Harvesting.
- Supervision.
- Shelling / Threshing / Peeling.
- Sorting.
- Drying.

- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management
- Waste management
- Wool management

- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management
- Disease prevention and health management

- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization and nutrient management

- Hive management
- Bee colony management
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.
- Honey processing.
- Packaging and labeling.
- Marketing and sales.

- Processing (milling, grinding, grating, etc.).
- Protection from losses.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs)
- Egg collection
- Marketing and sales
- Other activity (Please specify)

- Harvesting.
- Filleting and processing.
- Record keeping.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- Pest and disease management
- Weed control.
- Market and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).

(Please specify).

o Male adults not of working age (>64 years old)

#

Hours

- Crops (including perennial crops)
- Livestock
- Fish
- Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber)
- Honey
- Other (please specify)

- Land preparation.
- Planting.
- Weeding.
- Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities.
- Harvesting.
- Supervision.
- Shelling / Threshing / Peeling.

- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management
- Waste management

- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management
- Disease prevention and health

- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization and nutrient

- Hive management
- Bee colony management
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.
- Honey processing.
- Packaging and labeling.

- Cleaning.
- Processing (milling, grinding, grating, etc.).
- Protection from losses.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- Management of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs)
- Egg collection
- Marketing and sales
- Other activity (Please specify)
- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management
- Waste management

- Harvesting.
- Filleting and processing.
- Record keeping.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management
- Disease prevention and health

- Pruning and training.
- Pest and disease management
- Weed control.
- Market and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization and nutrient

- Other activity (Please specify).

o Female adults not of working age (>64 years old)

#

Hours

- Crops (including perennial crops)
- Livestock
- Fish
- Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber)
- Honey
- Other (please specify)

- Land preparation.
- Planting.
- Weeding.
- Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities.
- Harvesting.
- Supervision.

- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management

- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management

- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization

- Hive management
- Bee colony management
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.
- Honey processing.

- Sorting.
- Drying.
- Cleaning.
- Processing (milling, grinding, grating, etc.).
- Protection from losses.
- Other activity (Please specify).

- Wool management
- Management of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs)
- Egg collection
- Marketing and sales
- Other activity (Please specify)
- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Milking and dairy management

- management
- Harvesting.
- Filleting and processing.
- Record keeping.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality management

- management
- Pruning and training.
- Pest and disease management
- Weed control.
- Market and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Fertilization

- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Hive management
- Bee colony management
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.
- Honey processing.

o Male children (<15 years old)

#

Hours

- Shelling / Threshing / Peeling.
- Sorting.
- Drying.
- Cleaning.
- Processing (milling, grinding, grating, etc.).
- Protection from losses.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Waste management
- Wool management
- Management of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs)
- Egg collection
- Marketing and sales
- Other activity (Please specify)
- Animal feeding
- Health care and veterinary services
- Pasture management
- Herd management
- Disease prevention and health management
- Harvesting.
- Filleting and processing.
- Record keeping.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly).
- Stocking.
- Feeding and nutrition.
- Water quality
- and nutrient management
- Pruning and training.
- Pest and disease management
- Weed control.
- Market and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Soil preparation.
- Seedling production or sourcing.
- Planting and transplanting
- Irrigation and water management
- Packaging and labeling.
- Marketing and sales.
- Other activity (Please specify).
- Hive management
- Bee colony management
- Bee health management
- Honey extraction.

➤ Other
(please
specify)

➤ Supervision.
➤ Shelling /
Threshing /
Peeling.
➤ Sorting.
➤ Drying.
➤ Cleaning.
➤ Processing
(milling,
grinding,
grating, etc.).
➤ Protection
from losses.
➤ Other
activity
(Please
specify).

➤ Milking
and dairy
management
➤ Waste
management
➤ Wool
management
➤ Management
of housing
and shelter
(e.g.,
cleaning,
repairs)
➤ Egg
collection
➤ Marketing
and sales
➤ Other
activity
(Please
specify)

management
.
➤ Disease
prevention
and health
management
.
➤ Harvesting.
➤ Filleting
and
processing.
➤ Record
keeping.
➤ Marketing
and sales.
➤ Other
activity
(Please
specify).

➤ Fertilization
and nutrient
management
.
➤ Pruning
and training.
➤ Pest and
disease
management
.
➤ Weed
control.
➤ Market
and sales.
➤ Other
activity
(Please
specify).

➤ Honey
processing.
➤ Packaging
and labeling.
➤ Marketing
and sales.
➤ Other
activity
(Please
specify).

o Female children (<15 years old)

#

Hours

- | | | | | | |
|---|---|---|--|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Crops (including perennial crops) ➤ Livestock ➤ Fish ➤ Trees (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber) ➤ Honey ➤ Other (please specify) | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Land preparation. ➤ Planting. ➤ Weeding. ➤ Ridging, fertilizing, other non-harvested activities. ➤ Harvesting. ➤ Supervision. ➤ Shelling / Threshing / Peeling. ➤ Sorting. ➤ Drying. ➤ Cleaning. ➤ Processing (milling, grinding, etc.). ➤ Protection from losses. ➤ Other activity (Please specify). | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Animal feeding ➤ Health care and veterinary services ➤ Pasture management ➤ Herd management ➤ Milking and dairy management ➤ Waste management ➤ Wool management ➤ Management of housing and shelter (e.g., cleaning, repairs) ➤ Egg collection ➤ Marketing and sales ➤ Other activity | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Site preparation (e.g., prepare ponds, tanks, or cages accordingly). ➤ Stocking. ➤ Feeding and nutrition. ➤ Water quality management ➤ Disease prevention and health management ➤ Harvesting. ➤ Filleting and processing. ➤ Record keeping. ➤ Marketing and sales. ➤ Other activity (Please specify). | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Soil preparation. ➤ Seedling production or sourcing. ➤ Planting and transplanting ➤ Irrigation and water management ➤ Fertilization and nutrient management ➤ Pruning and training. ➤ Pest and disease management ➤ Weed control. ➤ Market and sales. ➤ Other activity (Please specify). | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Hive management ➤ Bee colony management ➤ Bee health management ➤ Honey extraction. ➤ Honey processing. ➤ Packaging and labeling. ➤ Marketing and sales. ➤ Other activity (Please specify). |
|---|---|---|--|---|--|

(Please specify)

SEASON 2 Select the months worked per year for SEASON 1: JAN FEB MAR ABR MAY JUN JUL AGO SEP OCT NOV DEC

Hired / Free / Exchange Labourers	Number of workers	Average number of hours worked per day	In what production activities did these household members work?	Select the activities perform for CROP production (including perennial crops):	Select the activities perform for LIVESTOCK production:	Select the activities perform for FISH production:	Select the activities perform for TREES production (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber):	Select the activities perform for HONEY production:
...

SEASON 3 Select the months worked per year for SEASON 1: JAN FEB MAR ABR MAY JUN JUL AGO SEP OCT NOV DEC

Hired / Free / Exchange Labourers	Number of workers	Average number of hours worked per day	In what production activities did these household members work?	Select the activities perform for CROP production (including perennial crops):	Select the activities perform for LIVESTOCK production:	Select the activities perform for FISH production:	Select the activities perform for TREES production (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber):	Select the activities perform for HONEY production:
...

SEASON 4 Select the months worked per year for **SEASON 1:** *JAN FEB MAR ABR MAY JUN JUL AGO SEP OCT NOV DEC*

Hired / Free / Exchange Labourers	Number of workers	Average number of hours worked per day	In what production activities did these household members work?	Select the activities perform for CROP production (including perennial crops):	Select the activities perform for LIVESTOCK production:	Select the activities perform for FISH production:	Select the activities perform for TREES production (e.g., for wood, bark, rubber):	Select the activities perform for HONEY production:
...

4.3.3.3. Climate resilience

- **Has any household member received training in the last 12 months in the following topics:**
- | | | | |
|---|-----|----|---------------------|
| ○ Training in Innovative or best management agricultural practices | Yes | No | <i>I don't know</i> |
| ○ Training in Agribusiness management and value addition | Yes | No | <i>I don't know</i> |
| ○ Other training (please specify) | Yes | No | <i>I don't know</i> |
- **In the past 5 years, has your household needed credit to support investment in your farming business, but was unable to obtain it?**
- *Yes, we needed credit but could not obtain it.*
 - *No, we did not need credit during that period.*
 - *Yes, we needed credit and were able to obtain it.*
 - *Don't know / Not sure.*

If the answer is Yes, please reply to the following question

- **Credit for what types of investment**
Hint: select all that apply.
- *Investments in machinery.*
 - *Investments to buy fertilizers or pesticides.*
 - *Investments to build storage.*
 - *Investments to build processing facilities.*
 - *Investments to change to less intensive farm production system (e.g. to organic).*
 - *Investments to plant trees on-farm.*
 - *Investments in irrigation systems (e.g., drip irrigation).*
 - *Investment to build livestock sheds.*
 - *Investment to build water storage facility.*
 - *Investment in bee keeping.*
 - *Other (please specify)*

If your household obtained the credit, please answer the following question:

- **Please indicate the source of the credit you obtained for your farming business.**
- *Bank*
 - *Cooperative*
 - *Microfinance Institutions*
 - *Governmental agricultural loan programs*
 - *NGOs*
 - *Farmers' associations/organizations*
 - *Friend loans*
 - *Family loans*
 - *Agricultural Insurance Companies*
 - *Trade Credit (e.g., from buyers, processors, or retailers)*

- *Supplier Credit (e.g., from input suppliers, equipment dealers)*
- *Other (please specify)*

➤ **Have your farm/household fully paid off the credit?**

- *Yes*
- *No*

➤ **How do you feel about your farm/household's ability to meet credit repayments now and until the loans are fully repaid?**

- *We are currently able to meet our loan repayments and confident that we can meet our future repayments.*
- *We are currently able to meet our loan repayments, but uncertain about meeting future repayments.*
- *We are currently not able to meet our loan repayments, but confident about meeting future repayments.*
- *We are currently not able to meet our loan repayments and uncertain about meeting future repayments.*

➤ **Do you have insurance against agricultural losses?**

- *Yes, fully covered.*
- *Yes, partially covered.*
- *No.*

If the answer is yes, please answer the following question:

➤ **What is covered, e.g. losses to crops/livestock/buildings from weather events, pest outbreaks, market shocks?**

➤ **Do you have access to subsidies for agricultural inputs?**

- *Yes*
- *No*

If the answer of the last question is “Yes”, please answer the following:

➤ **For which inputs?**

➤ **Do any children in the household attend school?**

- *Yes*
- *No*

If the answer for the previous question is “Yes”, please answer the following question:

➤ **On average, how many free schools' meals were received per week over the last 4 weeks of schools attendance?**

- *More than one meal per day every day.*
- *At least one meal per day every day.*
- *One meal per day on most days.*
- *One meal per day occasionally.*
- *No meals.*

➤ **In the last 12 months, what were the most severe shocks faced by the household?**

Hint: Enumerator: Shock means an unexpected or unpredictable event that is external to the specific household, causing a disturbance in the equilibrium or permanence of something, which can either harm or boost it. Please, mark all shocks mentioned.

- Extreme weather events (e.g. cyclones, dust storm, excess rainfall, insufficient rainfall, frost, high temperatures, high winds)
- Death of a household member
- Government change
- Indebtedness
- Market disruptions
- Natural disasters (e.g., floods, droughts, wildfires)
- Pest or disease outbreaks
- Policy changes
- Price fluctuations in market
- Severe illness of a household member
- None
- Other (please specify)

➤ **What did the household members do to cope with the shocks?**

- Accessed insurance or risk management mechanisms.
- Diversified on-farm income sources of income.
- Engage in off-farm income sources.
- Migrated.
- Reduced area under cultivation.
- Reduced food consumption.
- Reduced household expenditure.
- Relied on institutional support.
- Sold assets.
- Switched from chemical to organic farming.
- Switched from organic to chemical farming.
- Taken loans.
- Other (please specify).
- Nothing

➤ **How would you rate the capacity of the household's income and agricultural production to recover from shocks/perturbations?**

- 5 - They fully and quickly recover after shocks/perturbations.
- 4 - Income and production mostly recover after shocks/perturbations.
- 3- Income and production partially recover after shocks/perturbations.
- 2 - There is little capacity to recover after shocks/perturbations.
- 1 - There is no capacity to recover after shocks/perturbations.

➤ **Would any of the following individuals or organisations provide your household support in case of need. By support I mean all types of support no matter how small or big, including but not limited to emotional support, food, job opportunities, loans or credit, housing.**

Hint: Answer with yes, no or I don't know.

<input type="radio"/> Banks	Yes	No	<i>I don't know</i>
<input type="radio"/> Community leaders	Yes	No	<i>I don't know</i>
<input type="radio"/> Individuals from a different community (family/ friends/ farmers)	Yes	No	<i>I don't know</i>
<input type="radio"/> Individuals from my community (family/ friends/ fellow farmers)	Yes	No	<i>I don't know</i>
<input type="radio"/> Local farmer cooperatives	Yes	No	<i>I don't know</i>
<input type="radio"/> Local farmer producer organization	Yes	No	<i>I don't know</i>
<input type="radio"/> Local government	Yes	No	<i>I don't know</i>
<input type="radio"/> Moneylenders	Yes	No	<i>I don't know</i>
<input type="radio"/> National government	Yes	No	<i>I don't know</i>
<input type="radio"/> NGOs	Yes	No	<i>I don't know</i>
<input type="radio"/> Other local associations (e.g. women support groups, youth groups)	Yes	No	<i>I don't know</i>
<input type="radio"/> Shops/private input dealer	Yes	No	<i>I don't know</i>
<input type="radio"/> Other (please specify)	Yes	No	<i>I don't know</i>

➤ **How many of the following assets do household members own?**

- Car** #
- Motorbike** #
- Bicycle** #
- Gas cooker** #
- Electric cooker** #
- Mobile phone** #
- Smartphone (with internet access)** #
- Ox-plough** #
- Tractor** #
- Plow** #
- Seed drill** #

- **Crop storage facility** #
- **Other asset (please specify)** #

➤ **Does your household have the following services:**

Hint: Answer with yes or no.

○ Drinking water piped to the household	Yes	No
○ Toilet with piped sewer or septic tank	Yes	No
○ Electrical energy	Yes	No
○ Waste (rubbish) collection service	Yes	No
○ Mobile phone reception	Yes	No
○ Internet	Yes	No

➤ **How far (one way) is the household from your closest farmland in minutes / kilometers?**

Hint: If the household and farmland are located in the same place, please put 0 minutes/kilometers

○ **Select the state mode of transport:**

- Walking
- Cycling
- Motorbike
- Car
- Horse
- Donkey

Minutes/Kilometers

➤ **How far (one way) is the household from the closest accessible and functioning FRESHWATER SOURCE in minutes?**

Hint: If the household has piped drinking water, please put 0 minutes/kilometers

○ **Select the state mode of transport:**

- Walking
- Cycling
- Motorbike
- Car
- Horse
- Donkey

Minutes/Kilometers

➤ **How far (one way) is the household from the closest accessible and functioning PRIMARY SCHOOL in minutes/kilometers?**

○ **Select the state mode of transport:**

- *Walking*
- *Cycling*
- *Motorbike*
- *Car*
- *Horse*
- *Donkey*

Minutes/Kilometers

➤ **How far (one way) is the household from the closest accessible and functioning PUBLIC HOSPITAL OR HEALTH FACILITY in minutes/kilometers?**

○ **Select the state mode of transport:**

- *Walking*
- *Cycling*
- *Motorbike*
- *Car*
- *Horse*
- *Donkey*

Minutes/Kilometers

➤ **How far (one way) is the household from the closest accessible and functioning LIVESTOCK MARKET in minutes/kilometers?**

○ **Select the state mode of transport:**

- *Walking*
- *Cycling*
- *Motorbike*
- *Car*
- *Horse*
- *Donkey*

Minutes/Kilometers

➤ **How far (one way) is the household from the closest accessible and functioning AGRICULTURAL/CROPS MARKET in minutes/kilometers?**

○ **Select the state mode of transport:**

- *Walking*
- *Cycling*
- *Motorbike*
- *Car*
- *Horse*
- *Donkey*

Minutes/Kilometers

➤ **How far (one way) is the household from the closest accessible and functioning PUBLIC TRANSPORT in minutes/kilometers?**

○ **Select the state mode of transport:**

- *Walking*
- *Cycling*
- *Motorbike*
- *Car*
- *Horse*
- *Donkey*

Minutes/Kilometers

➤ **How far (one way) is the household from the closest accessible and functioning WELL-MAINTAINED ROAD SUITABLE FOR CARS in minutes/kilometers?**

○ **Select the state mode of transport:**

- *Walking*
- *Cycling*
- *Motorbike*
- *Car*
- *Horse*
- *Donkey*

Minutes/Kilometers

4.3.4. Social

4.3.4.1. Diet quality

Now I'd like to ask you some yes-or-no questions about foods and drinks that you consumed yesterday during the day or night, whether you had it at home or somewhere else. First, I would like you to think about yesterday, from the time you woke up through the night. Think to yourself about the first thing you ate or drank after you woke up in the morning. Think about where you were when you had any food or drink in the middle of the day. Think about where you were when you had any evening meal and any food or drink you may have had in the evening or late-night and any other snacks or drinks you may have had between meals throughout the day or night. I am interested in whether you had the food items I will mention even if they were combined with other foods. Please listen to the list of foods and drinks, and if you ate or drank ANY ONE OF THEM, say yes.

➤ **Yesterday did you eat any of the following foods?**

○ Foods made from grains	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
○ Whole grains	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
○ White roots, tubers, and plantains	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
○ Pulses	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
○ Vitamin A-rich orange vegetables	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
○ Dark green leafy vegetables	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>

<input type="radio"/> Other vegetables	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Vitamin A-rich fruits	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Citrus	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Other fruits	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Baked / grain-based sweets	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Other sweets	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Eggs	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Cheese	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Yogurt	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Processed meats	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Unprocessed red meat (ruminant)	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Unprocessed red meat (non-ruminant)	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Poultry	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Fish and seafood	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Nuts and seeds	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Packaged ultra-processed salty snacks	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Instant noodles	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Deep fried foods	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Fluid milk	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Sweet tea / coffee / cocoa	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Fruit juice and fruit-flavoured drinks	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Sugar-sweetened beverages (soft drinks, energy drinks, sports drinks)	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>
<input type="radio"/> Fast food	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>

4.3.4.2. Farmer agency

Now I would like to talk to you about how much power and freedom women and men have to make important decisions in the food system, for example about how and what kind of food is

produced, where it goes, how much it costs, and how and what kind of food people consume. Please imagine a five-step ladder, where at the bottom on the first step stand individual men and women of the community with little capacity to make their own decisions about food production, trade or consumption. These individuals have little to say about types and varieties of crops, animals, trees, they produce, the way they manage their water, land, soil, animals, and wildlife, the markets available to them, and the food source and food choices available to them. On the highest step, the fifth, stand those who have great capacity to make important decisions for themselves, including what they grow, how they manage their land, soil, water, animals, and trees, who they sell the food to, and what food they buy.

- **On which step of the ladder would you position the majority of women in your household today?**
 - *Step 5: Power and freedom to make all major life decisions.*
 - *Step 4: Power and freedom to make many major life decisions.*
 - *Step 3: Power and freedom to make some major life decisions.*
 - *Step 2: Only a small amount of power and freedom.*
 - *Step 1: Almost no power or freedom to make decisions.*
- **Could you explain the main reasons for your rating?**
- **On which step of the ladder would you position the majority of women in your household 10 years ago?**
 - *Step 5: Power and freedom to make all major life decisions.*
 - *Step 4: Power and freedom to make many major life decisions.*
 - *Step 3: Power and freedom to make some major life decisions.*
 - *Step 2: Only a small amount of power and freedom.*
 - *Step 1: Almost no power or freedom to make decisions.*
 - *Not applicable.*
- **Could you explain the main reasons for your rating? What has (or has not) changed for women in your household?**

- **On which step of the ladder would you position the majority of men in your household today?**
 - *Step 5: Power and freedom to make all major life decisions.*
 - *Step 4: Power and freedom to make many major life decisions.*
 - *Step 3: Power and freedom to make some major life decisions.*
 - *Step 2: Only a small amount of power and freedom.*
 - *Step 1: Almost no power or freedom to make decisions.*
- **Could you explain the main reasons for your rating?**
- **On which step of the ladder would you position the majority of men in your household 10 years ago?**
 - *Step 5: Power and freedom to make all major life decisions.*
 - *Step 4: Power and freedom to make many major life decisions.*
 - *Step 3: Power and freedom to make some major life decisions.*
 - *Step 2: Only a small amount of power and freedom.*
 - *Step 1: Almost no power or freedom to make decisions.*
 - *Not applicable.*
- **Could you explain the main reasons for your rating? What has (or has not) changed for men in your household?**
- **On which step of the ladder would you position the majority of women in your community today?**
 - *Step 5: Power and freedom to make all major life decisions.*
 - *Step 4: Power and freedom to make many major life decisions.*
 - *Step 3: Power and freedom to make some major life decisions.*
 - *Step 2: Only a small amount of power and freedom.*
 - *Step 1: Almost no power or freedom to make decisions.*
- **Would you position different types of women in different places on this ladder? Older people, younger people, poorer people, single people, etc.?**
 - *I would place them in the same step on the ladder.*
 - *I would place them in different steps on the ladder.*
- **Could you explain how the placements would be the same or not.**
- **On which step of the ladder would you position the majority of men in your community today?**
 - *Step 5: Power and freedom to make all major life decisions.*
 - *Step 4: Power and freedom to make many major life decisions.*
 - *Step 3: Power and freedom to make some major life decisions.*
 - *Step 2: Only a small amount of power and freedom.*
 - *Step 1: Almost no power or freedom to make decisions.*
- **Would you position different types of men in different places on this ladder? Older people, younger people, poorer people, single people, etc.?**
 - *I would place them in the same step on the ladder.*
 - *I would place them in different steps on the ladder.*

- **Could you explain how the placements would be the same or not.**
- **Are there changes you would like to see to give women or men more power and freedom in the future? What would be needed to achieve this?**

4.3.4.3. Land tenure

- **Do you perceive that you could involuntarily lose ownership or use rights to any of the land you currently own or hold use rights to in the next 5 years?**
 - *Not at all*
 - *Slightly likely*
 - *Moderately likely*
 - *Very likely*
 - *Extremely likely*
- **What is the total area of your land that could be affected in hectares/acres?**
Hint: Please provide the area of total land.

4.3.4.4. Human wellbeing

I am now going to ask how satisfied you feel about specific aspects of your life. Please indicate how satisfied you feel about specific aspects of your life.

- **Think about your own life and personal circumstances, how satisfied are you with your life as a whole?**
 - *5 – Completely satisfied.*
 - *4 – Somewhat satisfied.*
 - *3 – Neutral.*
 - *2 – Somewhat dissatisfied*
 - *1 - Completely dissatisfied.*
 - *0 – I don't know.*
- **How satisfied are you with your standard of living?**
 - *5 - Completely satisfied.*
 - *4 - Somewhat satisfied.*
 - *3 - Neutral.*
 - *2 - Somewhat dissatisfied.*
 - *1 - Completely dissatisfied.*
 - *0 - I don't know.*
- **How satisfied are you with your health?**
 - *5 - Completely satisfied.*
 - *4 - Somewhat satisfied.*
 - *3 - Neutral.*
 - *2 - Somewhat dissatisfied.*
 - *1 - Completely dissatisfied.*
 - *0 - I don't know.*

○ **How satisfied are you with what you are achieving in life?**

- 5 - Completely satisfied.
- 4 - Somewhat satisfied.
- 3 - Neutral.
- 2 - Somewhat dissatisfied.
- 1 - Completely dissatisfied.
- 0 - I don't know.

○ **How satisfied are you with your personal relationships?**

- 5 - Completely satisfied.
- 4 - Somewhat satisfied.
- 3 - Neutral.
- 2 - Somewhat dissatisfied.
- 1 - Completely dissatisfied.
- 0 - I don't know.

○ **How satisfied are you with how safe you feel?**

Hint: meaning physical safety.

- 5 - Completely satisfied.
- 4 - Somewhat satisfied.
- 3 - Neutral.
- 2 - Somewhat dissatisfied.
- 1 - Completely dissatisfied.
- 0 - I don't know.

○ **How satisfied are you with feeling part of your community?**

Hint: meaning feeling of inclusivity, or sense of belongingness.

- 5 - Completely satisfied.
- 4 - Somewhat satisfied.
- 3 - Neutral.
- 2 - Somewhat dissatisfied.
- 1 - Completely dissatisfied.
- 0 - I don't know.

○ **How satisfied are you with your economic security?**

- 5 - Completely satisfied.
- 4 - Somewhat satisfied.
- 3 - Neutral.
- 2 - Somewhat dissatisfied.
- 1 - Completely dissatisfied.
- 0 - I don't know.

○ **How satisfied are you with your nutritional security?**

- 5 - Completely satisfied.

- 4 - Somewhat satisfied.
- 3 - Neutral.
- 2 - Somewhat dissatisfied.
- 1 - Completely dissatisfied.
- 0 - I don't know.

○ **How satisfied are you with the amount of time you have to do the things that you like doing?**

- 5 - Completely satisfied.
- 4 - Somewhat satisfied.
- 3 - Neutral.
- 2 - Somewhat dissatisfied.
- 1 - Completely dissatisfied.
- 0 - I don't know.

○ **How satisfied are you with the quality of your local environment?**

Hint: e.g. is the area free from pollution including water, air, industrial, or litter pollution?

- 5 - Completely satisfied.
- 4 - Somewhat satisfied.
- 3 - Neutral.
- 2 - Somewhat dissatisfied.
- 1 - Completely dissatisfied.
- 0 - I don't know.

○ **How satisfied are you with your occupation?**

- 5 - Completely satisfied.
- 4 - Somewhat satisfied.
- 3 - Neutral.
- 2 - Somewhat dissatisfied.
- 1 - Completely dissatisfied.
- 0 - I don't know.

Appendix 2. Farm-household level HOLPA field survey

➤ What types of data will you collect?

- Collect data on soil health from SOIL SAMPLES (SOC) and on biodiversity and crop health from visual inspection (30-60 mins) - recommended response
- Collect data on soil health using PARTICIPATORY METHODS (SOCLA) and on biodiversity and crop health from visual inspection (30-60 mins)
- Collect data on soil health from soil samples AND participatory methods (SOC and SOCLA) and on biodiversity and crop health from visual inspection (60+ mins)

4.3.5. Site 1

4.3.5.1. Biodiversity

Now you will collect data on tree diversity, landscape complexity, soil and crop health, from three locations on the farm, with the first close to buildings, the second surrounded by farmland, and the third close to natural vegetation, ideally. If you have an app that can record bird sounds, you can also collect data on bird diversity.

First, walk to a single point on the farmland (land actively used for crop or livestock production) that is near to the homestead or other houses/buildings. If the farm-household plots are dispersed, walk to the edge of the closest, accessible plot. Delineate a 10 x 10 meter square area with the centre of the square corresponding to the location you are standing.

- Take a GPS point of the location

If you have i-bird or another app for identifying birds from birdsong, activate the bird detection audio recording now

Turn in a 360 degree circle, observing all trees and natural or semi-natural vegetation that are inside an approximately 10 x 10 meter square area with the centre of the square corresponding to the location you are standing.

- Total number of trees observed
- Number of different tree species observed

- Number of native tree species
- Number of trees with a diameter at breast height greater than 10 cm
- Number of mature trees, defined loosely as those with a height >10m or diameter at breast height >50cm
- Spatial arrangement of the trees
 - *Trees are arranged in straight rows*
 - *Trees are scattered around the plot*
 - *Trees are clustered mainly or entirely in one part of the plot*
 - *There are no trees*
- Select all the natural or semi-natural vegetation features that you can see inside the 10 x 10 m sample plot
 - *Hedgerows/Live fences*
 - *Grass borders*
 - *Flower strips*
 - *Woodlots*
 - *Remnant forest patches*
 - *Wetlands, ponds, or lakes*
 - *Fallow land which is unproductive for at least 1 year*
 - *None*
 - *Other (please specify)*
- Approximately how much of the 10 x 10 m square sample plot is covered by natural or semi-natural vegetation
 - *None (0%)*
 - *1-10%*
 - *11-20%*
 - *21-30%*
 - *More than 30%*
- Staying at the centre of your 10 x 10 m square sample plot, look south and take a photograph
- Staying at the centre of your 10 x 10 m square sample plot, turn 90 degrees to the right and take a photograph
- Staying at the centre of your 10 x 10 m square sample plot, turn a further 90 degrees to the right and take a photograph
- Staying at the centre of your 10 x 10 m square sample plot, turn a further 90 degrees to the right and take a photograph

If you have i-bird or another app for identifying birds from birdsong, please stop the audio recording now. Save the recording with a unique identifier for the farm and sampling site, such as farm12-birds-site1

4.3.5.2. Soil health

- How diversified is the production system where you took the soil sample?
 - *Annual crops grown as monocultures (one crop type)*
 - *Annual crops grown in diversified systems (more than one crop type, or crops and trees or shrubs)*
 - *Perennial crops grown as monocultures (one crop type)*
 - *Perennial crops grown in diversified systems (more than one crop type, or crops and trees or shrubs)*
 - *Pasture without trees or shrubs*
 - *Pasture with trees or shrubs*
 - *Other (please specify)*

4.3.5.2.1. SOC methodology

Now, in the same 10x10m square plot used to assess biodiversity, please collect soil samples at five points corresponding to the plot centre and each corner of the plot. At the first sampling point, remove any crop residues from the soil surface. Use a small trowel to dig vertically to a depth of 10cm measured with a ruler (or insert the soil probe to 10cm), and place the removed soil into an sealable plastic bag. Repeat this process at the other four sampling points. Soil from each of the five sampling points should be put into the same bag. Seal the bag and label it with a unique name that identifies the farm and sample site, such as 'Farm12-Site1'

- Label on the soil bag

4.3.5.2.2. SOCLA methodology

In the same 10x10m square plot used to assess biodiversity, please examine the soil around you and jointly answer the following questions with the respondent. You should dig or pick up a small amount of soil to examine it more closely.

- In consultation with the respondent, describe the soil STRUCTURE
 - *Loose, powdery soil without visible aggregate*
 - *Soil with some aggregates that break with little pressure.*
 - *3. Few aggregates that break with little pressure*
 - *Soil with several well-formed aggregates that are difficult to break.*
 - *Well-formed aggregates that are difficult to break*
 - *I am not sure*

- In consultation with the respondent, describe the soil COMPACTION
 - *Compacted soil, flag bends readily when attempting to penetrate.*
 - *Soil with a moderately compacted layer, some resistance to a penetrating wire.*
 - *Thin compacted layer, with slight restrictions to a penetrating wire.*
 - *Soil with minimal compaction, little resistance to a penetrating wire.*
 - *No compaction, the flag can penetrate all the way into the soil easily.*
 - *I am not sure*

- In consultation with the respondent, describe the soil DEPTH
 - *Exposed subsoil, no superficial soil present.*
 - *Very shallow soil depth.*
 - *Thin superficial soil, approximately 5 cm.*
 - *Moderate soil depth, about 10 cm.*
 - *Significant superficial soil depth, more than >10 cm.*
 - *I am not sure*

- In consultation with the respondent, describe the soil STATUS OF RESIDUES
 - *Slowly decomposing organic residues.*
 - *Some partially decomposed residues from the previous year.*
 - *Presence of last year's decomposing residues*
 - *Residues in various stages of decomposition, with some well-decomposed.*
 - *Residues in various stages of decomposition, most residues well-decomposed*
 - *I am not sure*

- In consultation with the respondent, describe the soil COLOUR, ODOUR, ORGANIC MATTER
 - *Pale, chemical odour, and no presence of humus.*
 - *Light brown color, neutral or mild odor, and some presence of humus.*
 - *Light brown, odourless, and some presence of humus.*
 - *Dark brown color, fresh earthy odor, and a substantial amount of humus.*
 - *Dark brown, fresh odour, and abundant humus.*
 - *I am not sure*

- In consultation with the respondent, describe the soil MOISTURE

- *Dry soil, does not hold water.*
 - *Very low moisture level, unable to sustain plant growth.*
 - *Limited moisture level available for short time, may not support full plant needs.*
 - *Adequate moisture level for a moderate period of time, suitable for most plants.*
 - *Reasonable moisture level for a reasonable period of time, providing excellent conditions for plant growth.*
 - *I am not sure.*
- **In consultation with the respondent, describe the soil COVER**
- *Bare soil, no residues or live cover present.*
 - *Less than 25% soil covered by residues or live cover.*
 - *Approximately 25% to 50% of the soil covered by residues or live cover.*
 - *Approximately 51% to 75% of the soil covered by residues or live cover.*
 - *More than 75% soil covered by residues or live cover*
 - *I am not sure.*
- **In consultation with the respondent, describe the soil EROSION**
- *Severe erosion, presence of small gullies and noticeable soil loss.*
 - *Moderate erosion signs, with some minor gullies or soil disturbance.*
 - *Evident, but low erosion signs, such as slight soil displacement and small rills.*
 - *Minimal erosion signs, with only slight indications of soil disturbance.*
 - *No visible signs of erosion, with the soil surface largely intact and undisturbed.*
 - *I am not sure.*
- **In consultation with the respondent, describe the soil INTERVEBRATE ACTIVITY**
- *No signs of invertebrate presence of activity observed.*
 - *Very few earthworms and arthropods present, with minimal activity.*
 - *A few earthworms and arthropods present, with minimal activity.*
 - *Moderate presence of invertebrate organisms, with noticeable activity in the soil.*
 - *Abundant presence of invertebrate organisms, indicating active and healthy soil life.*
 - *I am not sure*
- **In consultation with the respondent, describe the soil MICROBIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY**
- *Very little effervescence after application of water peroxide*
 - *Low effervescence observed*
 - *Light to medium effervescence*
 - *Moderate effervescence noticed*
 - *Abundant effervescence*

- *I am not sure*

4.3.5.3. Crop and pasture health

Now, in the same 10x10m square plot used to assess biodiversity and soil, please observe the crops and/or pasture present in the plot and jointly asking the following questions with the respondent (if present).

- In consultation with the respondent, describe the crop/pasture APPEARANCE

Hint: Use this image as reference

- 1. Discolored foliage with severe deficiency signs
 - 2. Discolored foliage with moderate deficiency signs
 - 3. Foliage with some deficiency signs
 - 4. Foliage with very minor deficiency signs
 - 5. Healthy foliage with no signs of deficiency
 - *I am not sure, or the question is not applicable*
- In consultation with the respondent, describe the crop/pasture GROWTH
 - 1. Uneven plant heights with limited new growth
 - 2. Uneven plant heights with some new growth
 - 3. Mainly even plant heights with limited new growth
 - 4. Mainly even plant heights with some new growth
 - 5. Even plant heights and vigorous new growth
 - *I am not sure, or the question is not applicable*
- In consultation with the respondent, describe the crop/pasture DISEASE INCIDENCE

Hint: Use this image as reference

- 1. 76-100% of plants have damaged stems, leaves and/or fruits
- 2. 51-75% of plants have damaged stems, leaves and/or fruits
- 3. 26-50% of plants have damaged stems, leaves and/or fruits
- 4. 6-25% of plants have damaged stems, leaves and/or fruits
- 5. ≤5% of plants have damaged stems, leaves and/or fruits
- I am not sure, or the question is not applicable

➤ In consultation with the respondent, describe the crop/pasture INSECT PEST INCIDENCE
 Hint: Use this image as reference

- 1. Very dense insect pest coverage on plant stems, leaves and/or fruits
- 2. Dense insect pest coverage on plant stems, leaves and/or fruits
- 3. Moderately dense insect pest coverage on plant stems, leaves and/or fruits
- 4. Sparse insect pest coverage on plant stems, leaves and/or fruits
- 5. No or very sparse signs of insect pests on plant stems, leaves and/or fruits
- I am not sure, or the question is not applicable

- In consultation with the respondent, describe the crop/pasture **NATURAL ENEMY ABUNDANCE**
 - *No presence of pest predators on plant stems, leaves and/or fruits*
 - *Sparse presence of pest predators on plant stems, leaves and/or fruits*
 - *Moderate presence of pest predators on plant stems, leaves and/or fruits*
 - *Dense presence of pest predators on plant stems, leaves and/or fruits*
 - *Very dense presence of pest predators on plant stems, leaves and/or fruits*
 - *I am not sure, or the question is not applicable*

- In consultation with the respondent, describe the crop/pasture **WEED PRESSURE**
 - *Crops stressed and overwhelmed by weeds*
 - *Crops growing well but starting to be overcome by weeds*
 - *Moderate presence of weeds with some competition*
 - *Low presence of weeds*
 - *Vigorous crop that overcomes weeds*
 - *I am not sure, or the question is not applicable*

- In consultation with the respondent, describe the **NATURAL SURROUNDING VEGETATION**
 - *Surrounded by other crops or pasture with no natural vegetation nearby*
 - *Surrounded by other crops or pasture with some natural vegetation nearby, such as inside fields or at field edge*
 - *Adjacent to sparse or limited natural vegetation on at least one side*
 - *Adjacent to dense or expansive natural vegetation on at least one side*
 - *Adjacent to natural vegetation on at least two sides*
 - *I am not sure, or the question is not applicable*

- In consultation with the respondent, describe the **MANAGEMENT SYSTEM**
 - *High chemical pesticide and/or fertilizer inputs; conventional tillage*
 - *Moderate chemical pesticide and/or fertilizer inputs; conventional tillage*
 - *Moderate chemical pesticide and/or fertilizer inputs; reduced or no tillage*
 - *No or low chemical pesticide and/or fertilizer inputs; reduced or no tillage*
 - *No chemical inputs; reduced or no tillage*
 - *I am not sure, or the question is not applicable*

4.3.6. Site 2

4.3.6.1. Biodiversity

Now, walk to a second point, this time at the centre of the farmland (land actively used for crop or livestock production) or as close as feasible to this, and ideally away from any houses or buildings. If the farm-household plots are dispersed, walk to the centre of the largest, accessible plot. Delineate a 10 x 10 meter square area with the centre of the square corresponding to the location you are standing.

.....

4.3.6.2. Soil health

4.3.6.2.1. SOC methodology

Now, in the same 10x10m square plot used to assess biodiversity, please collect soil samples at five points corresponding to the plot centre and each corner of the plot. At the first sampling point, remove any crop residues from the soil surface. Use a small trowel to dig vertically to a depth of 10cm measured with a ruler (or insert the soil probe to 10cm), and place the removed soil into a sealable plastic bag. Repeat this process at the other four sampling points. Soil from each of the five sampling points should be put into the same bag. Seal the bag and label it with a unique name that identifies the farm and sample site, such as 'Farm12-Site2'

...

4.2.2.2. SOCLA methodology

In the same 10x10m square plot used to assess biodiversity, please examine the soil around you and jointly answer the following questions with the respondent. You should dig or pick up a small amount of soil to examine it more closely.

...

4.3.6.3. Crop and pasture health

Now, in the same 10x10m square plot used to assess biodiversity, please observe the crops and/or pasture present in the plot and jointly asking the following questions with the respondent (if present).

...

4.3.7. Site 3

4.3.7.1. Biodiversity

Now, walk to a third point, this time at the edge of the farmland (land actively used for crop or livestock production) choosing an edge that is near to natural vegetation, if possible. If the farm-household plots are dispersed, walk to the edge of the most accessible plot that is nearest to

natural vegetation and furthest from human settlements. Delineate a 10 x 10 meter square area** with the centre of the square corresponding to the location you are standing.

...

4.3.7.2. Soil health

4.3.7.2.1. SOC methodology

Now, in the same 10x10m square plot used to assess biodiversity, please collect soil samples at five points corresponding to the plot centre and each corner of the plot. At the first sampling point, remove any crop residues from the soil surface. Use a small trowel to dig vertically to a depth of 10cm measured with a ruler (or insert the soil probe to 10cm), and place the removed soil into a sealable plastic bag. Repeat this process at the other four sampling points. Soil from each of the five sampling points should be put into the same bag. Seal the bag and label it with a unique name that identifies the farm and sample site, such as 'Farm12-Site2'

4.3.7.2.2. SOCLA methodology

In the same 10x10m square plot used to assess biodiversity, please examine the soil around you and jointly answer the following questions with the respondent. You should dig or pick up a small amount of soil to examine it more closely.

...

4.3.7.3. Crop and pasture health

Now, in the same 10x10m square plot used to assess biodiversity, please observe the crops and/or pasture present in the plot and jointly asking the following questions with the respondent (if present).

...

Appendix 3. Data collection using KoboCollect

If you do not already have a KoboCollect account, go to <https://www.kobotoolbox.org/> and set up a new account with your own username and password.

On an android tablet or smartphone, download the KoboCollect app (or if you already have it installed, make sure you have the latest version).

Login to the app from your tablet using your personal username and password.

Now follow the instructions below.

To download, fill in, and submit the standard HOLPA survey:

1. Click on **Settings** (top right logo)

2. Click on **Add projects.**

3. Scan QR code

Obs: grant camera permission (if required in prompt)

The QR code should automatically import the Holpa project into your device. If this doesn't work, you will need to add the project manually. To do this, select 'Manually enter project details' and enter the url.

Click 'Add' (bottom right).

4. Click on **Get blank form**

DRAFT

5. Select the latest survey version (normally the one at the bottom of the list, but if in doubt check the version number and timestamp to find the most recent). A check mark should appear on the right.
6. Click on Get selected (bottom right)

7. Click **Fill blank form**

8. Select the required form

9. Complete the form.

10. You can save a partially finished form at any time. To edit a saved form, select **'Edit saved form'**.

11. After completing the form, click **'Send Finalized Form'**.

12. Your sent forms will appear on KoboToolbox (the KoboCollect server) accessible only to users granted full access rights (i.e. you can choose whether all enumerators have access to the full dataset, or only selected members of the country team).